

Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the artistic crafts industry

Authors

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Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the artistic crafts industry

Project name	Creative Industries Cultural Economy Production Network
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Work package	<p>The CICERONE project consists of seven work packages (WPs). This report is part of WP2, which constitutes the empirical backbone of the project. WP2 contains case study research that focuses on networked production in eight cultural and creative industries: 1) architecture, 2) archives (including libraries and cultural heritage), 3) artistic crafts, 4) audio-visual media (film, TV, videogames, multimedia) and radio, 5) design, 6) festivals, as well as performing and visual arts, 7) music and, 8) publishing. The purpose of the case study research is to understand key linkages and mechanisms within real-life production networks in the cultural and creative sector (CCS) and the relationships of these networks to context-dependent variables.</p> <p>Drawing on the case study research, the CICERONE project explores a policy framework that may contribute to enhancing policy support for the cultural and creative sectors. Furthermore, the case study research facilitates the identification of gaps in extant sources of quantitative data, suggesting approaches on how these gaps can be plugged. For this reason, WP2 is not just the empirical backbone of CICERONE, it also provides critical inputs for the work in other WPs (most notably WP4 and WP6).</p> <p>This deliverable (D2.3) reports on the case studies on the artistic crafts industry. Together with the reports D2.1, D2.2, D2.4 to D2.8, it provides strategic snapshots of the rich and variegated tapestry of European production networks in the CCS.</p> <p>All the deliverables from the CICERONE project are publicly disclosed on the project's website www.cicerone-project.eu and through its Zenodo community on https://zenodo.org/communities/cicerone-h2020.</p>

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Executive summary

This report is part of a series of work package reports which performs a sector analysis of Europe's creative and cultural sector (CCS), utilising the innovative global production network (GPN) approach as a theoretical framework. It is situated within the larger multidisciplinary EU Horizon 2020-funded CICERONE research project, which has undertaken case study research in nine different sectors under the CCS umbrella (audio-visual, festivals, performance and visual arts, music, publishing, museums & heritage, architecture, fashion, videogames, and craft) in eight European countries. This report is the result of a sector analysis of the crafts industry.

In the context of the European CCS, craft undoubtedly represents a unique case. The industry is of high relevance for the EU, not only at the economic level but also at the social and cultural levels. Craft represents one of the most significant activities for the EU's economy, accounting for approximately 8.6 million enterprises, which represents 37.2% of the total population of the EU's non-financial business economy; at the social and cultural levels, there is no doubt that the industry – due to its deep-rooted tradition in most of EU Member States – plays a key-role in forging the rich and diverse European cultural identity.

In recent years, craft has experienced a substantial rediscovery, both as an economic and commercial industry. Although collocated in an extremely fluid global economy, these activities maintain a special relation with the place where crafted products are created and are often indicated as drivers of local development and urban regeneration. According to some scholars, craft represents a response to the challenges of globalisation because it constitutes a local, human, and sustainable alternative to large-scale manufacturing production, which is able to sustain lean, flexible, high-quality, and innovative production.

The interest of EU institutions in this industry has been confirmed by several projects funded under various research programmes, which have investigated the issues related to competitiveness, skills and education, innovation, and digital transformations that affect craft activities. Among these projects, the CICERONE project adopts the GPN approach and the case study methodology to examine the spatial and governance configurations of the craft industry.

Approaching the craft industry with the GPN methodology means accounting for the whole production network of the industry. What the GPN approach makes clear is that artisanal goods are the result of cooperation among various actors – sometimes located in dispersed territories – who contribute to creating and enhancing the value incorporated into the final product.

In this report, three different production networks of crafts in two different countries of the EU – namely Italy and Sweden – are investigated. To set the scene for these case studies, an in-depth literature review into the conditions of the European craft industry is conducted, which provides a

comprehensive view of the contemporary European craft industry. The literature review also helps to identify the governance models of the craft industry, which provides the background for selecting the cases.

Craft as a CCS represents a wide range of activities, where smaller batches of highly skilled production, deep knowledge of materials, tradition, and artistic intent are the basis of the value of the produced goods – often produced by self-employed craftspeople or in smaller firms. The literature review aims to unpack this complexity and present a framework for understanding crafts and artisanal production.

The first part of the literature review unpacks the nature of crafted goods, which due to the breadth of the industry (including activities ranging from ceramics, wood working, and smithing to luxury artisanal production and smaller industrial production) makes the industry complex and difficult to define. Building on this discussion, we present the varied labour conditions of contemporary craftspeople as well as the skills necessary for operating within the industry. The conditions for working and operating craft activities are influenced by local, national, and European-level policies, which are discussed from the perspective of a small and medium-sized business as well as that of initiatives directly targeted towards craft activities. Due to the lack of a shared, formal definition of what a craft enterprise is at the EU level, the policy framework for the craft industry is constituted by policies directed to micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises; more specific and tailored policies are designed and adopted at national and local levels. The policy interventions as well as the understanding of what craft entails differ between European countries, where tradition and local embeddedness can shape the structure of the industry.

Basing our understanding on the literature review, we are able to produce an input–output structure of the industry and identify five different models of governance for how craft products are made, moving from creation to a final consumer. The models of governance feed into our choices of case studies, which represent three of the models. The first case study is on Prisma, an Italian artisanal luxury yacht manufacturer located in Liguria and Tuscany. Here, craft is observed within a broader production network, illustrating in which ways it can contribute to luxury production. This project reflects the production network governance model. The second case study is on Konsthantverkarna, a membership-based organisation that gathers approximately 90 artisans using different materials and from different parts of Sweden. The case is chosen as it is an organisation of 90 independent artisans who follow the market governance model. The third case study is on a traditional glass manufacturing site located in a cluster of glass activities in southern Sweden. It reflects the vertically integrated governance model.

Through case-study research, with a main emphasis on qualitative interviews, we unpack the production networks of each case, highlighting the relationships between actors and the power relationships between them, as well as the embeddedness of the cases towards various institutions, networks, and places. Through this analysis and the application of the GPN approach, we present key research results and policy implications.

First, the research highlights that craft activities produce crucial economic and (especially) social tangible and intangible impacts – among which are the contribution to local development, particularly in rural regions; the activation of complementary industries such as tourism; and the nurture of both local and European collective identity. Second, unveiling the geographical reach of the craft networks investigated, the research highlights the geographical embeddedness of knowledge and skills, where areas that contain these artisanal clusters have over decades, and even centuries, developed infrastructure, educational institutions, and local know-how that anchor these industries in one place, where they are difficult to substitute to other regions. Third, despite its variety in terms of possible business models and the new sectoral trends, evidence from the research points to the continued relevance of the traditional mechanisms of reputation and trust that characterise the various business practices – and which seem to qualify all of the phases along the production networks.

The research has nonetheless raised several critical points, which are relevant to policy makers. First, although artisans and craft enterprises are generally indicated to be key actors for value creation and the realisation of high-quality products, they do not seem to harvest adequate material and symbolic compensation for their work. Even in the context of horizontal or multiple-actor networks, artisans and craft enterprises seem to be the weakest nodes of the production network. This is particularly true when considering the role and function of second-tier suppliers – whose conditions raise serious concerns in terms of working conditions and rights – and of self-employed craftspeople – who seem to be exposed to self-exploitative tendencies. Second, due to their participation in extra-local production networks, artisans are exposed to new competitive pressures, accelerated by the presence of global competitors and the transformations ongoing throughout the industry. Among these transformations, sustainability plays a critical role – seemingly constituting the new *cleavage* around which lies the competitive equilibrium upon which the next few years will be built. To remain competitive and sustainable, craftspeople and craft enterprises demand more adequate and tailored policy actions. Third, artisans and craft enterprises need substantial interventions in the fields of employment, grants, and training/skills; enterprises blame excessive tax burdens on labour and demand more attention to the recruitment of new generations of artisans. Fourth, the absence of policies that promote the protection and reproduction of the unique skills and know-how that characterise the craft industry – especially in niche production and traditional or artistic crafts – exposes the whole industry to the loss of competences and talents that are almost impossible to replace. This makes the craft industry susceptible to crises in ways that other manufacturing industries are not.

Keywords

Global production network (GPN), creative and cultural sector (CCS), artistic craft, traditional craft, craft manufacturing, leisure boat industry, glass making

Introduction

In recent years, the craft industry has received increasing interest from consumers, policy makers, and researchers. The industry comprises a wide range of activities, from artistic and traditional crafts to ceramics and leatherwork, from woodwork to boatbuilding, and from 3D printing to repair activities, among many others. The definition of craft depends on the framework within which it is used – and it is constantly evolving. Craft is a creative and cultural industry that has tended to be overshadowed by others, yet it is undoubtedly a unique case due not only to its economic, social, and cultural relevance but also to the specific features that characterise it. Based on these considerations, in this report, we choose not to limit our investigations to just one typology of crafts (namely, the artistic one) and we consider a wider area of artisanal activities whose analysis seem to be of great scientific interest.

investigate a wider area in which different and challenging definitions of craftsmanship can coexist. This report, part of the Horizon 2020—the lens of the global production funded CICERONE project, aims to unveil how the craft industry functions through network (GPN) approach. Such an approach is a heuristic tool developed to understand and analyse the spatial, social, and economic features of geographically dispersed and multi-actor production networks. Applied for the first time to the cultural and creative sectors, the approach allows a deep understanding of why certain activities of production networks occur in certain places as well as why value is captured at certain nodes. The analysis is driven by an overview of the industry and, through case study research in Italy and Sweden, unpacks the production networks of a highly skilled, traditional manufacturing boating company with deep historical connections (first case study), an artistic crafts-type organisation (second case study), and a glass factory (third case study). The three case studies reflect the following three governance models: the production network governance model, the market governance model, and the vertically integrated governance model, respectively.

The industrial report starts after a focused introduction to the GPN approach, which clarifies the key theoretical and epistemological aspects that instruct the CICERONE project. The methodological implications are detailed in both the report and the methodological appendix.

The report is organised as follows. In Part 1, an overview of the European production network of the craft industry is presented, which explores the great variety in the industry. Key information is provided regarding the goods and services that characterise this industry as well as the embeddedness of craft enterprises, labour conditions, and policy issues. Part 2 provides a statistical mapping of the industry at the EU level based on Eurostat data and integrated by a national dataset. Finally, Part 3 discusses the case studies selected by the Italian and Swedish research units.

The CICERONE approach to production networks

The point of departure for the analysis of the CCS is the Global Production Network (GPN) approach, which was developed by Neil Coe and Henry Yeung starting from the Global Value Chain (GVC) approach elaborated by Gereffi in 1994 (Coe & Yeung, 2015; Greco, 2016; Kloosterman, Pratt, D’Ovidio, Greco & Borén, 2019). The GPN approach has been used to unravel production networks that involve a complex cross-border spatial division of labour. Such production networks have proliferated across many sectors as a consequence of technological advances in communication and transport as well as due to the liberalisation and deregulation of trade (Kano et al. 2020). These processes have also affected (many) CCSs. However, the GPN approach has rarely been applied to them (Coe, 2015 is an exception). By opting for this innovative approach to the CCS, the CICERONE project generated new insights on its functioning.

In a sense, we have used the GPN method to spatialise. Sociological approaches were already proposed by Howard Becker (Becker, 1982), with his concept of the *art world*, and by Pierre Bourdieu (Bourdieu, 1996), who developed the concept of *field*. Both approaches, the differences between them notwithstanding (Buttero & Crossley, 2011), aim at embedding the process of creation into a broader societal setting and at going beyond the identification of individual genius. When we use the GPN approach, we cannot simply position the CCS in that broad context – we must also highlight its spatial footprint. We thus employ the GPN approach as a tool for analysing a wide variety of production networks in the CCS. In other words, the approach is a heuristic tool that explains how the products of the CCS progress from inception to sale and whether and how they may be preserved for future generations.

On the pages that follow, we first briefly summarise the key elements of the GPN approach that guided our fieldwork. Thereafter, we focus on the process by which we selected the units of analysis for our case studies. This section is followed by an explanation of the manner in which our sample of case studies lays the foundation for a concise typology of the CCS which can be used by policymakers to devise more targeted combinations of interventions to foster economic growth and employment as well as social and cultural diversity.

Key elements of the GPN approach

Phases and the spatial footprint

Evidently, the most obvious feature of the GPN approach is the carving up of the value chain into distinct value-adding stages which can unfold in different locations and which may involve different sets of actors (including other firms). We have inserted the archiving phase into the value-adding stages because many (if not all) of those who participate in cultural and creative endeavours draw on the works of their predecessors in one way or another (Pratt, 1997). Therefore, in the CICERONE project, we, in principle, distinguish between the following stages:

- 1) Creation (the initial conception of an idea or a set of ideas that define aesthetic quality),
- 2) Production (the realisation of those ideas through an actual good or service),
- 3) Distribution (sale of a good or the presentation of a service in front of an audience),
- 4) Exchange (the wider setting which enables distribution),
- 5) Archiving (the formal preservation of the cultural product).

Creation

It is in this part of the cycle that new ideas, processes or approaches are devised. The notion of “creation”, in the sense in which the term is used here, is a social one – what is new is also relational, situated and conditional. Therefore, a “creative process”, that is, a method, is involved (“design” is an example). Reference is also made to history and to previous instances of creation (the preceding stage). Sometimes, this is referred to as “ideation”, that is, having ideas.

Production

An idea or a creative new thing remains provisional, potential and conditional until it can be stabilised or made. The intervening period is often called prototype stage. Usually, the product is also developed during the multiple (or mass) production phase. Technology and labour costs, production decisions, and technological and regulatory standards affect costs and potential access to the products. Marketing and advertising are also relevant, but we allocate them to the exchange phase here.

Distribution or circulation

Products, even if they are new and unusual, are unformed and inaccessible unless they can be moved or migrated to markets or audiences. Physical distribution is clearly a key issue for access and reach. The same is true of digital approaches, which may overcome some barriers. Generally, distribution systems (or platforms) are expensive to develop and susceptible to monopoly control.

Exchange

Exchange is the stage at which the product or service engages the audience or customers. It is a critical moment of information exchange, and one in which (e)valuation occurs. That (e)valuation may take forms as varied as market transaction, participation or critique. Values are made and stabilised at this stage. Therefore, marketing and expectation setting provide a link to distribution. In the experience economy, and particularly in the cultural one, the negotiation of value is a critical element of the transaction, and institutions have been developed that normalise it and reduce risks. The engagement of the audience or consumer is also shaped directly by advertising and marketing – to refer to the previous stages once more, the exchange process can determine which products are available for production and distribution.

Archiving

Since cultural value is relational, history and cultural diversity always interact with the present. Moreover, the process of reflection and learning (or that of rejection) is part of the critical appreciation

of culture. The archiving of culture creates both normative structures that enable cultural production systems and the disruptive elements that facilitate new approaches. This stage also includes education (of audiences or consumers as well as of creative practitioners), institutions such as universities and media systems, and repositories such as libraries, museums and galleries. It is at this point that heritage is identified and later mobilised via the production system. More generally, archiving constitutes the resource from which new ideas are developed, which refers back to creation.

Source: D'Ovidio et al., 2019

We treat this model of the phases as a *point of departure*, not as a given, and we employ the case studies to explore the extent to which these distinctions may explain production in the CCS. As Throsby (Throsby, 2010, p. 25) observed, in some production processes in the CCS, there is no simple and neat sequence, and “[t]he apparent linearity of the value chain may be replaced, for some cultural products, by something more akin to a value network, where multiple inputs, feedback loops, and a pervasive ‘value-creating ecology’ replaces a simple stage-wise process”. Although he was rightly critical of the slavish application of a value chain approach to the CCS, he also observed that “[f]rom a policy point of view, depicting the cultural production process as a value chain allows an analysis of the effects of policy intervention at various points in the chain. For example, in assessing the impacts of existing policy measures, or in determining the optimal point at which to apply prospective measures, the policy analyst can use the value-chain concept to clarify where the effects of intervention have been or will be felt, and who are the affected stakeholders upstream or downstream from the point of intervention”.

It therefore stands to reason that one should start with the conceptual framework of these stages and then determine which phases can be identified as distinct, which boundaries are blurred and which phases overlap or are deeply intertwined. Subsequently, we locate phases or combinations of phases – the spatial footprint – and we identify the parties that are involved. In this manner, we extend our focus beyond creation to include other parts of the input-output structure of the CCS.

Governance

The second element that we derive from the GPN approach and which we use to open the black box of the production network is the concept of governance. The complex global value chains and production networks which have been studied (mostly in manufacturing) typically exhibit asymmetrical power structures, with one lead firm engaging in explicit coordination (Gereffi, 2005). This lead firm may be involved in the production phase (producer-driven chain) or in the distribution phase (buyer-driven chain). If power dynamics are asymmetric and a lead firm takes charge of coordinating the network, it may be inferred that it is capable of forcing the other actors to act in a certain way but also that it can capture much of the value that is created in the network. Similarly to our approach to the stages, we do not take the existence of a lead firm in the CCS for granted. Instead, we attempt to identify a more explicit hierarchical power distribution or a more dispersed horizontal one. Furthermore, we do not assume that the presence of a lead firm or actor necessarily results in an asymmetrical distribution of (economic) value, and we examine this issue as a research question.

Embeddedness

The third element that we use to understand the production networks of the CCS is that of embeddedness. In his seminal work on the transformation of the British economy in the 19th century, Karl Polanyi (Polanyi, 1957) emphasised the importance of the institutional context in which all economic actions are embedded. In this context, differences in embeddedness affect economic actions, the likelihood of their occurrence, the manner in which they unfold and their consequences (Granovetter, 1985). This view became widespread in economic sociology, organisation studies, strategic management (Smelser & Swedberg, 2005) and, somewhat later, in economic geography. The GPN approach explicitly aims to apply embeddedness to make sense of the spatial footprint of the production network: why are such-and-such activities located in such-and-such places? According to Kleiber and Horner (Kleibert & Horner, 2018), the operations of actors within the same universalistic category of a transnational production system is very much contingent on their embeddedness in a particular society, place and social network. Embeddedness thus becomes crucial for understanding the spatial and social division of labour within a production network. The forms of embeddedness are also critical for the design of effective policies for the CCS (Salder, 2022).

We have adopted the multi-layered approach to embeddedness that Coe and Yeung (2015) proposed. We therefore distinguish between three levels of embeddedness.

- i. Societal embeddedness: the influence of institutional contexts on the actions taken by actors in production networks (rules, laws and regulations) which are mainly located at the EU level and the national level.
- ii. Territorial embeddedness: the local context of the location where a certain activity takes place, which is closely related to local clusters and ecosystems with distinct sets of agglomeration economies that selectively sustain and foster economic activities (Scott, 2000).
- iii. Network embeddedness: the linkages between different actors and the functional and social connectivity of those relationships (e.g. social network relationships based on trust).

As with the phases, the boundaries between these forms of embeddedness are not set in stone. Place-based communities are an essential element of agglomeration economies, but they are also closely linked to social networks. We analyse these levels of embeddedness more comprehensively .

Unit of analysis

The CCS are characterized by their emphasis on unique aesthetic qualities and, importantly, on near-infinite horizontal differentiation (Caves, 2000), volatile (cross-sectoral) cooperation, and, crucially, forms of collaboration that are often ad hoc and usually involve several actors with different skills and functions. Those forms of collaboration often permeate the legal boundaries of firms. This particular way of producing involves, as a result, “complex teams – the motley crew property”, as well as “close temporal coordination of their activities” (Caves, 2000, p.8). Watson (Watson, 2012, p. 617) added

that “[t]he complexity of the [jointly produced product or service] necessitates the coordination of multidisciplinary skills” and that permanent centralisation is not economically efficient (Lorenzen & Frederiksen, 2005). Production must often be completed under severe time constraints (Hobday, 2000; Staber, 2004) Temporary networks, interpersonal collaboration and projects in the CCS are therefore very much intertwined. As de Klerk (de Klerk, 2015, p. 829) observed, “*[t]he dynamic environment in the industry is mostly project-based... thus often obliging these workers to find alternative employment between projects to optimise their limited work opportunities. Bricolage results from working arrangements structured by festivals or special assignments where creative workers move in and out of networks as they are needed*”.

The GPN approach has mainly been used to analyse the large-scale production of goods. Some CCSs, such as parts of the fashion industry, seem to fit this format of production well. However, at least some CCS activities are different from the usual subjects of the GPN literature, which tends to focus on production networks in which large firms manufacture large volumes of standardised goods. In other segments, small firms predominate. Instead of churning out many similar (tangible) products, they focus on creating products, such as goods and services, in small numbers (often just one) that require production networks to be more or less ad hoc. The composition of those networks typically fluctuates. A performance, a song or an album, a painting and the design of a theatre are all unique products which are typically created by such ad hoc production networks that vary from product to product (Power & Hallencreutz, 2002; Power & Jansson, 2004; Pratt, 2006).

It must be noted that projects in some CCSs are less volatile (for example, the spring and summer collection and the autumn and winter collection of a large fashion firm, which may involve the same designers, suppliers and sellers). Therefore, they resemble the type of networks which are prominent in the GPN literature. In other CCSs, such as architectural design or festivals, the composition of the networks is much more variable and contextual, and sequences of projects may have different networks and stakeholders.

In order to cover production networks in the CCS that are volatile and project based, we focus in most case studies on projects as a unit of analysis. This approach is very much in line with the literature on the forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. In more recent economic-geographic studies and in sociological research on CCS, project-based work, which involves a multiplicity of organisational and personal social networks, is a key component of the analysis (see Watson, 2012 for a very thorough overview). Notably, studies on labour conditions in the CCS have benefited from departing from the project-based approach. The important role of project-based work has been corroborated in many CCSs (de Klerk, 2015).

In the CCS, then, the firm should not be granted a privileged ontological status. Instead, networks should be central. One could even go a step further and conceptualise the firm as a more permanent or sustained project or as a collection of long-term projects (although it is evidently subject to recombination and change) that has been solidified into a legal entity. The temporal dimension of the project and therefore of its network then become a crucial variable for the case studies. This shift

evidently dovetails into our GPN approach, which emphasises the role of networks. In the CICERONE project, we conceive of these networks not *a priori* in terms of firms but in terms of interpersonal networks that are organised around a specific project. In *Art Worlds*, Howard Becker also highlighted interpersonal relationships (Becker, 1982). Our focus also allows us to emphasise the role of cultural value, which may trump economic value, and the salience of motives other than profit maximisation, especially in the creation phase. These distinguishing features of the CCS have significant consequences for the functioning of its production networks.

A more practical advantage of circling on specific projects is that it enabled us to select respondents more easily – we could simply focus on those individuals who were involved in a given project. It then also became easier to limit the number of respondents (only project-related key or lead actors or firms, strategic partners, strategic suppliers and key customers) that we had to consider.

Selection of cases

The main purpose of the CICERONE project is to provide a new foundation for CCS policies on the basis of a production network approach that generates novel insights on the functioning of the CCS and its cultural and social impact. Our approach situates the CCS in networks of production that extend far beyond the creation phase. We use case studies to map the configuration of production networks and to analyse relationships between actors in creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving. The case studies are thus intended to uncover linkages and mechanisms within these production networks and to lay the foundation for more informed policies which not only extend beyond the creation phase but also take spatial footprints and governance structures into account.

Business models within the CCS vary widely. That variance obtains not only across industries but also within them. There are differences in staff numbers, turnover, type of products, barriers to entry, the use of technology, capital needs, end markets and strategies, to name but a few. Networks also differ in terms of power relationships, shape and organisation, and the nature, complexity and geography of their linkages. At present, no data sets cover these characteristics comprehensively. Representative sampling is certainly not feasible within the timeframe of the CICERONE project. The investigation of the variance in question, accordingly, is a voyage into uncharted waters.

We have therefore opted for a purposive selection of cases, whereby researchers select the units to be sampled on the basis of their knowledge, which in our case is the background research that we conducted prior to the cases studies. The aim of this selection was to include cases which may plausibly be assumed to represent a sufficient range of easily assessable variations in key business model characteristics, notably staffing and turnover. This approach yielded cases that typify a significant proportion of the population of the CCS while also exhibiting sufficient differences to represent its variability (Gerring, 2007). In the case study reports that follow, each case study is positioned within the wider industry.

Typology matrix

While the case studies are intended to present a rich picture of the key mechanisms and the main linkages that show how spatial footprints, governance structures and levels of embeddedness are intertwined in real-life situations, a higher level of abstraction that transcends the study of individual production networks must be accessed if general insights are to be derived. We must simplify characteristics and relationships in order to present a clear narrative for policymakers. The key elements of our approach – spatial footprints, governance structures and multi-layered embeddedness – guided us in reducing the complexity of the case studies so as to distil insights from findings.

The first step is to position concrete cases from the CCS in a simple grid which combines the spatial footprint with the governance structure. The two variables are crucial determinants of societal effects. A completely local production network with a horizontal governance structure and a mainly global and hierarchical network that is coordinated by a lead firm or actor differ starkly in their social, economic and cultural impact and in the policy interventions that they require. Furthermore, if creation is local but production and distribution are global, targeting policy only at the creation phase may have unforeseen consequences for the wider network.

In principle, the typology matrix of production networks distinguishes between different phases. Since these phases may overlap, as is the case of many forms of visual art, they may be merged. For each phase or set of phases, it is possible to determine whether a single actor is in charge of all activities. Different phases may then exhibit different governance structures. It may also be the case that one actor is ultimately in charge of the whole network and is clearly present in the coordination of each phase. Alternatively, a small number of actors may control the network. The typology matrix allows more nuanced representations of this kind. Using this typology matrix enables us to draw cross-industrial comparisons between cases and therefore to depart from the conventional siloed approaches. We expect that certain combinations will transpire to be much more likely to occur than others: the likelihood of a small local network having a more horizontal governance structure is evidently much higher than that of a complex and truly global network adopting such a form of governance, which requires much more extensive coordination.

CCSs are embedded in multi-layered contexts, which range from the EU and the national level to that of the territorial and social network. Our empirical work shows how these contexts affect individual cases. Cross-case analysis shows how the forms of embeddedness are related to the typology matrix more generally. Power relations, for instance, may also depend on institutional conditions. Those conditions may allow an actor to assume leadership or to take advantage of the network.

This typology matrix is a starting point for an exploration of the potential role of hard policy levers (e.g. tax breaks, subsidies and such like) and soft policy levers (e.g. strengthening the institutional framework, establishing platforms for collaboration, improving education and so on) that various policymakers at different spatial levels may in principle manipulate. Policy makers can use this

typology matrix as a tool for assessing the key characteristics of the concrete CCS populations, which may be defined narrowly or widely, whose societal impact they wish to improve. Filling this typology matrix clearly also requires new sets of data which allow the larger CCS populations to be profiled.

The typology matrix is crucial to constructing an overarching narrative that transcends the idiosyncrasies of individual cases. Moreover, it supplies a basis for our policy recommendations, which are phase and location specific and must be sensitive to the organisation of network governance. We strove for high uniformity to enable comparisons. We present a guide to achieving that goal below.

It is often difficult to compress information for a whole production network on the spatial footprint dimension from the outset. Instead, we divide the network into phases and then locate the actors in each phase. This process yields a refined stepwise analysis of the production network. The next step is to summarise the findings for the whole network. Production networks may be local from the creation phase to archiving or global from start to finish. It may also be the case that creation and production are entirely local or regional but distribution and exchange are national or even global. Identifying such spatial footprints would convey important information to policy makers.

Similarly, we adopt a stepwise approach to assessing the organisation of network governance. For each phase, we inquire which actor initiates, organises, monitors and controls activities. It may be that one actor is in charge of the whole network. It may also be the case that two actors are in charge of different phases. A more horizontal governance configuration without clear leading actors is also a possibility. How policies impact production networks depends on their governance configurations. Throwing money at a specific cultural and creative industry which is controlled by a transnational corporation that is located outside the EU would be a different proposition from financing a network in which the leading actor is close to the others, in the same country or even in the same city.

We use the typology matrix to systematise the classification of the cases that we studied. This matrix must be completed by using the actor categories in Table 2. We use the labels from Table 2 to ensure consistency.

Table 1. The typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation					
Production					
Distribution					
Exchange					
Archiving					
Network level					Lead actor/multiple actors/horizontal

Table 2. Key actors in the production networks

Creators	Actors who participate in the initial creation (individuals, such as writers and musicians, or collectives, such as fashion brands and film crews)
Suppliers (specialised)	Suppliers that provide specialised/dedicated services or products and are hard to replace in the short term
Strategic partners (private sector)	Providers of strategic resources (capital, labour, knowledge and certifications) such as banks, educational institutions, professional associations, tastemakers and critics
Strategic partners (civil society)	Actors that operate at neither the state level nor the market level and which provide essential goods, services or resources (funding, labour, information and certifications)
Strategic partners (public sector, multilevel)	Public sector actors at the level of the EU, the national, the regional or the local government that provide strategic resources (e.g. funding and certifications)
Distributors	Actors (individual or collective) in charge of delivering the good or service to the customer or consumer
Consumers	B2C (business to consumer): final market with large number of buyers
Customer	B2B (business to business): final market, typically with a single buyer (e.g. real estate firm commissioning a design for a building)
Lead actor(s)	Actor(s) who initiates, organises, monitors and controls the activities of the network

Phases

We depart from the GPN approach with its five phases. In many cases, however, the phases overlap, and borders are blurred. Such issues can be addressed easily by merging the cells for phases that overlap or by drawing dotted lines if the phases are distinct but their boundaries are blurred.

The spatial scales

We distinguish between four scales: the local or the regional, the national, the intra-EU and the global. These scales, in principle, correspond to different policymakers and, in many cases, also to different policies (from local policies to provide workspaces through national subsidy programmes to EU competition regulations and trade policies). The anchor point for *the local or regional* scale is the point at which initial creation occurs, that is, the point at which the aesthetic component of the good or service is created. This spatial level may coincide with a particular city, a large metropolitan area or a rural region. The origin of the value chain may be located elsewhere, as in the case of architectural design, a domain in which the customer may be located across the globe. However, our focus here is on the first moves of concrete actors from a specific CCS. We then inquire, for each phase, where the other key actors in the production network are located. The location of an activity is where the actors are from: e.g., flying in a choreographer from Norway and a light engineer from Israel to create a modern dance work in The Hague is still a form of global import.

Governance

Governance pertains to the whole network. We distinguish between three options: a) networks with a lead actor, b) networks with multiple lead actors (not more than 2 or 3) and c) bottom-up horizontal arrangements.

PART 1. The European production network of the craft industry: an overview

1.1 Overview of the craft industry

According to the Collins Dictionary, the noun *craft* designates “a special skill, art, or dexterity” and any “occupation or avocation requiring special skills, especially manual ones, including carpentry, sewing, pottery, and so on”.¹ The Cambridge Dictionary adds that craft presupposes *experience* and extends the definition to any “job or activity that needs skill and experience”.² As a verb, in assent with the Oxford Dictionary, *to craft* means “to make or devise (something) with skills, expertise or ingenuity”, and “to produce or create (an object, piece of work, etc.) with careful artistry or attention to detail”.³ Although these definitions find common ground in manual skills, expertise, ingenuity, and care for finishing, the list of activities that one could include in the depicted frame could be endless. This list could comprise traditional craft activities, artistic craft activities, and many other activities requiring dexterity and theoretical-practical command over materials and manufacturing techniques, such as woodworking and upholstery, glass making and marble cutting, and leather cutting and sewing, but also the activities of plumbers, electricians, and iron carpenters among others. This circumstance seems to certify that, according to common sense, it is difficult to set a net boundary which identifies what, precisely, a craft activity is.

Things do not seem to change when shifting to other fields of definitions. In a long, compelling article published in 2018, the American Craft Council Magazine editor, Joyce Lovelace, openly asked the following: “Seriously, what does the word [craft] mean?”.⁴ Admitting the elusive nature of this “curious word”, the author recognised its capacity to summon tradition, history, skills, discipline and standard of quality, counterculture and antidote to the machine, art forms, hobby, do-it-yourself, and new-maker cultures. The academic field also struggles with the definition of craft, especially in the context of a globalised economy (Micelli, 2011). The imagery built on the old-fashioned idea of an artisan committed to the defence of tradition, unable to project him/herself beyond the local community in which he/she is embedded, has been largely overcome by the examples of some craftspeople or craft enterprises who have been able to innovate and carve out a crucial role in extra-local production networks. Thus, it seems clear that a definition of what constitutes a craft activity depends on the framework within which it is used. Moreover, as is discussed in Section 1.1.5, a shared, formal definition of craft enterprise is missing at the European Union (EU) level: building on its own tradition and history, each Member State has developed a specific definition of craft that is not completely comparable with those of the other States.

¹ <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/craft>

² <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/craft>

³ <https://www.oed.com/view/Entry/43695?rskey=X2yn2Z&result=2&isAdvanced=false#eid>

⁴ <https://www.craftcouncil.org/magazine/article/craft-seriously-what-does-word-mean>

These considerations suggest that the craft industry is an *uncertain territory*: researchers are called upon to conduct their investigations in a field whose perimeter is not perfectly defined.

To reduce complexity, a general definition of craft should be sketched based on the common factors that characterise the varied activities considered. According to this definition, the craft industry should comprise a wide range of activities where, regardless of the organisational and legal form assumed by such activity, (a) the craftsman has a high level of skill and knowledge of the materials and techniques used; (b) production is made by the craftsman or in close connection to him/her, often in small batches, using hands or simple machinery, employing different forms and degrees of technologies and innovation (i.e., digital technologies, innovation on materials and processes, and patents); and (c) production is the result of a dialogue between the craftsman and his/her customer: the former does not passively execute the tasks assigned by the latter, but can participate in their design or projecting, often suggesting alternative options.

Although the lack of data prevents accurate estimates (see Part 2 of this report), the craft industry undoubtedly represents a significant economic activity for the EU economy. The relevance of the industry can be deduced, at first, from the weight of the manufacturing sector – in which the craft industry is subsumed – in almost all EU Member States. According to Eurostat, approximately 1 in 10 enterprises in the EU's nonfinancial business economy (Sections B to J and L to N, and Division 95 of the NACE codes list) were classified as manufacturing (Section C) in 2019, a total of more than 2 million enterprises.⁵ In the same year, the manufacturing sector employed more than 30 million people and generated €1 998 billion of value added. Building on our elaborations (see Part 2 of this report for details), it is also possible to assume that, in 2019, the number of craft enterprises in the EU was approximately 8.6 million, representing 37.2% of the total population of the EU's nonfinancial business economy. Furthermore, some national data demonstrate how important the contribution of craft enterprises to national economies can be: in 2019 according to Confartigianato (2021), in Italy there were slightly more than one million craft enterprises, representing 23.1% of the overall number of active enterprises; craft is also a major asset for France, accounting for approximately 1 700 000 enterprises (38 000 in the artistic sector) and 3.1 million individuals employed (Chambre de Métiers et de l'Artisanat, 2021)⁶; in Germany, the 560 296 craft enterprises registered in 2019 employed more than 5 million people (Destatis, 2021⁷); craft activities are also well developed in small countries like Luxembourg, where the 7 800 craft enterprises detected in 2019 represented 21% of all companies in the Grand Duchy.⁸

The economic relevance of craft is only one of the reasons that stimulate a focus on the functioning of this industry. In fact, the craft industry also has a deep-rooted tradition in most EU countries, which has contributed to forging the rich and varied European cultural identity. This seems particularly

⁵ Starting from 2019, data from the UK are not included in the EU overall record.

⁶ www.artisanat.fr/lartisanat/un-secteur-cle-de-leconomie/lartisanat-premiere-entreprise-de-france

⁷ www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Economic-Sectors-Enterprises/Crafts/Tables/crafts-enterprises.html#fussnote-1-59044

⁸ www.luxembourg.public.lu/en/work-and-study/employment-in-luxembourg/craftsmanship-luxembourg-figures.html

evident when considering some typical productions, such as Bohemian crystal in the Czech Republic, Limoges porcelain in France and that of Puente del Arzobispo and Talavera in Spain, Solingen cutlery in Germany, Murano glass and Faenza or Grottaglie ceramics in Italy, and Donegal tweed in Ireland: these are just a few examples of European artisanal products which are part of European cultural heritage and contribute to local and national development.

At the EU level, attention to the craft industry is witnessed in several projects funded under its various research programmes along different funding periods. Projects such as EASYCRAFT⁹ and CRAFTS CODE¹⁰ address the challenges faced by craft small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in increasing their competitiveness in the global marketplace through the creation of an e-commerce platform and the development of a framework to stimulate policy learning and capacity-building activities. Other projects such as INNOCRAFTS¹¹ aim to promote entrepreneurship and business creation in the artistic and contemporary craft industry. Relating to training and skills, some projects have sought to identify areas of vocational training within small crafts trades where a regional or European need exists: the MINGEI project¹² seeks to capture the motion and tool use of heritage craft practitioners to preserve and illustrate skill and tool manipulation; other projects have aimed to develop an enhanced understanding of the current and future skill needs of micro and craft enterprises in Europe, strengthening the links between vocational and educational training and the labour market – which is the case of a study ordered by the DG Enterprise and Industry of the European Commission (EC).¹³ In some projects, innovation and training go hand in hand. For instance, the RICHES project¹⁴ explores how craft skills can be a source of innovation and value generation for the creative economy by leveraging on the potential of digital technology and through their transfer in other economic sectors; the eCraft2Learn project¹⁵ employs digital fabrication and making technologies to reinforce personalised learning and teaching in science, technology, engineering, arts, and math (STEAM) education, assisting the development of future skills that promote inclusion and employability for youth in the EU. Furthermore, the transformation of work has attracted research attention in its implications with professional and social identities: to obtain an enhanced understanding of the relationship between identity and work in the digital era, the EU-funded CRAFTWORK¹⁶ project has sought to develop a new framework exploring the relationship between identity and work in the context of the ‘neo-craft’ industries of the digital era.

From the GPN perspective, the special relationship between craft enterprises and the territories in which they are rooted is only one of many points of interest. Approaching the craft industry with the

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/IST-2000-26349>

¹⁰ <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/craftscode>

¹¹ <https://keep.eu/projects/5406/INNOvating-entrepreneurship--EN>

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/822336>

¹³ See “Identification of future skills needs in micro and craft(-type) enterprises up to 2020”, European Commission, DG Enterprise and Industry, Unit F.2 – Small Businesses, Cooperatives, Mutuals and CSR; financed by the EU, Service Contract No. 30-CE-0319368.

¹⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/612789>

¹⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731345>

¹⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/948982>

GPN methodology means considering the whole productive chain of the industry. In fact, although most of the attention is usually devoted to the production phase of crafted goods, the craft industry is based on an input–output structure through which such products are designed, manufactured, distributed, and archived. The GPN approach makes it clear that artisanal goods are the result of cooperation among different actors – sometimes located in dispersed territories – who contribute to the creation and enhancement of the value incorporated into the final product. Finally, as the case studies examined in the report will prove (see *Part 3*), the features of the production networks that this industry comprises are highly varied – the GPN approach can assist in understanding how these differences reflect in the different trajectories of value capture. To provide a brief idea of this variety, how the role of craftspeople (and craft enterprises) change depending on the governance model of the network should be considered: craftspeople (and craft enterprises) can work in relation with the creative units of a lead company and translate their ideas into models, prototypes, or (semi)finished products; they can work in direct relation with final customers, attempting to give shape to their desires, or as generic/qualified suppliers of larger companies involved in wider transnational production networks; they can conceive, develop, and realise their products and disseminate them in the market, with or without intermediaries. Further consideration is presented in the following pages of this report.

The remainder of Part 1 is organised as follows. Section 1.1.1 presents a general profile of the European production network of the craft industries, detailing the reasons why artisans’ work should be studied with renewed interest; Section 1.1.2 focuses on the great variety of the goods and services that characterises the industry and presents a threefold taxonomy that distinguishes between traditional crafts, artistic crafts, and craft manufacture; Section 1.1.3 discusses the structure of the craft labour market and presents the main job profiles and skills required by the industry; Section 1.1.4 emphasises the social, cultural, and spatial aspects that influence the craft industry – that is, the various dimensions of embeddedness; Section 1.1.5 presents and discusses the policy framework that affects the craft industry. Section 1.2 concludes part 1 and presents the production network configuration of the craft industry and discusses the main governance models operating within it.

Lexical notes

Within this report, to use and promote a gender-inclusive and non-discriminatory communication, the expression “craftsmanship” is replaced by “craft”, “craft activity”, or “craftspersonship”, which are used interchangeably; the expressions “craftsman” and “craftsmen” are replaced by “craftsperson” and “craftspeople”. The expressions “craftsperson”, “craftspeople” and “artisan(s)” are employed synonymously.

1.1.1 Profile of the craft industry

In recent years, craft activities have experienced a substantial rediscovery both as an economic and commercial industry (Micelli, 2011) and as an alternative way of life centred on sociality, communication, and the gratification connected to handmade creation (Gauntlett, 2011). Craft activities represent the economy of signs in space that characterises the postmodern era: it is an extremely fluid global economy but also, simultaneously, something that maintains a special relation with the place where cultural products are created (Lash & Urry, 1993). According to some scholars, beyond their idealisation (and celebration), craft activities represent a response to the challenges of globalisation because they are able to sustain lean, flexible, high-quality, and highly innovative production (Micelli, 2016). Furthermore, these activities are at the centre of what is often called the revival of urban manufacturing, namely the (timid) return of production activities into urban areas. It deals with small, highly innovative factories that often have an artisanal nature; in addition, they can become a source of urban regeneration (Armondi & Bruzzese, 2017; D'Ovidio & Rabbiosi, 2017a).

Historically, the term *craft*, which is used to express craft activities and techniques, has its origins in the British Arts and Crafts movement of the 19th century, which opposed the mass production of large factories, where workers are alienated from their production and craft qualities are denied. Craft is understood and presented as a local, human, and sustainable alternative to large-scale manufacturing production (Fox Miller, 2017; Mazzucotelli Salice, Medicina, Fondazione Cologni dei Mestieri d'Arte, & Scuola Cova, 2012). Scholars indicated that “[t]he more technology, mass-production and mass-consumption takes people away from tangible experiences, the more craft and crafts communities are galvanized due to their physical and psychological comforts” (Jakob & Thomas, 2017, p. 501).

Many reasons have led us to observe artisans’ work with renewed interest: the need for cooperation, the importance of innovation through open knowledge, the need to do things with your own hand and brain: all of these activities occur inside the artisan workshop (Sennett, 2008). The renewed appeal of the artisan laboratory also derives from the imagination of a place where, despite hierarchical working relationships, work is centred on human relationships on the one hand and the perfect integration between life and work on the other hand (Banks, 2010). Gauntlett (2011) went even further in building a celebratory narrative of the world that revolves around the artisan laboratory, arguing that the very same process of building something with one’s own hands allows one to connect with other people. From this perspective, one would face a real transition from a society dominated by a professional *élite* of craft producers to a society in which an increasing number of people are involved in the creative process. This occurs both because of the renewed attention to craft activities as well as the growing diffusion of digital manufacturing (e.g., 3D printing and laser cutting), of widening practices of sharing spaces and knowledge, and of creating and sharing through new communication technologies among others. Within this dynamic, the artisan laboratory is the main place of making and consequently of social connection.

Furthermore, from a policy perspective, there is growing interest in craft as it is viewed as a stimulus for the development of local and regional economies, skills, and materials that are also able to relate to wider networks (McHattie, Champion, & Broadley, 2018). Craft is positioned as a conduit to the revitalisation of local economies and as training mechanisms that support the creative economy: networking, apprenticeships, skills, training, mentoring, support for micro-businesses, the promotion of new markets, and fostering of innovation (Jakob & Thomas, 2017).

Lastly, the craft industry comprises a large range of activities. However, the definition of what constitutes a craft activity depends on the framework within which it is used – and is constantly evolving. As a general definition, craft activities are where the craftspeople have a high level of skill *plus* an applied knowledge of the materials and manufacturing techniques used; craft is also where production is made by the craftsman or in close connection to him/her, usually in small batches, using hands or simple machinery, and employing both traditional and innovative materials and processes. The activities can vary greatly. They can range from traditional heritage crafts to ceramics and leatherworking, from woodworking to repair activities, from boatbuilding to 3D printing. Some countries (e.g., Italy and France) have specific criteria for defining artisans; others (e.g., the Netherlands and Romania) do not differentiate craft from other types of skilled labour, categorising it together with other professions, such as construction and optometry. Based on these considerations, in the context of this report, the crafts industry is interpreted in a wider sense, to some extent as an *open set*.

The sections that compose *Part 1* explore the complexity, aesthetic and cultural meaning, and perception and valuation of the goods and services associated with the craft industry (Sec. 1.1.2); the job profiles, labour market conditions, workplace conditions, training and education, and skills required in the industry (Sec. 1.1.3); the main social, cultural, and spatial aspects that influence the network of the industry (Sec. 1.1.4); and the regulatory framework that directly or indirectly affects the industry (Sec. 1.1.5).

1.1.2 The incredible variety of goods and services in the craft industry

As discussed in Section 1.1.1, what constitutes the craft industry (and how it is positioned in relation to other creative industries such as fine arts and design) is fleeting. The definition and perception of craft activities differ between countries as well as contexts (Luckman & Thomas, 2018). Most definitions centre the essential aspects of what constitutes craft on the manual skills and expertise of the craftsman, on his/her direct involvement in the phase of realisation of the products, and on the nonstandardised characteristics of the products; moreover, the distinctive features of these products can vary significantly. These considerations are also true for a very commonly used – but not exclusively so – definition, namely that of UNESCO, which defines crafts as

produced by artisans, completely by hand or with the help of hand-tools and even mechanical means, as long as the direct manual contribution of the artisan remains the most substantial component of the finished product. Their special nature derives from their distinctive features, which can be utilitarian, aesthetic, artistic, creative, culturally attached, decorative, functional, traditional, and religiously and socially symbolic and significant. [...] [T]here is no particular restriction in terms of production quantity. Even when artisans make quantities of the same design, no two pieces are ever exactly alike. (UNESCO, 1997)

This definition is by no means normative but highlights how incredibly diverse the craft industry can be. Going beyond this definition, common forms of craft activities include traditional forms of making, such as basket weaving, textile weaving, ceramics, and woodworking, but can also include the making of luxury handbags, lamps, shoes, soap, paper, candles, or beer, as well as the manufacture of furniture, upholstery, and recreational boats, plus any other activity based on dexterity and theoretical-practical command over materials and manufacturing techniques (e.g., the work of plumbers, electricians, iron carpenters, and repairers). The defining aspect of the crafts industry lies in the chain that links design, production, and (eventually) assembly of the final products: goods are made by hand or with the help of simple machinery either as single objects or in smaller batches (Thurnell-Read, 2019); even when artisans make quantities of the same design, no two pieces are ever exactly alike. This guarantees the uniqueness and total customisation of the crafted products.

Crafted goods are not identified separately in the main international system for trade statistics, but they could be categorised by market segment or raw materials (USAID, 2006¹⁷). Classifying by market segment means adopting an end-market perspective: products are grouped by their natural destination of use (e.g., clothing and accessories, interior and exterior decoration, household items, toys, and stationery). Although practical and simple, this classification risks fuelling a partial vision of craft activities, since it focuses too much on traditional market segments (e.g., home accessories) while excluding alternative sectors (e.g., nautical crafts) or more innovative productions (e.g., digital manufacturing). On the other hand, classifying artisanal products by raw materials allows a wider understanding of the craft industry: the focus is not on the destination of use of the product but, to some extent, on its productive process. Thus, 'eclectic' or innovative products, even when combining different materials, could be recognised and framed as artisanal products. This classification was used in the *Methodological Guide to the Collection of Data on Crafts* published by UNESCO in 1990, where products are listed primarily according to the materials used and, in certain cases, the material and technique are combined with corresponding Harmonised System codes identified for each product category.¹⁸ The main categories considered in this classification are as follows: basket/wicker/

¹⁷ https://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PNADN210.pdf

¹⁸ The Harmonized Commodity Description and Coding System (HS) of the Customs Cooperation Council (CCC) is used worldwide as a reference for classifications of external trade statistics and for customs tariffs. It has the legal status of an international convention and has been in effect since 1.1.1988. The HS is a classification of goods by criteria based on raw materials and the stage of production of commodities. The industrial origin criterion is considered whenever it is compatible with the main criteria set out above. It also includes a set of explanatory notes and binding rules for interpretation, which form part of the Protocol of Agreement. The HS is at the heart of the whole process of the harmonisation of international economic classifications being jointly conducted by the United Nations Statistics Division

vegetable fibre-works; leather, metal, paper, pottery, soap, textiles, wood, various animal/mineral/vegetable materials (this category includes stone, glass, bone, horn, shells, or a combination); and extra categories (which refer to different materials and techniques applied at the same time, such as decorations, jewellery, gold/silversmith wares, and musical instruments).

As highlighted in the CICERONE D1.4 report, titled “Selection of the case studies”, another dimension of diversification of crafted goods relies on their degree of tradition of innovation: crafted goods can represent a product of heritage, tradition, history, and local culture or can be characterised by design- and innovation-led contemporary features (Jakob & Thomas 2017).

These classifications confirm the openness and variety of the craft industry, incorporating many different types of products, raw materials, and techniques. To reduce the complexity of the scenario presented, an effective strategy could be to present a (nonexhaustive) taxonomy of possible artisanal productions, characterised by blurred boundaries. Thus, on the basis of some common characteristics, it would be possible to identify some common groups of crafted goods or trades and move the discussion forward. The proposed taxonomy comprises traditional crafts, artistic crafts, and craft manufacture.

Within the *UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage*, traditional crafts are presented as the most tangible manifestation of intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2003). Crucial in this category is not the craft product itself but rather the skills and knowledge involved in its creation and realisation. Usually, the particular know-how incorporated in this form of crafts has been passed down over generations – often through age-old systems of instruction and apprenticeship – and is tied to a specific place (Kölling, 2007). Goods in this industry can include numerous materials – from ceramics and glass to wood working, basket weaving, and textile work – and highly diverse destinations of use, such as tools, clothing and jewellery, decorative art, transport and shelter, ritual objects, and musical instruments, both for amusement and education. Traditional crafts can be specifically tied to a nation, region, or specific location: they are part of the history or economic life of the areas in which they are located and contribute to strengthening the identity of communities and the so-called “sense of the place” (Relph, 1976). Places such as Murano for the Italian glassmaking tradition or the Swedish cultural hub of Glasriket (“The Kingdom of Crystal”) have become synonymous with the crafts produced there, benefiting from and contributing to the reinforcement of the know-how concentrated in those areas. To some extent, traditional crafts tend to cluster in ways that are different from those who characterise the creative and cultural industries (CCIs): whereas CCIs cluster in urban contexts, crafts seem to co-locate in rural areas (Lazzeretti, Domenech, Capone, 2009). The survival of this form of crafts is often supported by the tourism industry.

and Eurostat. Its items and subitems are the fundamental terms on which industrial goods are identified in product classifications. See RAMON – Reference and Management of Nomenclatures, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ramon/nomenclatures/index.cfm?TargetUrl=DSP_GEN_DESC_VIEW_NOHDR&StrNom=HS_2022&StrLanguageCode=EN.

The definition of artistic crafts relies on the high aesthetic, artistic, and creative features of the considered crafted products. This category is sometimes referred to by other terms, such as “applied arts”, and represents a not so easily definable form of craft, positioned between the traditional forms of craft activities and the fine arts. This form of craft challenges Becker's well-known distinction between “arts” and “crafts”, which he presented as “two contrasting kinds of aesthetic, work organization, and work ideology, differing in their emphases on the standards of utility, virtuoso skill, and beauty” (Becker, 1978). Products can either be everyday objects created with artistic intent and high-quality crafted goods, or be strictly artistic but with deep material knowledge, made with highly skilled dexterity. Sometimes, the handmade creations realised by hobbyists are assimilated to artistic crafts; in reality, the artistic craftsperson distinguishes him/herself from hobbyists by a deep professional knowledge of the material, wishing to be clearly separated from more generic types of craft activities. It is excluded from nearby industries, such as the fine arts, where craft is often seen as too applied to gain a place within typical fine art galleries (Adamson, 2013). A first attempt to define the field of artistic crafts was made in 2008 by the French and Italian organisations Ateliers d'Art de France, CNA Nazionale, Confartigianato Imprese Nazionale, and Artex, which developed an International Charter of Artistic Craftsmanship.¹⁹ Their aim was to highlight not only the values and peculiarities of the industry but also its strengths and weaknesses. According to the provisions contained in the Charter, which has no legal value, the artistic craft industry includes creations, productions, and works of high aesthetic value (whether inspired by forms, models, decoration, styles, and techniques that are traditional or historical or as the result of individual creative development and personal and artistic forms of expression) as well as works that are mainly created using manual techniques, at a highly professional technical level, using equipment, but excluding wholly mass-produced works; separate mechanised or automatic work stages are allowed, using innovative techniques and high-technology instruments (“Definitions”, art. 2). The definition of artistic crafts also covers works of restoration, designed to conserve, consolidate, or restore works of art or objects of architectural, archaeological, ethnographic, bibliographic, or archival heritage (“Definitions”, art. 2). The added value of the Charter is the identification of a definitive list of activities that should be considered artistic crafts, defined in accordance with the European classification of economic activities, NACE rev. 2 published in the *Journal Officiel* on the 20th of December 2006 (“Definitions”, art. 3). Artistic crafts have economic, cultural, and social value and stimulate the development of the areas in which they are located. Promoting artistic crafts means fostering a lifestyle, a philosophy, and a production ethic: for these reasons, “artistic craftsmanship is the best possible ambassador of ‘Made in...’ products” (“Proposals”, art. 2). Another attempt at a definition comes from the United Kingdom: according to the Creative & Cultural Skills & Crafts Council, the field of artistic craft should encompass a wide range of disciplines, such as ceramics, glass, graphic crafts, heritage and traditional crafts, iron and stone, jewellery and silversmithing, musical instrument making, taxidermy, textiles and leather, toys and automata, and finally wood (Creative & Cultural Skills & Crafts Council, 2009).

¹⁹www.artex.firenze.it/rete-internazionale-dell-artigianato/carta-internazionale-dell-artigianato-artistico-12-anni-di-successi

A third category of crafts differs from those just presented because it has no artistic content and, despite having a foundation in the tradition and history of the place where it takes place, it has managed to evolve and carve out a role within a broader production network located in a cluster or other forms of agglomeration economies (i.e., districts). This type of craft activity can be referred to as craft manufacture. It includes a great variety of finished and semifinished products made by individuals or micro/small craft enterprises with a relevant degree of specialisation. These artisans are able to cope with highly complex situations and are dedicated to production and repair activities. The artisans and craft enterprises that produce goods included in this category typically work as qualified or generic suppliers. They do not serve the local market exclusively; yet, due to their small size, they can work simultaneously only for a few clients. Generally, these artisans do not participate in the creation of the final products but are able to translate the idea in practice on the basis of the indications received from the customer or the creative unit of the company for whom they work. They realise the final product with high precision and competence, also suggesting alternative options for product improvement. Although these artisans are involved in the realisation of products that employ traditional materials and production processes (using their hands or simple machinery), they can also invest in process or product innovation, attempting to differentiate their business from local, regional, or national competitors. Usually, these actors have acquired their skills through a long internship or an apprenticeship with other craftspeople. Working with different materials and different production techniques, these actors can serve different industries, such as the fashion design industry (e.g., a tailor or pattern maker), yachting industry (e.g., a wood and iron carpenter, upholsterer, or marble cutter), or furniture industry and civil construction industry (i.e., a furniture maker or plumber). The considered crafted products can be sold individually (e.g., an artisanal leather sofa) or incorporated into the final product (e.g., the furnishings and finishes of a pleasure boat).

Other forms of craft are emerging in other fields, which is the case in the food and beverage industries, for example. These small-scale industries have attracted increasing interest from consumers and scholars, and they are often included in the definition of craft (Colombo, 2007, p. 22). Within this industry, small-scale beer production (Garavaglia & Swinnen, 2017) has received a great deal of recent scholarly attention. Many aspects related to this case can be seen as indicative of changes and trends in other craft activities. Originating as a movement of resistance against the global consolidation of beer breweries and a standardisation in beer products between the 1950s and the 1980s microbreweries have become a widespread phenomenon in both the United States and Europe, offering a wide variety of artisanal beer products (Garavaglia & Swinnen, 2017). Today, the presence of craft breweries is registered in most European countries, both in the form of new urban manufacturing and as local breweries in rural areas. Researchers have highlighted how these enterprises work as a form of alternative employment and a “labour of love” (e.g., Thurnell-Read, 2014), how they use digital services to disseminate their goods (Clemons, Gao, & Hitt, 2006; Foster et al., 2017), and how they create spaces for the local community and identity (e.g., Hubbard, 2019; Schnell & Reese, 2003) as well as tourism (Duarte Alonso, Sakellarios, & Bressan, 2017; Kline, Locum, & Cavaliere, 2017).

Beyond the creative and production aspects, other activities should also be considered, such as distribution/dissemination and exchange. The distribution and exchange of crafted products is highly differentiated and depends both on the typology of the product and the market segment in which the considered product is positioned. In general terms, as noted by the EC, crafted products “can be found in street markets, retails of different kinds, tourism-related venues, fairs and galleries” (European Commission, 2017); they can be sold directly by the maker in his/her workshop, at markets and fairs, or through the maker’s webpage; distributed by shops or e-shops or digital intermediary platforms; and shared in auction houses (virtual or not). The traditional and artistic segments of the craft industry production system are characterised by a small scale; here, the artisan or designer-maker can be solely responsible for the design, production, distribution, and exchange of their product. There are also larger production systems where craftspeople/makers can come together and make a sort of guild to share production spaces and distribution channels as well as exchange design ideas. Craftspeople who enjoy success can employ people to work in their workshops. As for the craft manufacture segment, when working as suppliers for larger companies, artisans and craft enterprises can sell their products directly to the lead firm; to find new commercial partners and to position their products in larger markets, they participate in business-to-business and business-to-customers fairs.

As anticipated, it should also be noted that distribution and exchange channels also depend on the market segments in which the considered products are positioned. Although it is not possible to draw net correspondences between market niche and type of channels, a general, drafted frame can be sketched. In relation to physical retail, it could be said that functional/utilitarian goods fall into the low-end market and tend to be normally (but not exclusively) sold through shops, stores, and other retailers. Higher-quality crafted products – meaning those that incorporate higher decorative or aesthetic contents – tend to be distributed in mid- to high-end markets through small chains, independent retail stores, and so on; the crafted goods that incorporate major shares of artistic/creative contents belong to the high-end market segment and can be distributed through speciality stores and craft or design centres and shops. Lastly, luxury products tend to be distributed through luxury boutiques and galleries or by the maker him/herself through personal channels.

As is clear, providing a complete list of how the dissemination of crafted goods takes its form is nearly impossible. For this reason, only some of the more common forms of dissemination are described here: workshops, web shops and Internet platforms, market fairs, and galleries.

Crafts are still largely disseminated and sold through the craftsperson’s own studio or workshop. Here, artisans can build direct contacts with clients, whereas customers can see the objects in real life, building a connection both with the maker and the object. For larger firms, showrooms or mill shops are also crucial parts of the dissemination and exchange stage, and for larger-scale productions are often accompanied by tours.

The impacts of digitisation and the Internet are deeply affecting the craft industry, as they have allowed for more craftspeople to access new markets, which are often far from their locales and even

globally. Since craft is, in many ways, a geographically sticky industry where knowledge, skills, and innovation are exchanged between artisans in workshops, often tied to local culture and heritage, researchers have noted how digitalisation has become a way to break some of these barriers. Much current research and the “third wave” of interest in craftspersonship highlight how the Internet has become a main part of why crafted goods have created interest. Platforms such as Etsy have allowed small-scale craftspeople to share their products with a large audience in locations far away, thereby connecting makers and consumers in ways that were not previously possible for small-scale producers. This ability has attracted a new set of makers to the craft industry, both hobbyists making a business out of their crafted passions as well as professional and well-established craftspeople (Gaytán, 2019; Luckman, 2013). New intermediaries, such as online platforms like *Etsy*, *Not on the high street*, and *Ravelry*, allow the easy dissemination of products well beyond their origin, creating markets that could never have been reached otherwise (Luckman, 2013). Other digital platforms, such as social media and online communities, and the easy access and sheer number of DIY videos and resources – crucial features of the new “maker movement” – have reduced barriers to engage with craft, making production and consumption available to wider audiences as well as producing spaces and communities wherein knowledge exchange and innovation can occur (Watson & Shove, 2008). Social media has also produced platforms where consumers and producers can interact directly (Foster, Kirman, Linehan, & Lawson, 2017). Posting content from workshops and even uploading videos of the manufacturing process on Instagram and YouTube are growing trends, where consumers get to engage and experience the workshop and production without having to physically be there – features that are essential in craft consumption (Thurnell-Read, 2019).

One critical socio-institutional dimension for many craft activities is the organisation of trade fairs and exhibition weeks, such as the World Craft Council Europe’s International Exhibition or the European Artistic Craft Days. They can either be oriented towards a particular craft, such as furniture or ceramics, or more commonly towards a larger span of craft activities. Craft fairs can be large, gathering artisans from many countries, or smaller and more local. These fairs and exhibitions serve as key activities where artisans gather to gain new audiences and markets, and where participants can engage in tangible experiences of the objects, touching and seeing them, which is not possible online. These craft fairs also serve as nodes for the face-to-face exchange of knowledge with other traders. Fair trades serve as arenas where norms of the industry are negotiated, such as social norms, quality criteria, and price (Moorean, 2015). Trade fairs can also provide valuable nodes of networking, where new contacts with intermediaries can be formed. Due to the networking opportunities, presence at craft fairs can also serve as an important strategy for artisans who aim to export their goods (Fillis, 2008; Sala, 2002). However, participating in trade fairs can be a large expense for many craftspeople, and funding from governmental or nongovernmental organisations may be key to entering these arenas (Sala, 2002). Although they are temporal and short-lived events, preparation for them can be intense and time consuming, and the knowledge exchange and contacts formed during these cyclical events have long-lasting effects for the traders (Power & Jansson, 2008). Artistic crafts, on the borders between crafts and fine art, often turn to galleries to disseminate and exchange their goods. This is not an easy process as artistic crafts are often understood as part of the “applied arts”, and therefore,

they do not have the platform of fine arts opened to them. This is even the case when artistic crafted products are more artistic than applied, and only the material and skill set of the craftsperson differs (Adamson, 2013). Still, it makes up a critical part of those artistic craftspeople who manage to achieve a larger following outside of artisan circles and gain recognition in fine art circles.

1.1.3 Vocation, precariousness, and skills: The main features of labour in the craft industry

Scholars have not paid much attention to the conditions of artisans, but the wide body of knowledge on creative labour can partially be applied to such conditions. During the 20th century, the craft industry was continuously under pressure as the availability of cheaper, imported, mass-produced goods through globalisation processes pushed craft activities to a niche position in the marketplace (RICHES, 2016). Interest from younger generations has also decreased, and the workforce able to or interested in engaging with crafts has reduced in size. Over the last two decades, however, craft activities have been regaining interest, often due to the same processes that pushed them to the margins. Growing awareness of the ethical and sustainability implications of globalised mass-production and a consumer desire to consume goods where the production process is known, tangible, and customisable have created a demand for craft production (Collins, 2018; Fox Miller, 2017; Luckman, 2013). New versions of the original arts and crafts movement's notions of the dignity of the workshop and the alienation of workers in industrialised production have emerged, and a new idealised desire to work and produce with one's own hands has caused craft activities to experience a renaissance (Fox Miller, 2017; Krugh, 2014; Thurnell-Read, 2019). Pursuing a career in craft has also become a way for people to monetise their home production and started to be seen as career path that is more in tune with a work-life balance, especially in precarious labour markets (Luckman, 2013, 2015b, 2018).

Within the EU, crafts refer to a wide set of activities. Not only does a wide variety of craft products exist but also a wide variety of makers and artisans, from high-quality fine craftspeople, with highly expensive sought-after goods, to micro-enterprises and "mumpreneurs" (Ekinsmyth, 2011), who start a business "to do what they love" and downsize their lifestyle to fit family life (Luckman, 2015b). A heightened interest in craft products in recent years has also led to a recent romanticisation surrounding craft labour, which has come to be seen as a form of labour that is more satisfactory and rewarding than office work; furthermore, occupations that have previously been the enterprise of the working class are now being performed by educated people of the upper and middle classes (Dawkins, 2011). Oejo (2017) studied the choices that highly educated "culturally savvy" young men have made to engage in types of craft labour that have previously been viewed as low-status manual labour, such as butchery, brewing, and barbering. He argued that these types of work are more satisfying and creative than previously trodden paths and that these young men have turned previously undesirable work into niched, upscaled occupational niches, building narratives of bespoke and specialty. Similarly,

a return to the artisan's form of work has been highlighted in literature over the past few decades, such as in the seminal piece *The Craftsman* by Sennett (2008). Sennett argued for a form of labour where the worker gets to develop and create perfect skills, leading to highly satisfactory work, which is in contrast to much of the alienated work of our times. Awareness of the merit and satisfaction of working dedicatedly with one's hands as a form of less alienating and more dignified labour is also part of this new trend.

The downside of this type of labour and the romanticism that surrounds it has also been critiqued extensively (Dawkins, 2011; Ross, 2009; Taylor & Luckman, 2018), as people are driven to work under precarious and often self-exploitative labour situations. The freedom of organising one's labour and developing deep cultural and creative skill sets is typical for the CCI in general, and the craft industry is no exception, where precarious work situations are common. In fact, craft is often said to be one of the least profitable among the CCIs, where the focus on handmade and small-scale production, from which the objects to a large extent derive their value, also limits the potential for upscaling.

The vast majority of active craftspeople in Europe are independent craftspeople working independently, or in small enterprises and a one-person firm. They can be located in cities – as for most professions in the CCS – but also exhibit a tendency to locate in rural areas, sometimes connected to the traditional crafts of that area. Independent craftspeople can be highly skilled with years of education and experience on their CVs, but there are also a large number of hobbyists who operate their craft business as a supplementary income (Luckman & Thomas, 2018). Within the industry, another set of craftspeople are employed in larger firms that produce high-quality or luxury objects. They are trained either by the companies themselves or by schools, contributing high-level craftsmanship to these areas. Regarding craft enterprises involved as suppliers in wider production networks, it should be considered that these craft can also employ a share of the blue-collar and low-skilled workforce (e.g., assemblers, polishers, and varnishers).

In the diverse stages of the production network, other workers must be considered, such as those at market fairs, art galleries, and museums as well as agents who export goods to market or work in the media system. Another recurring theme is rural entrepreneurship and craft. Craft is one of the few industries where clusters of creativity are more common in the peripheral regions, and it is often interpreted as traditional, parochial, and place-bound, rather than as innovative as their urban counterparts (Harvey et al., 2012; Thomas et al., 2013, Wood 2012). From a policy perspective, hope exists that peripheral regions could benefit from such industries if understood correctly, particularly when it comes to marketing the place-specific aspect of craftsmanship towards tourists. Craft has also been studied as a way to make a living in rural areas, where it is one of the few creative industries that tend to be more common than in some cities. It is seen as a way for local economies to attract tourists (McHattie, Champion, & Broadley, 2018) as well as to provide otherwise nonexistent labour (J. R. Barnes, 2018; Jakob, 2013). McAuley and Fillis (2005) studied how these rural craft entrepreneurs connect to global market flows, as Prince (2017) did in her study on Danish rural craftspeople in a summer destination, the complex connections that exists between consumer and artisans, as well as

the management of intermediaries that connect their work to markets in cities and further into global commodity markets. Situating crafts in global commodity markets is also a research theme, either through the aforementioned digitalisation processes or through analysing how entrepreneurs in the global south use traditional crafts to break into these global markets, transforming traditional crafts into commodities purchased by an ethnic chic global north, either as tourists or interior decor (e.g., Wherry, 2006, 2008).

Just as the nature of the products of the industry varies greatly, so too does the intrinsic complexity of the product. Of interest in the CICERONE context is that the required labour, knowledge, and skills for making can range between quite simple to highly complex. In general, however, skill is the key element in craft and represents its very asset (Gibson, 2016; Jakob, 2013; Luckman, 2018; Sennett, 2008); as products can vary from highly traditional to highly innovative, the skills required to produce them vary greatly. For instance, in the case of musical instruments or traditional ceramics, skills and the process of making have not changed substantially over the last centuries, although the crucial know-how is extremely specialised and acquired over many years of practice. Frequently, skills, know-how, as well as cultural sensibility and aesthetics are linked to a particular *milieu*, where knowledge is mainly tacit.

The craft industry is defined by the skills of different artisans in their chosen material. These skills are driven by manual skills that often take years to master and are continuously developed during the artisan's career. Schools and professional training represent a critical area for crafts, as firms strongly rely on a skilled workforce. Collective craft associations, regional institutions, higher education institutions, and also private actors (namely firms) can provide advanced professional training in a particular segment of crafts. Yet, although qualified labour is a key element for territorial competitiveness, investment in education and training is one of the riskiest elements within a market logic (Pacetti, 2009). In some countries, acquiring a Master of craft degree is essential for setting up an enterprise for certain craft activities and may even be required by law, whereas for other craft activities formal training is not necessary (but often undertaken) and the craft maker can be self-taught, have knowledge handed down from older generations, or learn their skill in other alternative ways (Kölling, 2007). Since craft is geographically sticky and many techniques are grounded in their localities, artisans may have to travel to undertake and further their education as well as to learn new traditions and techniques to integrate into their work. Independent craftspeople are also required to master skills that are less frequently taught at school but can be vital for their career and for getting their products to market. Digital and marketing skills for managing websites and social media accounts are integral to the contemporary craftspeople, as these intermediaries are of growing importance.

1.1.4 Social, cultural, and spatial aspects influencing the craft industry

As underlined by Gibson, understanding the emergent, craft-based forms of production “requires a focus on place- and path- dependent histories and materialities of labour process” (Gibson, 2016: 62).

Typically, craft-based productions maintain strong links with a specific place and its history. These links are to be found in the cultural traditions, history of the place, and the present local manufacturing labour. In general terms, the path-dependency of the craft industry is highly evident for the following reason:

“[C]raft and maker scenes rely upon material elements: they nest in particular urban or regional spaces (with built landscape features and visceral memories of industrial heritage), extract value from the fleshy bodies of workers, use configurations of labour and technology in the physical production process, emphasize quality materials for which provenance is a source of distinction, and ultimately trade in completed physical objects” (Gibson, 2016: 62-63).

Crucially, crafted products are often related to particular places (Feagan, 2007) that give value to the product, either because of the local craft traditions (e.g., violins made in Cremona, Italy, Bohemian crystal made in the Czech Republic, or porcelain made in Limoges, France) or the presence of a particular know-how, raw material, or social and cultural capital.

To address the variety of socioeconomic relations in space, scholars use the concept of embeddedness. This concept has gained much prominence in social sciences and, in general terms, refers to the idea that social actors, both individual or collective, exist only within relational, institutional, and cultural contexts (Mingione, Ghezzi, 2016). In terms of economic behaviour analysis, the concept implies that economic action is shaped, constructed, and influenced by noneconomic conditions. The concept originates from the work of Karl Polanyi (1944) and was influentially revised by Mark Granovetter (1985) as well as Sharon Zukin and Paul Di Maggio (1990), becoming a key notion in the fields of economic sociology, organisation and business studies, and economic geography. Despite its success among scholars, the concept suffers from indeterminacy as it seems difficult to establish exactly “who is embedded in what” (see Pike et al., 2000). In a persuasive article review, Hess attempted to solve the dilemma by revisiting the main contributions to the theory (Hess, 2004). Briefly, as Table 1 below summarises, the business systems approach considers that firms are embedded in institutional and regulatory frameworks, whereas the new economic sociology approach considers the economic behaviour of actors (both individuals and firms) as embedded in networks of ongoing social interpersonal relations²⁰; organisation and business studies open up to a multidimensional conception of embeddedness, focusing on how firms and networks are influenced by cognitive, cultural, structural, and political mechanisms (Zukin and DiMaggio, 1990), whereas organisational and business specialists add spatial, temporal, market, and technological variables to the analysis (e.g., Halinen and Törnroos, 1998). Lastly, economic geographers prioritise the embeddedness of firms in networks and institutional settings (see Hess, 2004).

²⁰ The focus here is on the agency of social actors and the role of the network in generating, for example, trust and/or malfeasance (Granovetter, 1958).

Table 3. Who is embedded in what? Different views on embeddedness

	Who?	In what?	Geographical scale
Polanyi's <i>Great transformation</i>	'The economy', systems of exchange	'Society', social and cultural structures	No particular scale, but emphasis on the nation state
Business systems approach	Firms	Institutional and regulatory frameworks	Nation state, 'home territory'
New economic sociology	Economic behaviour, individuals and firms	Networks of ongoing social (interpersonal) relations	No particular scale
Organization and business studies	Firms, networks	Time, space, social structures, markets, technological systems, political systems ...	No particular scale
Economic geography	Firms	Networks and institutional settings	Local/regional

Source: Hess, 2004

In the context of the GPN approach adopted within the CICERONE project, as discussed in report D1.1, titled *“Creative and cultural industries and global production network approaches so far”*, embeddedness is considered in three interrelated forms: societal, network, and territorial (Coe and Yeung, 2015). Briefly, societal embeddedness refers to the cultural, institutional, and historical origins of the economic actors involved in the production network; network embeddedness relates to the network structure – that is, to the structure of the linkages between different actors in the GPN as a measure of the “degree of functional and social connectivity within a global production network, the stability of its agents’ relations, and the importance of the network for its participants” (Coe and Yeung, 2015: 17); finally, territorial embeddedness captures how firms and related organisations are anchored in different places through the social dynamics that already exist in there (e.g., firm’s dependence on the particular resources, labour markets, and state policies). Thus, the notion of embeddedness also has spatial and temporal connotations; on the one hand, it evokes the threefold typology of space elaborated by Mol and Law (“fluid spaces”, “networks”, and “regions”; see Mol and Low, 1994), while on the other hand it entails a temporal dimension, requiring the study of formation and the change of social structures over time (Hess, 2004).

With reference to societal dimensions, it is never inappropriate to stress that craft is not only an economic activity but also – and above all – a social labour. Anthropologists and archaeologists remember that crafting is an ancient human behaviour with roots in the primary needs of the most ancient human communities, committed to producing the necessary tools to survive, procure food, realise means of transport, build rudimental dwellings, and manufacture protective clothing; understanding crafts in terms of social labour means considering the human relations, social experiences, and societal organisation, which are connected with the “productive” activities (Costin, 1998). This is particularly evidenced when considering the cultural value of heritage and traditional crafts: these products represent and reveal the symbolic dimensions, material culture, and societal

organisation of the communities in which they were developed. In fact, as suggested by Bunn, making things reveals much more than just the mechanics of the skill or technique:

[I]t provides an insight into the embodied practices, perceptual skills, and tacit knowledge involved in making; it frequently reveals quite different social relations from those associated with use or exchange; it entails an understanding of human-environment relations; it gives space to specific kinds of social talk; and it may reveal new understandings of aesthetics and belief, articulated and understood through bodily practice. (Bunn 2011: 24)

These considerations do not apply only to ancient, crafted products but also to those modern and contemporary products (including nontraditional crafts) that reflect the values, attitudes, cultural references, and aesthetic canons of the makers “embedded” in their communities. In other words, through crafted products, the culture and societal organisation are to some extent “materialised” and revealed. In this sense, crafts should be framed as “social objects” (Costin, 1998). The topic is not new to cultural sociologists either: according to Griswold (1994), cultural objects can be thought of as a “shared significance embodied in form”, representing a part of the wider social system; thus, analysing a cultural object – including crafted products – which means also considering the *social world* in which it emerged and which is characterised by specific “economic, political, social and cultural patterns and exigences” (Griswold, 1998: 14). Considering the richness and variety of the societal dimensions incorporated in crafts, building on Bourriaud’s concept of “relational aesthetics” (Bourriaud, 2002), some scholars have coined the label “relational crafts” to explain how these products contribute to the preservation, transmission, and reproduction of social relations and knowledge that would otherwise be lost (Gray 2012; Barrett 2014).

In addition, societal embeddedness considers how the aesthetic norms, tastes, canons, or styles that characterise a place or a community can influence or shape the production of goods and services. Aesthetics is a social, relational construction (Bourdieu, 1994) involving makers, consumers, materials, artistic currents and traditions, and cognitive assumptions among others; when crafting a product, the artisan finds him/herself embedded in this aesthetic regime, contributing to reproducing the materiality of this regime (Bunn 2011). When recognised collectively, a particular aesthetic form becomes a “style”. This concept is often referred to when representing the *uniqueness* of the products produced in particular places. The example of the so-called Italian style testifies to how diverse interrelated historical, economic, social, cultural, and environmental factors (e.g., the Etruscan idea of beauty, Roman heritage and the season of the Communes, Humanism and the Renaissance, the Baroque age and modernism, the artisanal dimension of the Italian economy, and biodiversity) have forged, throughout the centuries, a precise and fully recognisable cultural style, which has also influenced design, artistic, and crafts activities (Benini, 2018). Lastly, some scholars emphasise how the presence of a particular *genius loci* (“the spirit of the territory”) presides over every creative act in a given territory, expressing “the connection between craftsmanship, community, landscape and beauty” (Benini, *ivi*: 26).

Furthermore, crafts are embedded in a web of institutionalised relations, in which collective organisations and guilds play a crucial role. Regarding the role of collective organisations, different sets of institutions grant representation and protection to the craft industries, observing the interest of both the sector and its workers. At the international level, UNESCO represents the organisation that “has [...] endeavoured to develop well-balanced, coherent and concerted action in favour of this industry” (UNESCO, 2019). The main activities of UNESCO concern the promotion of the craft industry through prizes (namely the UNESCO Crafts Prize from 1990 to 2005 and, since 2001, the UNESCO Award of Excellence for Handicrafts), support of local organisations, improvement to the lives and working conditions of craftspeople, protection of craft creation, and harmonisation of data collection on crafts. Moreover, UNESCO supports training and promotional activities and stimulates cooperation between the relevant national bodies and regional, international, and nongovernmental organisations. At the European Level, the World Craft Council Europe is a second-level association that groups national, regional, and professional representative organisations. It promotes crafts and applied arts at the European level, supporting members to form networks, organise events, and enhance awareness around craft locally, among other activities. It acts as a crucial stakeholder in the European governance of the crafts industry. Most of the collective actors and institutions that support and promote craft are at the national and regional levels, where collective bodies, guilds, and associations play a critical role, framing both craftspeople’s agency and institutional structure (Thomas, 2018; Thomas, Harvey, & Hawkins, 2013). As craft is heavily linked to local society, its associations and collective bodies tend to take different forms locally as they represent the interests of a particular craft or a set of crafts. Their main activities tend to include regulating and stimulating training and education; organising events, retail venues, and exhibitions; and raising awareness of their activities. Very often, such local collective bodies work together with national organisations (e.g., the Craft Council and Heritage Craft Council in the UK, the Institut National des Métiers d’Art in France, and Confartigianato in Italy). One of the most critical actions of collective bodies is the creation of a common brand that guarantees qualities and particular features of the products and creates a network of producers (Santagata, 2002).

From a historical perspective, scholars have also remarked on the role that craft guilds played in offering institutional, organisational, and practical support to local artisans. Following Lourens and Lucassen, craft guilds are defined here as “organizations that unite members of the same occupational group, with as their most important goal the furthering of their economic interests, but not without taking into account the general well-being of their group as well” (cit. in Soly, 2008). These organisations, mainly located in urban areas, spread to western Europe via southern Italy and reached French and Flemish cities, Germany, and England in the 12th century, followed by Spain in the middle of the 13th century (De Moor, 2008). The guild system played a crucial role in organising the collective action of artisans: as Richardson highlighted, “they had a common theme. Guild members acted to increase their incomes, and their efforts required action in concert. Members had to cooperate. Each had to do his part for the guild to attain his goals” (Richardson, 2005: 145). Income protection was only one of the goals of guilds. In fact, they supported networking, apprenticeships, and skill training, sustaining and empowering the social identity of artisans. With reference to skills and human capital,

the role of guilds was in the public interest: in a way, they contributed to collectivising human capital, turning it into a sort of commonality (Soly, 2008). An example of this evidence is found in the glassmakers of Venice:

The skills to make quality glass constituted a form of intellectual property. Knowledge was [...] a valuable commodity. In the community of Murano, where practically everyone's livelihood depended on glassmaking to some degree, the knowledge associated with the glass craft was "communal property". Failing to protect or maintain this property was to the detriment of the community, the guild and the Venetian state. (McGray, 1999: 150)

Lastly, regarding the territorial dimension of embeddedness, it should first be noted that craft activities tend to cluster, not necessarily in cities, but rather in more rural areas or smaller cities. Besides the links with the local *milieu* (Santagata, 2006), the "buzz" created in these clusters, shared workspaces, suppliers and help with distribution, closeness to nature, and the chosen lifestyle (Luckman, 2018) are the main reasons that explain why this sector clusters. Scholars have extensively explored the connection between CCI and spaces/places/territories. Academic attention has been particularly focused on the analysis of the main factors that make places successful in developing CCI (see European Commission, 2010; UNDP/UNCTAD, 2008, Tay 2005; Scott 2006; Yun, 2008; Kong & O'Connor 2009). According to Lazzaretti, Domenech, and Capone (2009), these analyses may be summarised in five perspectives. The first emphasises the endowment and strategic role of artistic and cultural heritage in fostering the co-location of CCI: the literature on cultural districts (Frost-Kumpf, 1998; Santagata, 2002; Lazzaretti, 2008), cultural clusters (Van den Berg et al., 2000; Mommaas, 2004), creative cities and cultural quarters (Landry and Bianchini, 1995; Wynne, 1992) acknowledges cultural heritage as a key factor in the clustering of CCI and the activation of knowledge-based productive *filières*²¹ (Pilotti & Rinaldin, 2004). The second interpretation stresses the role of spatial agglomeration and the concentration of productive resources and actors (Ohlin, 1933; Hoover, 1937) and focuses on the so-called external economies. According to this theory, creative firms can cluster to benefit from the localised presence of a skilled labour market, specialised suppliers, and knowledge spillovers ("localisation economies") as well as from the urban dimension, or the density and diversity of the social and productive activities ("urbanisation economies") that encourage entrepreneurship, innovation, and the exchange of knowledge among firms and industries (Ohlin, 1993; Hoover, 1937; Jacobs, 1961, 1969; Hoover & Vernon, 1959; Ciccone & Hall, 1966). Connected to this interpretation is the concept of "related variety". Drawn from economic geography (Frenken & Boschma, 2003), this concept has been applied to the study of the CCI from Lazzaretti (2009) to demonstrate that spatial proximity among firms can turn into cognitive proximity (Nooteboom, 2000), enabling clustered creative firms to share, exchange, and transfer competences, knowledge, and innovation through cross-fertilisation processes. The fourth interpretation highlights the externalities connected to the existence of human capital (Rauch, 1993; Ciccone, Hall 1996) intended as the availability of competences and talent. This contribution leads to Florida's creative

²¹ *Filière* is the French equivalent of the concepts of "value chain" or "supply chain".

class theory, which calls attention to how high shares of talent, technology, and tolerance can transform cities into poles of attraction for creative individuals and firms (Florida, 2002; 2005).

As demonstrated by Lazzeretti, Domenech, and Capone (2009), the relationship between the clustering of creative employment and the abovementioned determinants could be highly nonlinear. In fact, according to the authors, *“the forces behind clustering and their intensity are not unique, and that there are several ways in which creative industries cluster”* (2009, p. 29). These insights can help to develop a better understanding of the reasons why creative firms co-locate (cluster) in territories (geographical notion of space). Although craft enterprises have specific features and needs, the examined body of knowledge also applies to them. Moreover, craft activities are embedded within institutional and historical legacies, contexts, specific culturally constructed contexts, and place-based cultures. To quote Hawkins and Price, this means that to examine their “geographies of making”, it is necessary to explore the “making of these geographies” (see Hawkins and Price, 2018: 2). This implies also considering the role of the material environment in shaping relations between craft-based manufacturing and territories. Building on this point, Gibson presented a framework for understanding the rise of contemporary craft-based manufacturing in particular locations (Gibson 2016). Based on the case of the craft boot-making cluster in El Paso (Texas), he demonstrated that the presence and availability of particular input materials, the latent skills in the local labour market, and their reconfiguration into new communities of practice are key factors in the resurgence of craft production (see also Blundel & Smith 2013; Patchett 2017; Fox Miller 2019). Similarly, Marques, Santos, Ratten, and Barros (2018) demonstrated that young entrepreneurs in northern Portugal have been able to develop commercial activities that benefit from endogenous materials, the local culture, and traditional knowledge. Focusing on the case of craft beer production, Musso demonstrated that the lack of a local, rooted production culture hinders or limits the development possibilities of the local economic system due to the absence of cooperative relationships among local actors (Musso 2020). As Gibson argued, *“[s]uch aspects of materiality linger in city landscapes, in the bodies of manual workers, and become resources that direct new geographies of craft production in an era of cultural capitalism where authenticity is a key source of value”* (Gibson 2016, p. 65). Moreover, other institutional dimensions, such as specific policies and regulatory frameworks, can contribute to structuring the context and activities where craft-based enterprises occur.

The case of Italian craft-based districts could be helpful for demonstrating the multiplicity and interdependence of the examined dimensions of embeddedness. Regarding Italy, scholars have remarked that CCIs exhibit different patterns of clustering according to the very nature of their activity: whereas content and service-oriented creative activities tend to locate in large metropolitan areas (i.e., Rome and Milan), design-related industries present different co-location models due to their ‘dual’ nature (design and manufacturing activities are strictly interconnected). Then, if “design emerges from more complex and intangible interactions between actors located in different sites along the production pipeline” (Bertacchini & Borrione, 2013: 11), manufacturing activities, based on crafts, traditional skills, and/or both artisanal and industrial techniques, tend to locate in specialised districts. In their mapping of craft-based industries, Bertacchini and Borrione identified craft-

specialised districts in Emilia Romagna (i.e., ceramic tile production in the Sassuolo district), Tuscany (i.e., textile production in Prato and the jewellery district of Arezzo), the Adriatic Marches (i.e., shoes, clothing, furniture, and leather products in Pesaro, Ascoli, and Macerata), Veneto (i.e., textiles, sport footwear, glass frames, jewellery, and furniture manufacturers in Treviso and Vicenza), and the north-western regions of Piedmont and Lombardia (i.e., the textile and clothing industrial districts of Biella and Como). According to the authors, these clusters are clearly rooted in the path-dependent formation of industrial and manufacturing districts in the so-called “Third Italy” (Bagnasco, 1977).

The case of ceramic tile production in Sassuolo is highly interesting because it demonstrates a clear interconnection between the three dimensions of embeddedness. Mentioned in the seminal contribution of Porter (1990), Sassuolo, a medium-sized town near Modena, has since the 1960s been one of the major European production centres for tile manufacturing. The industry is rooted in ancient, artisanal traditions. In fact, in 1731, local artisans set up “La fabbrica della Maiolica”, the first company dedicated to the production of majolica in the town. The enterprise was facilitated by the mercantilist policies of Duke Francesco III d'Este, which favoured production and export. Thus, the company developed a monopolistic position within the borders of the Este Duchy (corresponding to the provinces of Modena and Reggio Emilia) and laid the first stone for the birth of a craft tradition. Several factors contributed to the development of the cluster and made its connection to the territory strategic. At first, the availability of natural resources (i.e., clay deposits close to Sassuolo, the abundance of water, and the availability of methane gas for firing the clay) allowed for low transportation costs. Moreover, the presence of local banks (notably the Banca Popolare di Modena) facilitated access to capital and the birth of new entrepreneurial activities. Finally, the area benefitted from laws established in the 1950s to favour investments in underdeveloped regions by way of tax exemptions or credits (Muzzioli et al., 2006; Serri, 2008). Over the years, the cluster has been able to achieve critical technological breakthroughs (i.e., the “single-firing” technique and the “gres porcellanato”) and growth at significant rates, becoming one of the world’s major ceramic tile production centres (Vertova, 2004). The district takes advantage of the dense network of suppliers and specialisations present in Emilia Romagna and forms local production systems in several economic fields: clay mining, refining, and atomising as well as tile manufacturing, including pressing, decoration (chemical), and burning in kilns. Especially relevant is the production of machinery and equipment for tile production (including kilns, presses, and other equipment), in addition to design, marketing, and logistics among other areas, all of which are focused on tiles. Despite the entry of China as the largest ceramic producer worldwide changing the scenario, the cluster of Sassuolo has been able to resist and defend its position, and its resilience and innovation strategies are objects of study today (Russo, 2004). These strategies, including the nature and form of the relations of the actors interconnected within the cluster, are relevant in the embeddedness perspective. In fact, these relations have been described as a “virtuous circle of interrelations among actors [...] emerged not only as the result of the purely cooperative game, but also from the interplay of competitive relations” (Russo, 2004: 5). These patterns of interactions seem “a key to interpreting the dynamics of change in the district, characterized by cooperation, competition and innovation” (ibid.). Furthermore, local institutions, collective actors, and strategic stakeholders play a strategic role in promoting and defending the

cluster. This is the case for Confindustria Ceramica (formerly Assopiastrelle), which represents, supports, and connects affiliated companies; organises Cersaie (the most important ceramic exhibition held annually in Bologna); and participates in Coverings, the major tradeshow for the sector in the United States. Moreover, Italian ceramic manufacturers are represented at international events and initiatives by the “Ceramics of Italy” trademark, the institutional image of the Italian ceramic industry and a symbol of the quality and innovation of Italian ceramic tiles. Finally, the Sassuolo district is served by the Ceramic Centre, a research consortium founded in 1976 that includes the University of Bologna, Confindustria Ceramica, and Legacoop. The Centre, part of the Industrial Research Laboratory of the Emilia-Romagna High Technology Network, has headquarters in Bologna and Sassuolo and guarantees companies the skills, tools, and resources necessary for innovating products and processes within the ceramic industry. In 2016, the Municipality of Sassuolo signed a programme of promotion for local, traditional productions with the Municipality of Faenza, which was titled “Ceramic Land”. Faenza, two hours from Sassuolo, is today acknowledged as one of the major international poles of artistic ceramics production. As observed for Sassuolo, the town owes its relevance to the following natural and social factors: an abundance of clay deposits, proximity to the relevant cultural and commercial hubs of Firenze and Bologna, and the existence of a long tradition of *maestri d’arte*. These factors fertilised the territory as well as founded a local know-how and an idiosyncratic sense of aesthetics, which have made the town famous since the 16th century (Fondazione Cologni, 2009). In the 1960s, the town developed its own trademark (“Ceramiche di Faenza”) to designate and protect the local production of artistic ceramics. A dense and interconnected network of cultural and economic actors and initiatives arose around this activity; this is the case for the International Museum of Ceramics, one of the most important ceramic museums in the world; the Ente Ceramica Faenza, founded in 1977 to protect and promote the Faenza ceramist; the International Competition of Contemporary Art Ceramics, an event of international prestige, enriched by collateral exhibitions and an exhibition-market; the International Biennial of Ceramic Antiques; the Polo Ceramico Agency, which performs services to promote the development of the Faenza ceramic district in the artistic, industrial, and technological sectors; the Institute of Technological Research for Ceramics of the National Research Council; the Art for Ceramics Institute, which provides high qualifications in the artistic, restoration, and technological sectors; the Higher Institute for Artistic Industries, technicians, and designers; and the Consorzio Ceramisti, which promotes the national and international distribution of local crafts and potters.

1.1.5 The fragmented regulatory framework relating to craft

As anticipated in the previous section, regulatory frameworks can influence craft production and contribute to structuring the context in which craft-based enterprises occur. Regulation occurs at different scales (i.e., local, regional, national, EU, and global) and each scale convenes different sets of actors, legal and policy contexts, regulations, temporalities, and particularities. All of these scales are simultaneously distinct and intertwined. In the context of the CICERONE project, the regulatory framework covering CCI encompasses both policy and legislation, but it also includes frameworks

that exist at the local, regional, national, EU, and supranational levels. As Borén and Power suggested in the CICERONE report D3.3 titled “*A brief review of regulation for creative and cultural industries*”, this interscalarity complicates the identification of coherent regulatory frameworks for European CCI; moreover, CCIs cross-cut policy areas and regulatory fields (or *silos*), making it difficult to implement systematic policy support regimes. As if that was not enough, depending on the considered policy area, the competences required to take action in the field of CCIs are fragmented through different European, national, or local institutions (Borén & Power, 2021). As a general rule, regulations on CCIs tend to straddle two main policy pillars: (a) industrial policy at the national/supranational level, including trade and competition policy; and (b) cultural policy, which is mainly enacted at the national and regional/local levels. When it comes to craft, the scenario hereby represented becomes much more fragmented. As is discussed in depth in the following pages, this fragmentation mainly relates to the ways of conceiving crafts both at the EU and national levels. On the one hand, at the EU level, a specific framework for craft-based enterprises does not exist as they are included in the broader category of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). On the other hand, at the national level, no consistency exists between the legal definitions that operate in each Member State, and not all Member States have a legal definition of craft. Moreover, relating to national legislations, different visions of craft influence the ways in which this activity is addressed by public policies: where craft is considered a cultural heritage or where the artistic craft industry is considered, the policies aimed at it are normally implemented by culture ministries; by contrast, where considered a (creative) industry, craft is addressed by policies designed and implemented by economic and development ministries (see Mignosa, 2019: 51-60).

In the context of this overview, we focus mainly on the EU regulatory level, clarifying the reasons why a single “map” of the current regulatory environment for crafts is almost impossible to create. Subsection 1.5.1.1 tackles the problem of a lack of a formal definition of a craft enterprise at the European level and presents (where possible) the ways in which each EU Member State has defined, within its own legislation, what a craft enterprise is (an in-depth textbox is dedicated to the definition of crafts in Italy and Sweden – the countries to which the research units responsible for this report belong). Subsection 1.5.1.2 briefly discusses the legal basis for the policy intervention of the EU institutions; then, based on secondary sources, the major challenges and policy issues for craft enterprises are presented. Lastly, Subsection 1.5.1.3 presents the major policy actions taken by the EU institutions in the “area” of SMEs from 2008 to the present day.

1.1.5.1 Struggling with definitions: How to frame crafts within EU and national legislations?

As widely discussed in the previous paragraphs, the craft industry in Europe is highly diverse and comprises a great variety of economic activities, trades, and professions. Despite this, a shared definition of craft-type enterprise is not provided at the EU level. Attempts to establish a standard definition have been mostly unsuccessful, and the industry has been subsumed into the general

category of SMEs. Due to the absence of a common definition of SMEs, the EC decided to ensure a coherent and effective framework where policies in favour of these types of enterprises could be formed. In 1996, following the *White Paper on Growth, Competitiveness and Employment*²² and the *Integrated Programme in Favour of SMEs and the Craft Sector*,²³ the *Commission Recommendation of 3 April 1996 (1996/280/EC)*²⁴ established a precise set of requirements for recognising SMEs, specifying that micro-enterprises “should not be confused with craft enterprises”. Referring to the latter, the EC stated that they “will continue to be defined at national level due to their specific characteristics”. Consequently, at the EU governance level, the craft industry is covered by the regulatory framework of SMEs and placed out from the cultural policy area.

In 2003, the original definition of SMEs was revised to reflect the major economic changes affecting the business demography of SMEs. Finalising a wide discussion among the EC, EU Member States, business organisations, and experts, a new version of the SME definition was adopted with the *Commission Recommendation of 6 May 2003 (2003/361/EC)*.²⁵ According to the Recommendation, the main factors that determine whether an enterprise is an SME are staff headcount and either turnover or balance sheet total. As a general rule, the category of MSMEs comprises enterprises that employ fewer than 250 individuals and have an annual turnover not exceeding €50 million, and/or an annual balance sheet total not exceeding €43 million. Within this macro-category, further classifications are provided as follows:

Microenterprises	Small enterprises	Medium-sized enterprises
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ fewer than 10 individuals • Have an annual turnover or annual balance sheet total that does not exceed EUR 2 million 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ fewer than 50 individuals • Have an annual turnover and/or annual balance sheet total that does not exceed EUR 10 million 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employ fewer than 250 individuals • Either have an annual turnover that does not exceed EUR 50 million or an annual balance sheet not exceeding EUR 43 million

To ensure a better understanding of the real economic position and power of SMEs, the EU institutions provided a further distinction between *autonomous*, *partner*, and *linked* enterprises.²⁶

²² European Commission (1993). *Growth, competitiveness, employment. The challenges and ways forward into the 21st century: White paper*, EU Publications.

²³ Communication from the Commission of 3 June 1994 on Integrated Programme in Favour of SMEs and the Craft Sector, COM (1994) 207 final.

²⁴ Commission Recommendation of 3 April 1996 concerning the definition of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (96/280/EC).

²⁵ Commission Recommendation of 6 May 2003 concerning the definition of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (2003/361/EC).

²⁶ SMEs are autonomous when they are completely independent or have one or more minority partnerships (each less than 25%) with other enterprises; if holdings with other enterprises rise to at least 25% but no more than 50%, the relationship is deemed to be between partner enterprises; if holdings with other enterprises exceed the 50% threshold, they are linked enterprises.

A shared definition of craft enterprises does not even emerge from the exploration of individual EU Member States' legislations. A comparison of national definitions of crafts was conducted in November 2001 by the Istituto Tagliacarne²⁷ in the context of the elaboration of a statistical and economic methodology for quantifying small enterprises and enterprises with craft-trade characteristics in the EU. The analysis documented the existence of highly heterogeneous definitions of crafts and remarked that this diversity, combined with the scarce supranational coordination in the collection of data on SMEs, was hindering any attempt to study and quantify the role and contribution of craft enterprises to the EU economy. Analysing the legal definition of a craft enterprise in 15 EU Member States, the Istituto Tagliacarne presented the following three main classification approaches:

Sector/size approach	Professional approach	Artistic approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The definition of a craft enterprise is based on the size of the firm in terms of the number of employees • This approach was adopted in France, Italy, the Netherlands, and Portugal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The definition of a craft enterprise is based on the classification of a list of “craft occupations” requiring specific training or qualifications • This approach was adopted in Austria, Germany, Luxembourg, and Sweden 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only firms exclusively involved in artistic activities are classed as craft industries • This approach was adopted in Spain

Hybrid approaches or no legal definitions are provided by Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Greece, and the United Kingdom. This set of problems made clear that a statistical comparison of data between Member States was impossible. To provide a practical solution, the Istituto Tagliacarne proposed a standard statistical definition of a craft enterprise. The researchers identified a common minimum statistical basis based on four factors that could help to define and quantify craft enterprises in all EU countries. These factors were as follows: (i) the legal nature of the enterprise; (ii) the type of professions undertaken by the enterprise; (iii) the economic activity (NACE Code) of the enterprise; and (iv) the dimension of the enterprise expressed in number of workers.

This proposal has never been integrated into EU statistical investigations or the EU regulatory framework; therefore, the craft industry continues to be included in the general area of SMEs.

In 2011, research funded by the EU²⁸ partially updated the analysis conducted by the Istituto Tagliacarne. Focusing on the legislations of Austria, Bulgaria, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Poland,

²⁷ Istituto Guglielmo Tagliacarne (2001), *Proposal for the development of a methodology for the collecting and grouping of statistical data on small craft businesses in Europe*, https://ec.europa.eu/growth/content/proposal-development-methodology-collecting-and-grouping-statistical-data-small-craft-0_it.

²⁸ Buschfeld, D. and others (2011), *Future Skills Needs in Micro and Craft(-type) Enterprises up to 2020*, Final Report of the Research Project “Identification of future skills needs in micro and craft (-type) enterprises up to 2020 - European

and the UK, the investigation developed a *qualitative* understanding of the craft enterprises and demonstrated that, in many of the observed legislations, they were substantially equated to the statistical category of microenterprise. These enterprises are characterised by the central role of the owner, who is directly involved in the business; the personal responsibility of the owner and his/her preference to be financially independent; the prevailing tailor-made production or production in small quantities; the crucial role of craft, technical, and managerial competences, which are transferred via person-to-person relationships (e.g., through apprentice systems); and the close relationship with clients, craft organisations, and local communities. The study also provided an in-depth analysis of the aforementioned national legislations, focusing on the following four variables: the existence of a legal definition of craft, the definition of a dimensional threshold, the existence of a craft chamber system, and the legal definition of craft professions. The results of the analysis are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4. Status of craft enterprises across European countries (source: Buschfeld *et al.*, 2011: 46)

	General understanding of crafts	Legal definition	Definition of maximum number of employees	Craft chamber system	Craft professions as legally defined
Austria	List of regularized craft professions in the Trade Act	Yes	No	No	42
Bulgaria	List of occupational profiles considered as crafts	Yes	No	Yes	129
Denmark	Micro and small enterprises in production, repair and services	No	50	No	62
France	Independent economic activity in the field of a legally defined craft trade with a limited number of employees	Yes	10	Yes	250 (approx. 100 trades)
Germany	List of legally defined and regularized craft professions	Yes	No	Yes	94
Italy	Enterprises up to a certain size meeting a number of legal requirements	Yes	up to 40 under certain conditions	No	103
Poland	Independent economic activity in certain sectors and up to a certain size	Yes	15	yes	103
United Kingdom	Term is only used with view on artisan activities	No	No	No	Not defined

As the table displays, among the investigated countries, only Denmark and the UK do not have a formal definition of crafts. As for Denmark, craft enterprises belong to the “small enterprise size” group (i.e., enterprises with fewer than 50 employees); moreover, registration as a craft business requires certain competence certificates. With reference to the UK, craft does not exist as a legal category, and the only existing characterisation of craft and craft-related activities comes from a definition of the Craft Council, which is based on the following three main criteria: the prominence of the human factor in all phases of production, the use of natural components (e.g., glass, textiles, and wood), and a certain

Commission, DG Enterprise and Industry, Unit F.2 – Small Businesses, Cooperatives, Mutuels and CSR; financed by the European Union. See pages 39–46.

dimension of creativity. On the other side, Austria, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Italy, and Poland have a legal definition of crafts, which is in France, Italy, and Poland accompanied by the provision of a dimensional threshold expressed in terms of numbers of employees. Lastly, except for the UK, all of the investigated countries provide legal definitions of craft professions, which in some cases are registered and integrated by the territorial systems of the Chambers of Crafts and Commerce. To further reiterate the issue the following boxes provide a definition of craft in the two European countries where the case studies are located.

Box no. 1: Definition of crafts in Italian legislation

In Italy, crafts are mentioned in the National Constitution of the Republic. Art. 45(2) acknowledges the relevance of these enterprises for socioeconomic development and states that *“the law safeguards and promotes the handicrafts”*. The legal framework for the industry is provided by National Law n. 443 of August 1985 and subsequent amendments. The law sets out three sets of requirements that define a craft enterprise: subjective requirements, industry and legal form requirements, and dimensional requirements.

Subjective criteria define who the owner of the craft enterprise is. Art. 3 states that the craft enterprise is managed by the artisan. According to Art. 2, the artisan is the owner of the enterprise and assumes full responsibility of risks and burdens derived from the management of the enterprise; he/she directs and manages the enterprise professionally and is directly involved in the production process. When exercising activities that require special training or imply responsibility for the protection of customers, the craftsman must be equipped with specific technical-professional requisites established by state law. Industry requirements refer to the production output of the enterprise. In fact, Art. 3(1) states that the craft enterprise should produce goods (including semifinished ones) or deliver services in all sectors, excluding agriculture, commercial services, intermediation, and beverages and food. The following paragraph of the article specifies the legal form that a craft enterprise should have. Finally, Art. 4 sets out dimensional requirements. Different dimensional thresholds, based on the number of employees, are set according to the prevailing economic activity of the enterprises. To provide an idea, as for the artistic, traditional, and tailor-made garment production sectors, craft enterprises should not exceed 32 employees (including a maximum of 16 apprentices) or 40 employees (additional units should be apprentices); in nonserial productions, enterprises should not exceed 18 employees (including a maximum of nine apprentices) or 22 employees (additional units should be apprentices), whereas in serial productions (but not fully automated), enterprises should not exceed nine employees (including a maximum of five apprentices) or 12 employees (additional units should be apprentices). As a general rule, home workers and workers with disabilities are not considered for the size threshold.

Building on the distribution of powers enshrined in Art. 117 of the Italian Constitution, the abovementioned National Law transfers to the Regions the power to adopt measures aimed at protecting and promoting craft activities (see Art. 1). Notably, the Regions can exercise legislative and administrative functions concerning craft enterprises' access to finance, technical assistance, research and development, professional training, and export. Regions also hold a Special Register of the enterprises in which craft enterprises should register; registration is the legal and mandatory condition for benefiting from access to credit facilities. Lastly, the Decree of the President of the Republic n. 1202 of 1956 lists 12 professional categories and 103 jobs defined as craft professions. The list was formally revoked in 1985 but its provisions continued to be applied until regions adopted their own dispositions concerning a classification of craft professions. In 2001, with the Decree of the President of the Republic n. 288, the list was updated to include 13 professional categories and 158 jobs.

Box no. 2: Definition of crafts in Swedish legislation

As with many of EU Member States nations, no clear legal definition exists of what constitutes crafts within Sweden, nor any legal protected status of the wider concept of craftspeople. There are, however, a

number of public institutions and departments that act to protect and promote different forms of crafts, which can be understood as indicative of what the Swedish regulatory framework considers craftspersonship.

One such specific government department is the Sloyd department (Hemslöjdsnämnden), which works to promote and support craftspeople working in the sloyd sector (i.e., traditional forms of domestic manufacture, such as wood working, felting, and brass work), mainly through project stipends and the encouragement of entrepreneurialism among sloyd professionals. The government has also assigned an organisation, the Artistic Craft Centre (Konsthantverkscentrum), the task of promoting the artistic crafts and funds them through the Swedish Arts Council.

Additionally, the government have assigned to the Nationalmuseet the task of collecting and having important pieces of contemporary crafts represented in their collection for future presentation. The government also rewards stipends to craftspeople and craft projects through the Swedish Artistic grant's committee. By understanding these different initiatives and types of institutional support that the government focuses on, one can see that it is a particular form of craftspersonship that tend to be premiered – the pure artistic crafts and the more traditional forms of craftspersonship.

1.1.5.2 Legal basis for EU actions and key policy challenges for SMEs

As discussed in the previous sections, due to the lack of a shared definition of crafts at the supranational level, the craft enterprises fall into the general category of MSMEs. In terms of regulations, this implies that “size” is the first character (and, in some way, the only character) that is relevant when EU institutions think of craft enterprises. As discussed below, it is not a case that the whole policy strategy for SMEs is based on the “Think Small First” principle. This circumstance has led organisations such as the European Economic and Social Committee to highlight that “the concept of *crafts* is another issue that needs to be dealt with. We must think about craft companies as having the entrepreneurial value of custom manufacturing. As such, the size of a company should not determine whether it can be (legally) classified as a craft company”.²⁹

To examine the EU regulatory framework for SMEs, it is necessary to first clarify the legal basis that allows EU institutions to take legal action. Competences for regulating MSMEs are distributed between the EU and the Member States according to the principle of conferral enshrined in Art. 5(2) of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU)³⁰: “The Union shall act only within the limits of the competences conferred upon it by the EU MS in the Treaties to attain the objective set out there in”; “competences not conferred upon the Union in the Treaties remain with the Member States.” According to Art. 3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU),³¹ the EU has an exclusive competence in highly limited fields (the customs union; competition law necessary for the functioning of the internal market; monetary policy of the Eurozone; and common commercial policy), whereas competences are shared between Member States and the EU in the areas of the internal market (Art. 114 TFEU), employment (Art. 9 and 145–150 TFEU, with a special emphasis on coordination ex Art. F TFEU), social policy (Art. 151–157 TFEU) and the European Social Fund (Art.

²⁹ <https://www.eesc.europa.eu/en/members-groups/categories/msmes-crafts-and-family-business-category>

³⁰ Consolidated versions of the TEU and the TFEU, 2012/C 326/01.

³¹ *Idem*.

162–164 TFEU); economic, social, and territorial cohesion (Art. 174–178 TFEU); research and technological development (Art. 179–188 TFEU); and economic, financial, and technical cooperation with third countries (Art. 212 TFEU). In regard to the key competences for industrial policy, the EU’s power is limited to supporting the actions of Member States. In fact, as Art. 173 TFEU highlights, “the Union *contributes* to the achievement of the objectives” set out in paragraph 1 of the article³²; the EC “may take any useful initiative to *promote*” coordination among Member States, such as “initiatives aiming at the establishment of guidelines and indicators, the organisation of exchange of best practice, and the preparation of the necessary elements for periodic monitoring and evaluation”; lastly, the European Parliament and Council “may decide on specific measures in *support* of action taken in the Member States to achieve the objectives set out in paragraph 1, excluding any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the Member States”.

As can be seen, most of the competencies connected to MSMEs are shared between States and the EU, which confirms the general prominence of the former over the supranational governance level. Nevertheless, over time, the EU institutions have adopted significant actions for SMEs. The keystone of the EU regulation is the Small Business Act, adopted by the EC in 2008. Built on the concepts elaborated in the 2005 Community *Lisbon Programme for a Modern SME Policy*,³³ the Small Business Act marks a breakthrough in the EU SME policy and provides for a novel, overarching approach that recognises the central role of SMEs in the EU economy. The Small Business Act is anchored on the “Think Small First” principle, which implies the following:

*Policy makers give full consideration to SMEs at the early policy development stage. Ideally rules impacting on business should be created from the SMEs point of view or in other words, SMEs should be considered by public authorities as being their “prime customers” as far as business regulation is concerned. The principle relies on the fact that “one size does not fit all” but a lighter touch approach can also be beneficial to larger businesses. Conversely, rules and procedures designed for large companies create disproportionate, if not unbearable burdens for SMEs as they lack the economies of scale.*³⁴

In relaunching the Lisbon strategy for jobs and growth, the Small Business Act identifies four priority intervention areas and 10 principles that should guide the design and implementation of policies for SMEs, at both the EU and Member State levels. The priority areas stress the need to promote entrepreneurship, reduce regulatory burdens, provide access to finance, and support the internationalisation of the considered enterprises. The 10 principles emphasise, among other things, the need to create a positive and rewarding cultural environment for entrepreneurs, including the possibility to give a second chance to those who have faced bankruptcy; the need to translate the

³² These objectives include accelerating the adjustment of industry to structural changes; encouraging an environment favorable to initiative and the development of undertakings throughout the Union, particularly small and medium-sized undertakings; encouraging an environment favorable to cooperation between undertakings; and fostering better exploitation of the industrial potential of policies of innovation, research, and technological development.

³³ European Commission (2005), *Implementing the community Lisbon program—modern SME policy for growth and employment*, 10 Nov 2005, COM (2005) 551 final.

³⁴ Report of the Expert Group (2009), *Think Small First – Considering SME interests in policymaking*.

“Think Small First” principle in practice, i.e. by adapting policy tools to SMEs’ needs, by making public administration responsive to these firms, by facilitating their access to finance, and by developing a legal and business environment supportive of timely payments in commercial transactions. Moreover, the principles bring attention to promoting skill upgrading in SMEs and all forms of innovation, to encourage SMEs to benefit from the growth of markets and enable them to turn environmental challenges into opportunities. Building on the Small Business Act, several initiatives have been adopted by the EU institutions, which are briefly presented in Section 1.5.3.

Despite regulatory efforts at the EU level, SMEs continue to demand more adequate and tailored policies. A 2019 study on the EU policy framework on SMEs identified the major challenges and problems that SMEs – including craft enterprises – must deal with.³⁵ Building on a literature review and quantitative analysis, the report highlighted the major factors that limit SMEs’ potential. These factors can be summed up as follows:

Limited availability of skilled labour

According to the SAFE Survey,³⁶ the scarcity of skilled labour was the most pressing problem for 25% of SMEs in 2018. Due to competition of big companies and increased labour costs, these SMEs have difficulties in hiring skilled workers. Furthermore, because of the credit constraints provoked by the financial crisis, smaller enterprises are not able to invest sufficiently in training their staff, limiting their capacity to adjust to technological changes. The lack of training translates into a lack of innovation, hindering the capacity of these businesses to fight external competition, especially from developing countries. The lack of competence and skilled labour has also been designated the second key challenge faced by SMEs by the Local and Regional Authorities, which were interviewed in the aforementioned study from 2019.

Difficulty in accessing finance

Although this issue was indicated as the most pressing problem by only 7% of SMEs involved in 2018 SAFE Survey, access to finance has remained a crucial issue for EU SMEs since the 2008 financial crisis. In fact, their financial needs are still significant, especially for fixed investments (41%) and working capital (37%), but the costs for obtaining finance are still high. Moreover, access to public financial support continues to be a negative factor. The Local and Regional Authorities stress the role that banks and financial institutions can play for supporting SMEs.

Excessive regulations and administrative burden

The regulatory framework is considered a burden for SMEs both in terms of compliance costs (i.e., privacy and safety regulation) and requirements such as fiscal obligations and participation in public procurement. Generally speaking, SMEs are less efficient than large firms in dealing with regulatory environments,³⁷ which can translate into a competitive disadvantage. Moreover, the production,

³⁵ European Committee of the Regions (2019), *EU policy framework on SMEs. State of play and challenges*, European Union Publications, doi:10.2863/612657.

³⁶ European Commission (2018), *Survey on the Access to Finance of Enterprises (SAFE) – Analytical Report*.

³⁷ OECD (2018), *Improving the business environment for SMEs through effective regulation*, p. 3.

distribution, and sale of goods and services in Europe are subject to numerous administrative requirements and regulations (i.e., registering a firm, certification of products and services, mutual recognition schemes, emissions requirements, the security of industrial goods, safeguarding of intellectual property rights, and technical standards), and these factors affect SMEs' capacity to innovate and reach global markets.³⁸ Referring to the public sector, the Local and Regional Authorities surveyed in 2019 considered the main problem in supporting SMEs to be a lack of personnel resources and competences.

In 2019, the European employer organisation SMEUnited – the Association of Crafts and SMEs in Europe presented a memorandum for the European elections³⁹ in which European decision makers were invited to *act* in favour of MSMEs instead of just *talking* about them. SMEUnited encouraged decision makers “to shape Europe for SMEs and shape SMEs for Europe”, relaunching a full application of the “Think Small First” principle. Building on the results of a survey conducted among SMEUnited member enterprises, the Association presented 10 priorities for craft enterprises and SMEs to be considered in the EU policies. These principles can be summarised as follows:

Friendly and coherent regulatory environment

Craft enterprises and SMEs demand policymakers to create a friendly and coherent regulatory environment for SMEs. This includes a full application of the “Think Small First” principle, paying specific attention to how new national and European rules can impact craft enterprises and SMEs' functioning and competitiveness, with concern paid to their type (e.g., dimension and legal form), industry, and position in the value chain. In addition, SMEs request a comprehensive and transparent dialogue between European policy makers and craft and SME organisations. They ask for the full implementation of EU legislation and decisions in all Member States, and also effective cooperation between Member States to guarantee the cross-border enforcement of judgements and fines; they also request the reduction of barriers within the single market, which hinder SMEs' growth (e.g., different tax systems, IPR protection, and standards).

Structural reforms and barriers to the circular economy

Craft enterprises and SMEs want to be recognised as drivers of social progress and demand structural reforms in the field of employment, labour policies, and social protection systems. These reforms would be necessary for sustaining growth, jobs, and competitiveness and ensuring the sustainability of national welfare systems. Entrepreneurs ask for the removal of all barriers that hamper SMEs' access to the circular economy: they require the introduction of specific measures to foster eco-innovation and measures for reducing energy prices.

³⁸ See Committee of the Regions (2017), *The future of industry in Europe*, pp. 56–58.

³⁹ SMEUnited (2019), *Memorandum for the European elections 2019. Strengthening crafts and SMEs for the future of the European Union*, <https://smeunited.eu/admin/storage/smeunited/smeu-memorandum-2610-pages.pdf>.

Skills and digitisation

Craft enterprises and SMEs encourage a strong programme for reducing the skills gap. This includes the promotion of targeted policy actions for improving high-quality vocational education and training and apprenticeship; for promoting employability and the acquisition of digital and green skills; and for easing access to the EU's labour market for skilled third-country nationals. Moreover, they emphasise the need for programmes to teach and coach an entrepreneurial mindset to the current and future generations of entrepreneurs. Relating to digitisation, enterprises demand specific support to ensure the right level of skills development, capacity building, and access to appropriate infrastructures and data.

Financial support to innovate and invest

Craft enterprises and SMEs suffer from their dependence on bank lending. For this reason, they demand other forms of financing, allowing them to realise riskier projects which are not accepted by banks; venture capital, equity, and bond markets should become more attractive for SMEs and SMEs should become more interesting for investors; and alternative forms of finance should be developed and made accessible to innovative SMEs. New forms of financial support would be necessary to grant competitiveness, dimensional growth, and innovation.

Fair competitiveness and support for internationalisation

Due to their dimensions and limited financial power, craft enterprises and SMEs encounter imbalances in relation with economically more powerful market players, and they demand competition policies that can tackle unfair trading practices and provisions in B2B relations. In addition, they request critical actions to facilitate their access to international markets, including investment protection and trade defence measures.

To conclude, the following visualisation in Figure 1 (see next page) summarises the key policy challenges faced by craft enterprises and SMEs:

Figure 1. Key policy issues faced by craft enterprises and SMEs

1.1.5.3 Major EU policy actions adopted from 2010 to the present

To respond to the challenges and problems faced by craft enterprises and SMEs, since the aforementioned Small Business Act of 2008, the EU institutions have implemented a series of actions concerning the different policy areas highlighted in the previous subsection and affecting – directly or indirectly – the craft industry. The aim of this subsection is to present the major actions.

In 2010, the EC launched *An integrated Industrial Policy for the Globalisation Era*,⁴⁰ which was a novel approach to policy that placed competitiveness and sustainability centre stage in the EU's industrial strategy. Due to the 2007 global crisis, the EU and Member States' industrial policies had assumed a rescue and short-term focus, risking the weakening of the EU's competitiveness and economic stability; to react to this contingency, a 2010 EC Communication stressed the importance of a long-term and structural approach. This approach was characterised by a horizontal basis and sectoral application (all economic sectors are important and require coordinated, European policy responses, but each requires specific adjustments and tailor-made strategies); a global, value, and supply chain orientation (all steps from access to raw materials to after-sale services – inside or outside Europe – must be considered); and regular monitoring of the EU and Member States' competitiveness as well as industrial policies and performances provided by the EC.

Several policy areas have been affected by the new industrial approach. In particular, the EC and the Member States were invited to implement and coordinate activities and policies aimed at improving framework conditions for industries (i.e., improving access to finance for enterprises); strengthening the single market (i.e., enforcing intellectual property rights); supporting new industrial innovation policies and modernising the skills base (i.e., promoting industrial research on advanced manufacturing technologies and encouraging initiatives to modernise Europe's skill base); supporting the integration of capital market and firms, especially SMEs, in global value chains (i.e., better trade and international regulations and specific strategies for supporting the internationalisation of SMEs with concrete measures based on the Small Business Act framework); and promoting industrial modernisation (i.e., developing a long-term strategy to assist the transition to a low-carbon and studying a policy initiative on corporate social responsibility addressing business and human rights, and company disclosure of environmental, social, employment-related, and governance information).

Between 2010 and 2019, several actions were adopted by the EU institutions to unlock the economic potential of SMEs. Although not directly addressed to SMEs, the E-government Action Plans adopted in 2010 and 2016⁴¹ contributed to shaping a more SME-friendly business environment, making administrative procedures simpler for these enterprises (i.e., developing cross-border eGovernment

⁴⁰ European Commission (2010), *An Integrated Industrial Policy for the globalisation era. Putting competitiveness and sustainability at centre stage*, COM (2010) 615.

⁴¹ See: European Commission (2010), *The European eGovernment Action Plan 2011-2015 Harnessing ICT to promote smart, sustainable & innovative Government*, COM (2010) 1539 final; European Commission (2016), *EU eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 Accelerating the digital transformation of government*, COM (2016) 0179 final.

services for citizens and businesses and promoting cross border e-procurement) and removing digital barriers to the Digital Single Market.⁴²

In 2011, the EC launched its Action plan to improve access to finance for SMEs.⁴³ The Plan recognised that “Europe’s economic success depends largely on the growth of Small and Medium sized Enterprises (SMEs) achieving their potential”. To facilitate SMEs’ growth and innovation, the EC presented a set of regulatory and financial measures. The former included a taxation reform benefiting SMEs, new State aid rules relevant for SMEs’ access to finance, an innovative regime for socially innovative business (European Social Entrepreneurship Funds), and other measures for improving the visibility of SME markets and reducing all kinds of burdens for SMEs. The financial measures comprised a new financial instrument to facilitate SMEs’ access to finance⁴⁴ and additional initiatives to improve lending to SMEs.

In 2012, the EC adopted the Regulatory Fitness and Performance Programme (REFIT),⁴⁵ aiming to make EU legislation more simple, effective, and efficient in achieving its policy objectives. The Programme did not specifically mention SMEs but could contribute to lessening SMEs’ administrative and regulatory burdens thanks to the introduction, implementation, and monitoring of a set of smart regulation tools. In the same year, the Guide to Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation⁴⁶ encouraged policymakers to design, draft, and implement national/regional research and innovation strategies for smart specialisation (RIS 3).⁴⁷ Regarding SMEs, the Guide stressed their key role in creating jobs, stimulating growth, and introducing new products and services to the marketplace; it remarked on the necessity of supporting the innovation capacity of SMEs, heavily depending on regional environment. The Guide stimulated the implementation of the Small Business Act at a regional level and urged Regional Authorities to put SMEs’ needs at the centre of their innovation agendas. Policymakers were also encouraged to adopt actions and measures to support SMEs’ innovation activities (i.e., facilitating their access to risk capitals and supporting their R&D activities) and to create a positive environment in which entrepreneurship could occur (i.e., stimulating initiatives to promote an entrepreneurial spirit and to foster enterprise creation or development, encouraging Erasmus for young entrepreneurs).

⁴² The Action Plans are based on the four political priorities identified in the Malmö Declaration: “Empower citizens and businesses”; “Reinforce mobility in the Single Market”, “Enable efficiency and effectiveness”; and “Create the necessary key enablers and pre-conditions to make things happen”.

⁴³ European Commission (2010) *An action plan to improve access to finance for SMEs*, COM (2011) 870 final.

⁴⁴ The financial instrument was funded by the *Programme for the Competitiveness of Enterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises 2014-2020 (COSME)*, the *Horizon 2020 Programme*, and the *Creative Europe Programme*.

⁴⁵ European Commission (2012), *EU Regulatory Fitness*, COM (2012) 746 final.

⁴⁶ European Commission (2012), *Guide to Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, doi:10.2776/65746.

⁴⁷ RIS 3 are integrated, place-based economic transformation agendas that focus policy support and investments on key national/regional priorities, challenges, and needs for knowledge-based development, including ICT-related measures. These agendas build on each country’s/region’s strengths, competitive advantages, and potential for excellence and support for both technological and practice-based innovation, aiming to stimulate the private sector and encourage innovation and experimentation.

Deepening this point, in 2012 the EC also launched the Entrepreneurship 2020 Action Plan.⁴⁸ Building on the SBA (2010) and the EC Industrial Policy Communication (2011), the Plan set out a renewed vision of entrepreneurship as well as several actions to be taken at both the EU and Member State levels to support entrepreneurship in Europe.⁴⁹ The EU strategy for promoting entrepreneurship in Europe was based on the following three pillars: (i) entrepreneurial education and training to support growth and business creation; (ii) the creation of the right business environment by removing administrative barriers and supporting entrepreneurs in crucial phases of their business; and (iii) boosting the culture of entrepreneurship in Europe and nurturing the new generation of entrepreneurs by promoting positive entrepreneur role models.

In 2013, the EC adopted a new Communication on Smart regulation for SMEs.⁵⁰ The EC reaffirmed the need to design EU policies “with SMEs in mind” and recommended new measures for building a positive business environment for SMEs. These measures should include exemptions or lighter regulatory regimes for microenterprises and SMEs plus supporting and consulting activities addressed to SMEs.⁵¹ In 2014, stressing the need for Europe to focus on post-crisis growth and modernisation, a new Communication from the EC – evocatively titled *For a European Industrial Renaissance*⁵² – stimulated concrete actions to facilitate the participation of SMEs in the internal/international market as well as their access to finance and pan-European technological infrastructures. These actions affected several policy areas. In regard to competitiveness, they aimed to help SMEs access international markets, integrate into global value chains, and ensure access to critical inputs at affordable prices. Regarding human resources, learning mobility initiatives were encouraged (such as the ‘Erasmus+ Programme’), plus any other activity for promoting job creation potential and facilitating the emergence of skills in the green economy. Referring to innovation, the EC emphasised the need to maximise the efficiency of EU regulations and policy initiatives, to develop adequate infrastructures (including cluster and support services for SMEs innovation), and to increase strategic investments⁵³ to help regions to modernise their industrial bases. Referring specifically to investments, the EC established increased funds available to States, regions, and industries to foster innovation.⁵⁴

⁴⁸ European Commission (2012), *2020 Action Plan. Reigniting the entrepreneurial spirit in Europe*, (COM) 2012 0795 final.

⁴⁹ The opening statement of the Plan leaves no room for doubts: “To bring Europe back to growth and higher levels of employment, Europe needs more entrepreneurs”. Entrepreneurship is considered “a powerful driver of economic growth and job creation” that “creates new companies and jobs, opens up new markets, and nurtures new skills and capabilities [...] makes economies more competitive and innovative and is crucial in achieving the objectives of several European sectorial policies”.

⁵⁰ European Commission (2013), *Smart regulation. Responding to the needs of small and medium - sized enterprises*, COM (2013) 122 final.

⁵¹ These consulting activities included: an annual SME scoreboard identifying the main issues and regulatory initiatives impacting on SMEs; regular annual meetings between SMEs associations and the Commission; consultations of SME employers’ organisations and the “TOP 10 Consultation”; identifying the main ten areas of EU and national legislations that were considered burdensome by the SMEs, etc.

⁵² European Commission (2014), *For a European Industrial Renaissance*, COM (2014) 14 final.

⁵³ The Communication identifies six strategic areas for innovation: advanced Key Enabling Technologies (KETs); clean vehicles and transport; bio-based products; construction and raw materials; and smart grids.

⁵⁴ Additional funds were provided by *COSME Programme* to support entrepreneurship, *ESIF Funds for Regions* to finance investments in industrial competitiveness, and the *Horizon 2020 Programme* for financing the commercialisation of research.

Furthermore, the 2015 EC Communication titled *Upgrading the Single Market*⁵⁵ aimed to simplify regulatory conditions to allow SMEs to grow in the single market and support companies with pan-European ambitions. In particular, addressing the key difficulties that SMEs and start-ups had to face in all phases of their lifecycle (e.g., VAT regulations, uncertainties over company law, understanding of and compliance with regulatory requirements, lack of access to finance, fear of punitive bankruptcy laws, and barriers to innovation), the EC announced a legislative proposal on business insolvency and further measures to remove administrative burdens to the starting and scaling-up of companies' activities; moreover, it announced the launch of a Start-up and Scale-up Initiative in 2016,⁵⁶ aimed at facilitating start-ups' access to finance and the single market, stimulating the growth of the skills base, and creating new opportunities for partnerships.

In 2017, a new Communication titled *Investing in a smart, innovative, and sustainable Industry*⁵⁷ focused on the economic, societal, environmental, and technological transformations engaging the EU industrial system. It also expressed the necessity of relaunching investments in advanced manufacturing, people's skills and talents, as well as intangible assets such as research and innovation. To ensure that the EU remains competitive in the global market, the EC urged a number of actions for making the EU industrial system stronger, fairer, more sustainable, and digitally upgraded. These actions included measures aimed at supporting industrial innovation on the ground (i.e., introducing the innovation principle in EU regulation, stimulating the uptake of digital technologies among SMEs, and encouraging innovation in less innovative sectors), stimulating more capital investments (i.e., initiatives on venture capital and social entrepreneurship funds), promoting the digital upgrade (i.e., through the Strategy on Digitising European Industry) and transition to sustainable production models (i.e., through the Innovation Fund and Modernisation Fund proposals, Clean energy package, and New circular economy package), encouraging education and training systems to equip citizens with the right set of skills (e.g., through the European Social Fund, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and A New Skills Agenda for Europe), promoting the international dimension and partnership with Member States, regions, cities, and the private sector (i.e., new trade agreements, a new anti-dumping calculation methodology, and an EU framework for screening foreign direct investments), and providing a positive environment for the scaling-up of dynamic SMEs.

In the EU, 2020 was a momentous year for SMEs. The COVID-19 crisis has had significant impacts on the world economy. Following the various lockdowns and other measures taken to limit the spread of the pandemic, many enterprises experienced drops in sales and the capacity to generate wealth and employment. The pandemic was also a turning point for policies. Before the global crisis, EU strategies for SMEs were mainly addressed to the issues of the digital and green transition; after COVID-19, policy measures turned into first aid and repair actions, aimed at relieving businesses and citizens from the damages caused by the pandemic.

⁵⁵ European Commission (2015), *Upgrading the Single Market: more opportunities for people and business*, COM (2015) 550 final.

⁵⁶ European Commission (2016), *Europe's next leaders. The Start-up and Scale-up Initiative*, COM (2016) 733 final.

⁵⁷ European Commission (2017), *Investing in a smart, innovative and sustainable Industry. A renewed EU Industrial Policy Strategy*, COM (2017) 479 final.

In March 2020, before the spread of COVID-19, the EC launched the SME Strategy for a sustainable and digital Europe.⁵⁸ The Communication recognised that “SMEs are very diverse in terms of business models, size, age, and entrepreneurs’ profiles” and “range from liberal professions and microenterprises in the services sector to middle-range industrial companies, from traditional crafts to high-tech start-ups”. To meet the needs of this large range of actors, the EC set a comprehensive approach based on horizontal measures for helping all kinds of SMEs as well as actions targeting specific needs. The EC’s strategy was based on three pillars (capacity-building and support for the transition to sustainability and digitalisation; reduction of regulatory burden and improvement of market access; and improvement of access to financing) as well as on several key actions linked to each pillar.⁵⁹ The major EU policy actions are summarized below (see Figure 2, next page).

1.1.5.4 Coronavirus, craft, and SMEs: The EU reaction

The ambitious package of measures set out in the 2020 Communication crashed into the unpredictable scenario of COVID-19, the global pandemic that has upset the world with serious consequences for human lives and economic activities. Throughout 2020 and 2021, the EC coordinated a European response to the outbreak. To limit the economic and social damages caused by the pandemic, the EC proposed on 26 May 2020 a Recovery plan for Europe. On 21 July 2020, EU leaders agreed on this recovery plan and on the temporary instrument designed to boost the recovery (Next Generation EU), a multiannual financial framework for 2021–2027.⁶⁰

The Recovery and Resilience Facility is the largest component of Next Generation EU. The RRF has provided grants amounting to € 338 billion as well as loans amounting to € 390 billion at current prices. EU Member States had to submit national recovery and resilience plans that describe the reforms and public investment projects they plan to implement with the support of the RRF. A 2021 publication titled Culture Action Europe demonstrated that CCIs receive special treatment in the national recovery plans. The publication analysed the types of investments and reforms (if any) contained in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans directly supporting Europe’s cultural ecosystem.⁶¹ It revealed that, until

⁵⁸ European Commission, *A SME Strategy for a sustainable and digital Europe*, COM (2020) 103 final.

⁵⁹ In regard to the first pillar, the EC has adopted high-impact measures to improve digital skills and innovation through SMEs, such as digital courses for SME employees to become proficient in areas (i.e., AI, cybersecurity, or blockchain), a Digital Volunteers Programme to allow young skilled people and experienced seniors to share their digital competences with traditional businesses, and the allocation of at least €300 million to encourage breakthrough Green Deal innovations under the EIC. Regarding the second pillar, the EC announced several actions aimed at enforcing the Single Market and removing administrative barriers that hinder SMEs’ potential (including the development of proposals for regulatory sandboxes by testing pilots), enhancing SMEs’ access to third countries’ markets, promoting cross-border cooperation among SMEs, facilitating research and innovation ecosystems, and supporting Member States in designing early warning mechanisms for companies in financial difficulties to prevent them from bankruptcy. In regard to the third pillar, the Commission planned to introduce new private-public financing schemes for SMEs, to support innovative SMEs that develop/adopt green tech solutions, to launch a blockchain-based initiative for enabling the issuance and trading of SME bonds across Europe, to simplify the existing state aid rules, and to launch a gender-smart financing initiative for stimulating funding for women-led companies and funds and empowering female entrepreneurship.

⁶⁰ Special meeting of the European Council (17, 18, 19, 20 and 21 July 2020) on the recovery plan and multiannual financial framework for 2021-2027 – Conclusions, EUCO 10/20CO EUR 8 CONCL 4.

⁶¹ https://cultureactioneurope.org/files/2021/11/NRRPs_analysed_digital.pdf

November 2021, at least 2% of the EU26 – approximately €12 billion – had been mobilised for culture from both the EU budget and national co-fundings. Comparing the national plans is challenging because they present data in highly diverse structures. For the reasons discussed within Section 1.1.5, comparisons are much more difficult when considering the craft industry.

Figure 2. Major EU policy actions in relation to the new industrial approach of the EU.

Focusing on the general area of SMEs, the EC adopted some instruments to reduce the impact of COVID-19 on their business. First, it ensured access to liquidity measures, mobilising financial support through the COSME programme. In particular, the Loan Guarantee Facility (LGF) was expanded with additional resources from the European Fund for Strategic Investments to enable banks to offer bridge financing for SMEs. These measures were made available through the European Investment Fund (EIF). In EU countries, national promotional and commercial banks put additional measures in place for adversely affected SMEs, focusing on mechanisms for facilitating financing (in particular working capital) and flexibility for repayments of existing loans. Moreover, the European Scale-up Action for Risk capital (ESCALAR) programme supported venture capital and growth financing to help promising companies to scale-up. The Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) helped SMEs through innovation partnerships on areas linked to COVID-19 (e.g., personal protective equipment and medical equipment) and provided advice on accessing dedicated European and national financial support. Furthermore, the EC responded to the COVID-19 crisis with a recovery strategy focused on European supply chains and ecosystems and the consumer and business climate to restore confidence, stimulate investments, and help the unemployed back to work.⁶²

The broad discussion on the craft policy framework closes Section 1.1 of the Part 1 of the report. The following Section 1.2 presents the production network configuration of the craft industry and discusses the main governance models operating within it.

⁶² See 'Coronavirus response in relation to mitigation of effects on SMEs', https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes_en, and 'Coronavirus response in relation to financing for businesses', https://ec.europa.eu/growth/access-to-finance_en.

1.2 Production network configurations

In the context of the CICERONE project, CCSs are observed through the lens of the GPN perspective, highlighting the chain of flows that cross all phases of the production network. As highlighted in the CICERONE report D1.1, the flows and dynamics of the selected industries are the primary objects of analysis and not the firm *per se*. Thus, these chains of flows are unpacked in different phases that compose the basic input–output structure of the industry. Following the typology of the stages used in *Mapping the Creative Value Chains: A Study on the Economy of Culture in the Digital Age* (European Commission, 2017) and by UNESCO (2009), these stages are creation, production, distribution, exchange, and archive. As discussed in the aforementioned CICERONE report, the analysis of the input–output structure enables one to distinguish a number of models of governance of CCSs, leading to the identification of a specific case study (the network of firms to explore empirically). This section presents the input–output structure and the prevailing governance models in the crafts industry. Said structure identifies the key economic activities necessary for the transformation of raw materials and other inputs into finished products. In the craft industry, it is possible to identify the following steps:

Creation

The craftsperson develops the product, starting from its ideation to its production; in the case of a very traditional craft activity, this phase is based on local traditions and history. It might also be that the craftsperson or craft enterprise receives the design or idea from a client (individuals or the creative units of larger firms; i.e., a brand) and reproduces it with his/her ability: in this case, artisanal knowledge and competences are at the service of the industry, which might require highly exclusive items or, by contrast, mass goods.

Production

This phase concerns the actual making of the product, where the idea of the object becomes real. This can be a rather standard process in case of a production based on a very traditional procedure. By contrast, the process can also be particularly complex, innovative, or unusual when the craftsperson or enterprise is involved directly in creating something brand new or when they adapt something following a customer's requests. In any case, in this phase the craftsperson uses all of their skills to create something unique, high-quality, and valuable as an artisanal product. Production is typically executed by the craftsperson him/herself or in the workshop under the craftsperson's supervision. Production can in some instances also be outsourced, but production occurs in close contact with the craftsperson and where s/he possesses the design, skill, and deep knowledge of the material used. When the craftsperson/enterprise works as a supplier of a larger enterprise, production can be conducted within the enterprise's production plant and can involve low-skilled labour (e.g., blue-collars, such as assemblers, fitters, and polishers).

Distribution

This phase concerns the processes of product marketing and distribution in different marketplaces. In the more traditional craft industry, this often implies selling products through fairs and markets organisations, galleries, shops, or auction houses. Other venues can be museums, art galleries, and other archives. The interaction between the craftsperson/enterprise and the final customer is of essential value when they sell their products directly in their workshop (i.e., if the workshop is also a shop). In addition, the craftsperson or enterprise must interact with fair and festival organisers and curators; for example, he/she/it might want to develop marketing strategies using the Internet (websites and social media) or use the services of a payment platform. For industrial and commercial craft, this phase implies the sale of products through a variety of exclusive brand-shops, shops, or mass retailers. The role of intermediaries can be crucial, such as selling agents or e-platform managers. As anticipated, the role of e-platforms has grown over time. When the artisan or craft enterprise works as a supplier for a larger enterprise, final or semifinished products are sold directly to it.

Exchange

In this phase, the artisan or craft enterprise engages with their audience and clients. This can be very direct, especially for the most artisanal model of production, where exchange often occurs in the crafts workshop or at fairs. A crucial form of contact between artisans and clients (individuals or larger firms) also occurs with the customisation of products, a highly common practice not only in the traditional craft industry. Exchange also occurs through advertising and the media (e.g., websites, social networks, and magazines).

Archive

Craft products can be displayed in museums and exposition centres. They can be part of the collections of educational institutions in archives, be part of the historical repertoire of local crafts associations, and be displayed in specialised magazines, books, or other publications. Private collections of craft products are increasingly important. Archives can serve an important function for craftspeople interested in traditional and heritage crafts, where older forms of manufacturing and design can be rediscovered.

The observed stages represent more of a cycle – they do not have a clear hierarchical order and sometimes overlap or become blurred. Based on the Cultural Industries Production System model presented by Pratt (2000), the stages can be represented as follows (see Figure 3 on the next page).

It is well known that the craft industry is dominated by small and medium-sized craft producer businesses (Hay, 2008), usually – but not exclusively – oriented towards the satisfaction of local needs and markets. As anticipated, the globalisation wave and the processes of market integration pose greater challenges in terms of products' adaptation to variegated consumer segments, organisation's changes, and firms' strategies for accessing national and transnational markets. Craft producers often face difficulties selling their products due to a lack of access to production and retail space; to equipment and raw materials; to information, marketing, and markets; to finance; and to

transportation. In general terms, artisans are numerous, and entry (as well as exit) barriers are usually low. With concern to organisational models, production networks and logistics are among the major challenges facing the industry. In a scientific panorama that has thus far largely neglected the issue, it is possible to identify the following organisational models in the craft industry:

Figure 3. Stylized model of production phases in the craft industry

The vertically integrated model

This model refers to craftspeople/craft enterprises who are an essential part of a larger firm’s organisational architecture, which spans a variety of national geographies. The planning and design of a product – involving the analysis of market tendencies, definition of the product, and definition of a collection – are followed by the production activities: the latter involve product prototyping and modelling and are usually performed by artisans or craft businesses, which translate ideas into actual models on the basis of which production is made. In the typology proposed by Micelli (2011), the artisan is a craftsperson. By considering and applying the cycle of cultural production, in the vertically integrated model the craftsperson/enterprise works in relation with the creative units of the company. Usually, the craftsperson/enterprise receives the project from the creative units of the company and makes it using their manual skills (from creation to production). Very often, modelling and prototyping activities are critical preproduction activities, where production and creation are bridged together. Vertically integrated companies and global players take special care of both the training and formation of new generations of artisans and of activities that involve an engagement with their direct audience/public through events such as fashion shows and exhibitions.

The production network model

This model refers to organisations of craftspeople who act as qualified/generic suppliers of medium-large companies involved in wider, extra-local production networks. In this case, the company crafts goods that are then produced and commercialised by the lead firm as well as other firms of its network – this model implies firms with upstream suppliers. If the lead firm is a niche producer (e.g., a fashion *maison* or a luxury yachting brand) creative, craft, and prototyping activities are often considered core activities more than production ones, with different implications in terms of value. If the lead firm is an industrial/mass producer, the reverse applies. In the typology proposed by Micelli (2011), these artisans are translators: they sell their ability to other firms. By considering and applying the cycle of cultural production, in this model the organisation providing artisanal services – especially to SMEs – works in tight relations with the creative units in charge of product ideation. Modelling and prototyping activities are critical preproduction activities. In these two cases, power relations depend on the reputation or recognition that the artisans or craft enterprises have from the lead firm. They can range from being extremely asymmetrical, as they respond to the demand of other industries, to being more symmetrical when artisans' skills are specific and rare on the market and when the complexity of the products requires them. In any case, these models involve the insertion of the craftsman/enterprise in specific extra-local production networks often led by global players. As anticipated, the valorisation of artisanal skills and competencies becomes a priority especially for brands. For instance, relating to fashion, the French holding multinational corporation Moët Hennessy Louis Vuitton (LVMH) with the training project *Métiers d'Art* aims to preserve the *savoir-faire* of craft masters. This is not an isolated case: many other companies operating in diverse industries, especially in the luxury segment (e.g., furniture making, ceramic and glass making, jewellery, and boat manufacturing) have started several projects to recover and safeguard traditional professions that are now crucial in production (Cavalli, 2013).

The commercial (retail) network model

Through this model, by considering and applying the cycle of cultural production, the craftsman conceives and develops the idea of the product and also produces it or is in close contact with and proximity to production. With production, the idea of the object becomes real. It might be a rather standard process in the case of very traditional crafting, or the process can, on the contrary, be particularly complex, innovative, or unusual, such as if the craftsman creates something brand new, or adapts something following the customer's needs. In this architecture, the marketing and distribution occur through intermediaries. This model emerges when the craftsman or the craft enterprise does not have the capacity to run a complex business or is not interested in doing so. In this case, the craft-based business must rely on intermediaries (either a platform or business professionals) who are able to commercialise the product. Here, it is the intermediary that enables the globalisation of the production network. Recent research focused on the platform system, especially online handmade goods retailers such as Etsy or DaWanda (Jakob, 2013). The development of such platforms enables many crafters to sell their goods to a global audience. Thus, although 'peer-to-peer' advertisements create an accumulative audience as well as a sense of community and

'ownership' as platforms aim to function as a 'middleman' in facilitating vendor—consumer exchange, they also pose challenges. According to Hracs et al. (Hracs, Jakob, & Hauge, 2013), they are confronted with the "dilemma of democratization". Not only do an increasing number of crafters share a relatively small and slowly growing consumer market, but it is also much harder to be found and to gain the attention of potential customers among thousands of other crafters (Levine & Heimerl, 2008; Taylor & Luckman, 2018; Jakob, 2013, p. 137). Therefore, the rising sales figures of e-commerce platforms do not necessarily mean that artisans are running successful and thriving businesses.

The market model

This model deals with a basic business model in which the artisan creates and produces his/her products, which are then disseminated and exchanged in the market. Artisans are responsible for their own showcasing, distribution, and marketing activities. In the typology proposed by Micelli (2011), these artisans are a Master of craft, meaning independent craftspeople who manage their whole production process. With reference to fashion, Mazzucotelli et al. (2012) suggested that this model represents pure craftpersonship: each product/object is unique, the outcome of a long tradition connecting ideation and production and far from any industrial practice. In the market model, by considering the cycle of cultural production and applying it, the craftsperson has and develops the idea of the product, the collection of products, or the project. In the case of a very traditional craft activity, this phase is based on local traditions and history. It might also be that the craftsperson receives the design or idea from a client and reproduces it with his/her abilities. With production, the idea of the object becomes real. It might be a rather standard process in the case of very traditional crafting, or particularly complex, innovative, or unusual if the craftsperson creates something brand new or adapts something following the customer's needs. The marketing and distribution occur directly through, for example, shops and sales exhibitions.

PART 2. Statistical mapping of the craft industry

2.1 Quantitative analysis of the craft industry

Conducting an effective statistical mapping of craft enterprises in the EU is not a simple task. As discussed in Part 1, the lack of a formal, shared, definition of a craft enterprise makes data collection problematic and risks obtaining inconsistent analyses. At the EU level, the most reliable data are offered by Eurostat, which, in the Structural Business Statistics dataset, presents a set of information on SMEs.⁶³ These enterprises undoubtedly represent “the backbone of the European economy, providing a potential source for jobs and economic growth”⁶⁴; however, it is difficult to prove whether they have an artisanal status. Where legally relevant, this status is established by criteria and conditions adopted with internal regulatory instruments of the Member States. Consequently, the only way to perform a precise mapping of craft enterprises in Europe would seem to be to conduct a study on each of the observed States, following national sources and criteria and, in conclusion, making appropriate comparisons. Such a task has never been carried out, except for a tentative, exploratory study by Istituto Tagliacarne in 2001, and exceeds the limits and scope of this report.

Consequently, in the next pages we work on the Eurostat dataset on SMEs but we will make some adjustments that can, by bringing statistics closer to reality, contribute to refining the informative potential of data. The results of these adjustments, unprecedented in the literature, are proposed here for the first time and are based on the practice of Confartigianato, the major Italian collective organisation representing craft enterprises. When comparing data on Italian craft enterprises with those of such enterprises in other EU Member States, Confartigianato used to rely on the Eurostat nonfinancial SME dataset, establishing a formal equivalence between craft enterprises and nonfinancial micro/small enterprises.⁶⁵ In short, Confartigianato omits medium-sized enterprises⁶⁶ from the statistical sample, focusing on Eurostat data that refer to the total business economy (including all enterprises that operate with NACE codes from B to N plus S95⁶⁷), except for agricultural, financial, and insurance activities (NACE codes A and K). Such an operation does not seem entirely satisfactory, the reason for which becomes clear through a concrete example. When referring to the national criteria that define a craft enterprise, Confartigianato reported that in Italy in 2019, there were 1 011 318 craft enterprises in Italy (Ufficio Studi Confartigianato, 2022); faced with the need to compare these data at the EU level, Confartigianato changed the unit of analysis, focusing on the aforementioned micro and small nonagricultural and nonfinancial business (NAFBs⁶⁸) described in the Eurostat dataset. This operation leads to a notable increase in the number of enterprises considered; in fact, the 1 million craft enterprises initially considered becomes 3,592,336 enterprises. The difference between the estimates is relevant, resulting in a significant alteration of data

⁶³ SMEs, with the number of persons employed ranging from 0 to 249.

⁶⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/structural-business-statistics/small-and-medium-sized-enterprises>

⁶⁵ Number of persons employed ranging from 0 to 49.

⁶⁶ With the number of persons employed ranging from 50 to 249.

⁶⁷ ‘Repair of computers, personal and household goods’

⁶⁸ When referring to nonfinancial businesses, Eurostat uses the acronym NFBs. Since agricultural businesses are also omitted from the analyses, we proposed modifying this acronym to NAFBs (nonagricultural or financial businesses).

representativeness. In fact, it is quite evident that this strategy does not support data for grasping the reality of craft enterprises. For these reasons, some additional adjustments seemed necessary to refine the Eurostat dataset and obtain a corpus of enterprises which, based on explicit criteria, were presumed to more accurately reflect the features and nature of a craft enterprise. These criteria, based on literature (see *Part 1*), are complemented by the reference to Italian legislation and the praxis of the Italian Chambers of Commerce, which provides a detailed list of activities that, based on NACE codes, can be considered undoubtedly artisanal.⁶⁹ The aforementioned corpus was populated according to the following criteria:

- the inclusion of micro, very small, and small enterprises (0–9, 10–19, and 20–49 persons employed) and the exclusion of medium-sized enterprises (50–249 persons employed);
- the inclusion of enterprises that produce/transform goods/products;
- the exclusion of enterprises that provide services, except for specific activities (e.g., cleaning activities);
- the exclusion of agricultural, financial, and wholesale activities;
- the exclusion of accommodation and food and beverage service activities;
- the exclusion of professional, scientific, and technical activities;
- the exclusion of administrative, educational, and artistic activities;
- the exclusion of activities of households as employers;
- the exclusion of activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies.

These operations required a deep, extra selection of NACE codes. The results of this selection are presented in the following Table no. 5 and compared with the NACE codes list initially considered by Confartigianato.

Table 5. NACE Codes for micro/small enterprises

Nace codes for micro/small enterprises	Confartigianato's praxis	Our proposal
A	Not considered	Not considered
B–F	Considered	Considered
G	Considered	Not considered, except for G45.2 and G 45.4
H	Considered	Not considered, except for H49, H52 and H53
I	Considered	Not considered
J	Considered	Not considered, except for J58.1, J62.0 and J63.1
K	Not considered	Not considered

⁶⁹ As a general reference, see: <https://www.tn.camcom.it/content/elenco-delle-attivita-albo-imprese-artigiane>.

L	Considered	Not considered
M	Considered	Not considered
N	Considered	Not considered, except for N81.2
O–R	Not considered	Not considered
S	Not considered, except S95	Not considered, except for S95
T–U	Not considered	Not considered

Evidently, by applying these rules, the Eurostat dataset is considerably reduced and seems more consistent with the numerical substance of the studied phenomenon. Again, proof of this consistency comes from referring to the Italian case. As stated earlier, in 2019 the number of Italian craft enterprises defined on the basis of the Italian legislation was 1 012 318; referring to Confartigianato’s praxis, this number reached the threshold of 3 592 336 units; by applying the additional filters, the number of presumed craft enterprises returns to 1 212 527, which is very close to the original precise estimate.

Table 6. Estimates of the number of Italian craft enterprises

No. of craft enterprises in 2019 according to Italian law	No. of presumed craft enterprises in 2019 according to Eurostat	No. of presumed craft enterprises in 2019 based on our proposals
1,012,318	3,592,336	1,212,527

The general assumption that guided our statistical mapping is that the smaller the enterprise and the more refined the NACE codes list, the more reliable the estimates relating to craft enterprises should be. From this point onwards, the term craft reflects the adjustments presented in table 5.

Over the next few pages, the results of this operation are presented. Specifically, Section 2.2.1 presents a Eurostat-based descriptive statistical analysis on the number of enterprises (Subsec. 2.2.1.1.), employed persons (Subsec. 2.2.1.2), and turnover (Subsec. 2.2.1.3) of the craft industry in Europe. Based on other complementary sources (i.e., national statistics institutes), Subsection 2.2.1.4 presents some data referring to single countries.

2.2.1 The craft industry in the European Union

2.2.1.1 Number of enterprises

In 2019, craft enterprises in the EU numbered approximately 8.6 million. These enterprises represent 37.2% of the total population of NAFB companies in the EU, whose overall number is 23.2 million. With 1.2 million units, Italy is the country with the highest number of craft enterprises in the EU, just before France and Poland, which have 1.1 million and 989,000 companies, respectively. Among the Nordic and Baltic EU countries, Sweden has the highest number of craft enterprises (247,028), followed by Finland (102,363) and Lithuania (94 763; see Graph 1).

Graph 1. Number of craft enterprises by State in 2019

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Italian craft enterprises represent 13.9% of the total number of EU craft enterprises, followed by France (13%), Poland (11.5%), and Germany (11%). Therefore, as Graph 2 (see next page) below indicates, almost half of the craft enterprises of the entire EU are concentrated in four Member States.

The Italian primacy is due, in particular, to the numbers of the manufacturing and construction industries: here, approximately 350,000 micro and small craft enterprises are concentrated, which represent the backbone of the States' productive artisanal fabric (see Graph 3, see next page).

Graph 2. Percentage of craft enterprises by State

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Graph 3. Number of craft enterprises in Manufacturing

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Within this scenario, micro craft enterprises (0–9 persons employed) have a crucial role. With 7,965,363 units, they represent 34.4% of the overall number of EU NAFBs, whereas small craft enterprises represent 2.8% of the overall number (see Graph 4). Considering the overall EU craft enterprises, micro craft enterprises represent 92.4% of the total.

Graph 4. Percentage of craft enterprises by size

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Moving to the State level of analysis, the relevance of micro craft enterprises is also demonstrated by the study of the ratio between micro craft enterprises and the overall NAFBs of the State. As displayed in *Graph 5*, in almost all EU Member States, these enterprises represent at least 25% of the NAFBs of the State. The highest percentages are found in Slovakia (48.5%), Poland (46.5%), and Ireland (43.4%), whereas the lowest are found in Portugal (23.6%) and Luxembourg (19.7%). Sweden stops at 35.6% and Italy at 30.2% (see *Graph 5*).

Graph 5. Percentage of micro craft enterprises

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Another way to describe the relevance of craft enterprises to the economic structure of the EU is to study the ratio between each nation’s craft enterprises and the overall number of EU NAFBs. This ratio is indicated with the expression crafts rate. As previously mentioned, referring to the EU level, the overall crafts rate is 37.2%, with a clear prevalence of micro craft enterprises (see Graph 4). Moving to the analysis of each State, the performance of Italy stands out, whose craft enterprises represent 5.2% of the total EU NAFBs, just before France (4.9%) and Poland (4.3%). Among the Nordic and Baltic states of the EU, Sweden is confirmed as the first country with a rate of 1.07%, while Estonia is at the bottom of the ranking with 0.15% (see Graph 6).

Graph 6. Craftpersonship rate by State in 2019

Source: Author’s elaboration of Eurostat data

Based on these ratios, the study of the standard deviation may clarify how much each State differs from the EU average crafts ratio. Referring to the general mean (= 1.38) and the standard deviation (= 1.60), it is possible to classify four groups of States segmented on the intensity of their crafts rate. As the graph below displays, Italy and France are States with an extremely high crafts rate (>2SD) whereas Poland, Germany, and Spain have a high crafts rate (2SD < x < 1SD); Czech Republic and the Netherlands have medium crafts rates, whereas the remaining States have low rates (see Graph 7 on the next page).

Graph 7. Standard deviation of craftpersonship rate by State

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

2.2.1.2 Employed persons

In 2019, the number of persons employed in NAFBs in the EU was 131.2 million. The share of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises was 27.4 million, which is 20.9% of the total. The State that employs the highest number of workers in craft enterprises is Germany, with 5.5 million persons, followed by Italy with 4.2 million and Spain with 2.9 million (see Graph 8).

Graph 8. Number of persons employed in the craft industry in the EU

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

This ranking is confirmed by examining the ratio between the number of persons employed in the craft enterprises of each Member State and the overall number of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises. As Graph 9 displays, approximately 20% of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises are employed in Germany; Italy and Spain follow with 15.5% and 10.4%, respectively; the sum of the percentages related to these three countries reaches almost 50% of the overall number of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises (45.9%). The share of workers employed in the craft enterprises of the Netherlands (3.46%), Sweden (2.25), and Austria (2.25%) appears to be marginal.

Graph 9. Percentage of persons employed in the craft industry in the EU

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

Moving to the analysis of the ratio between the number of persons employed in craft enterprises and the number of employees in the NAFBs of each State, the proportions change considerably. As Graph 10 below demonstrates, the State with the highest percentage of persons employed in craft enterprises is Estonia (29.6%), followed by Italy (27.9%) and Slovenia (27.1%; see Graph 10).

Graph 10. Percentage of persons employed in craft enterprises out of the number of persons employed in each NAFB State in 2019

Graph 11 below displays the percentage composition of the number of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises by size of enterprise. As seems clear, more than half of the overall number of persons employed are employed in micro craft enterprises (see Graph 11).

Graph 11. Percentage of persons employed in EU craft enterprises by size of the enterprise in 2019

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

These data can be studied in a deep and integrated manner through an analysis of the ratio between the number of persons employed in micro craft enterprises (0–9 persons employed) in each State and the overall number of persons employed in the EU craft enterprises (0–49 persons employed). Based on these data, it seems clear that the top five EU Member States with the highest percentage (Italy, Germany, Poland, Spain, and France) have two-thirds of the total number of employed persons in craft enterprises (see Graph 11).

Graph 12. Percentage of persons employed in micro craft enterprises out of the overall number of persons employed in EU craft enterprises in 2019

Source: Author's elaboration of Eurostat data

The ranking does not change when moving to the analysis of the ratio between the number of persons employed in micro craft enterprises and the overall number of persons employed in EU NAFBs (see Graph 12).

Graph 13. Percentage of persons employed in micro craft enterprises out of the overall number of persons employed in EU NAFBs in 2019 (overall percentage = 11.2%)

2.2.1.3 Turnover

As Eurostat clarifies, the analysis of turnover indicates “the total of all sales (excluding VAT) of goods and services carried out by the enterprises of a given sector during the reference period”. According to Eurostat estimates, the global turnover of EU NAFBs in 2019 amounted to €26.5 billion. The turnover generated by EU craft enterprises is approximately 3 086 billion, which represents 11.65% of the EU's overall data. The EU Member State that contributed most to the turnover of craft enterprises is Germany (19%) followed by Italy (18%) and France (12.6%). The sum of the turnover in these three States represents almost half of the global turnover of EU craft enterprises; this proportion grows to 70.3% if one includes Spain, Poland, and the Netherlands (see Graph 13). In 2019, the craft enterprises of these six countries achieved a turnover of €218,285 billion.

Graph 14. Percentage of turnover of EU craft enterprises

2.2.1.4 Complementary sources

As anticipated, other statistical sources can be used (when available) to integrate the statistical mapping presented in the previous subsections. These data, mainly based on national sources, can provide a general idea of the economic relevance of craft enterprises, but they do not lie on a shared understanding of what a craft enterprise is. For this reason (as was deeply discussed in *Part 1* – see Sec. 1.1.5 – and *Part 2* – see Introduction), these data are not comparable with each other, nor are they comparable with those presented in the statistical mapping. Thus, a single and coherent “map” of the craft enterprises in Europe is impossible to draw.

In 2019 in Italy, there were 1 011 318 craft enterprises, representing 23.1% of the overall number of active enterprises; moreover, the number of employed persons was 2 613 608 (source: Confartigianato, 2021). As for France, craft enterprises number approximately 1 700 000 – with 38 000 in the artistic industry and 3.1 million persons employed (source: Chambre de Métiers et de l’Artisanat, 2021).⁷⁰ In 2019 in Germany, the 560 296 detected craft enterprises employed more than 5 million persons (source: Destatis, 2021⁷¹). In Spain, the craft industry comprised 38 000 enterprises employing 125 000 persons (source: EOI-Fundesarte⁷²). By 2020 in Portugal, according to national definitions, there were 6 371 artisanal profiles (3 016 individuals and 3 359 enterprises; source: Direção-Geral de Agricultura e Desenvolvimento Rural).⁷³ In the UK, where there is no legal definition of a craft enterprise, the estimated total number of craft jobs in the CCIIs in 2018 was 10 000, plus 88 000 estimated craft jobs outside of those industries (source: Creative Industries Council of the UK).⁷⁴ In Luxembourg, crafts represent 21% of all companies (i.e., 7 800 firms). Further investigations could be conducted to implement this provisional mapping.

⁷⁰ www.artisanat.fr/lartisanat/un-secteur-cle-de-leconomie/lartisanat-premiere-entreprise-de-france

⁷¹ www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Economic-Sectors-Enterprises/Crafts/Tables/crafts-enterprises.html#fussnote-1-59044

⁷² www.diasdelaartesanania.es/artesania-en-espana

⁷³ www.dgadr.gov.pt/images/docs/div_meiorural/Estatistica_Artesanato_2020.pdf

⁷⁴ <https://www.thecreativeindustries.co.uk/facts-figures/industries-craft-facts-figures>

2.2 Open issues

As clarified in *Part 1* and in the introduction to *Part 2*, the main open issue to report is the lack of a shared definition of a craft enterprise. This issue influences the whole process of data collection. In fact, official estimates on EU craft enterprises are missing. The data presented in Section 2.2.1 derive from a corpus built ad hoc, starting from the Eurostat general dataset on SMEs. Although literature-oriented, explicit, and capable of giving general coherence to the data, the criteria that guided the building of the corpus were experimental and open to revisions. Nonetheless, they were the result of a process of reflexivity that seemed necessary to reduce complexity and provide some reliable information on the selected industry.

In addition, it should be noted that the data provided by Eurostat are not systematic. The dataset presents some breaks in series and missing data. Moreover, data for the UK for 2019 are not provided. Referring to specific Member States, the provided EU and national totals diverge from the totals calculated as a sum of all single records. To provide homogeneity to the data, the calculated totals were preferred. Finally, to maintain consistency among the units of analysis, it was necessary to prefer the variable of number of persons employed instead of the variable of employees.

The selected corpus does not include information about the share of craftspeople that perform their job as self-employed. Data on self-employment are provided by a different Eurostat dataset (*Employment and unemployment – Labour Force Survey*), which does not segment information by NACE codes.

After critically discussing the statistical profile of the craft industry in the EU, *Part 3* of the report discusses the case studies selected by the Italian and Swedish research units.

PART 3. The fieldwork: Analyses and results

3.1 Case studies in the craft industry: setting the scene

The following pages focus on three different *forms* that crafts can assume within broader production networks. On the basis of the different governance models examined in *Part 1* (see Sec. 1.2), three artisanal projects – one in Italy and two in Sweden – were identified and selected to describe and explain variations in territorial, governance, and value dynamics within the production networks. Before going into the cases, it seems useful to outline the contours of the craft industry of the countries where case studies are localised.

As is known, the Italian productive fabric is characterised by a significant presence of craftpersonship. According to estimates by Confartigianato, at the end of 2021, there were 1 010 318 active artisan enterprises in Italy, equal to 23.1% of the overall number of national firms. It is estimated that these companies employ 2 613 608 persons, equal to 15.0% of all employees (the share rises to 24% if one considers the overall number of employees in micro and small enterprises). Going beyond the national formal definitions of a craft enterprise – based on the legal form, size, and economic sector of activity – Confartigianato argues that an *artisan value* can be tracked in a much wider range of enterprises: 4 348 912 micro and small enterprises are active in Italy's various economic sectors, which employ 11 080 250 employees (63.5% of the total number of employees in the country; Confartigianato, 2022). These numbers confirm that Italy is a European leader in terms of the number of micro and small enterprises. In fact, according to Eurostat, Italian SMEs employed 62.8% of the overall national economy's employees in 2019 – almost 15% more than the EU average (18.5%) and higher than the share of Spain (55.6%), Germany (40.8%), and France (38.4%). Italy is also the first European country in terms of the number of employees in manufacturing SMEs, with 1 902 190 employees (21.1% of the corresponding overall number related to the EU, and 17.5% more than Germany's; Poland stops at 883,879 employees, Spain at 824,835, and France at 735,708).

A profound artisan value is concentrated in Italian SMEs, which transcends the formal definitions of a craft enterprise. In fact, in line with Micelli's suggestion, a marked artisanal imprinting characterises most of the high-quality manufacturing productions of the country, even in sectors which appear far from the *traditional* concept of craftpersonship (Micelli, 2016). Among these sectors, the yachting industry certainly stands out, in which Italy is among the leaders at the European and global levels. The selected case study is grafted directly inside the yachting industry – whose economic, social, and cultural contours are described in Section 3.1.1 in the description of the case.

Finding data on the active number of artisans in Sweden, with the breadth of the sector, is more complex for a few reasons. First, the number of active craftspeople tends to be misleading in official statistics, as these are often based on the main source of income of individuals, of which craftspeople

tend to have several; moreover, for independent artisans (i.e., the majority of Swedish artisans), this income tends to come from other sources, often teaching. The second problem, as discussed above, is that craft activities occur in industry codes that are typically not considered crafts. For example, smithing is predominantly an industrial profession in Sweden, such as welding at construction sites, but it could also include small-scale traditional smiths. Much of the data are collected through salary admissions and through surveys of firms, who assign the code themselves. There is an underestimation among one-person enterprises, as the codes selected might not accurately convey what the person does. This becomes imperative to note as craftspeople in Sweden are a relatively small set of professionals, and the self-reporting of codes brings uncertainty to the actual number. According to Statistics Sweden's database over professions (SSYK), one code covers craftspeople and artistic crafts – 7319 – which covers a breadth of different crafts, from glass blowers to ceramicists. According to the database, in 2019 there were 695 active craftspeople in Sweden – 451 men and 244 women. These statistics can be compared with the latest report on the number of active artistic craftspeople in Sweden, which is from 2014, when the Swedish Arts Grant Committee (Konstnärsnämnden) collected data from a set of interest organisations and their members. The report stated that in 2014, there were 2284 active artistic craftspeople and form designers in Sweden – 1845 women and 439 men. According to the official Sweden Statistics database (2022), there has not been a significant drop in the number of active craftspeople as 607 were active in 2014; therefore, there appears to be an underreporting of official statistics for this industry, as the number under the larger code 7319 is smaller than the estimated number of active artistic craftspeople – a subset of active craftspeople. This is to be expected as the industry contains a range of different types of employment, and independent craftspeople often have their main income from other sources of employment. Extending the statistical search to include professions excluded from the 7913 code but that are typically counted towards the understanding of craft (e.g., gold and silver smiths and furniture carpenters), the number of active craftspeople in Sweden is 5837, which is a large jump from the 695 active artisans (Statistics Sweden 2022; SCB 2022).

Examining only artistic crafts, which the second and third case studies can both be defined as, there are also other data to investigate apart from the 2248 reported by the Swedish Grants Committee (which also includes form designers). The Konsthantverkarcentrum, a national membership organisation working on behalf of the government to promote Swedish artistic crafts, has approximately 700 active members. Not all artistic craftspeople are inclined to join such organisations, but it does offer a rough estimate. They accept members widely but require the artisan to have a higher education degree in artistic craftpersonship or to be admitted through a jury that examines the professional accomplishments of the applicant. This excludes those artistic craftspeople who work as hobbyists or in a more generic form of artistic craft activity – a part of the artistic craft industry that is not unsubstantial, but nonetheless excluded from such statistics.

For the third case study on artistic crafts, we investigated Swedish glass production. This industry takes its form in craftpersonship (e.g., blown and cast glass) and industrial machine production (e.g., glass fibre and glass panes). Regarding Swedish glass production on a national scale, excluding glass

machine production, fibre production, and glass pane production, there were 245 enterprises in 2018, a figure that had decreased to 229 by 2021 (source: Statistics Sweden 2022; SCB 2022). The number of employees working with glass craftsmanship is more difficult to determine as the data collected in the Swedish professions database (SSYK by Statistics Sweden, SCB 2022) stops at code 731, which is a combination code that covers a variety of hand-based manufacturing and artistic craftsmanship, giving the number of workers as in the broader category – 695 active craftspeople – which as discussed is not an accurate understanding. The media reported that there are slightly more than 200 active glass workers in the studied region of Småland, where most Swedish crafted glass is made (Eriksson SvD, 2019). The number of glass artisans is higher but, being the largest cluster of glass production, we can speculate that the number of active glass artisans does not exceed the hundreds, perhaps a few thousand, but it is a relatively small set of professionals. Of the estimated 20 893 workers producing “artistic, literary, and artistic works” in Sweden (code 90.010 in the enterprise database FDB of statistics Sweden, 2017), artistic artisans can be observed to comprise a relatively small part of this industry, and the craft industry in general is small in official statistics. How these data are collected and whether craftspeople are reported under other codes and alternative streams of income make these data unreliable, and it is nearly impossible to obtain an accurate understanding of the scale of the industry. For highly skilled artistic crafts, we can say with greater certainty that the number of workers is not more than a few thousand – for more generic forms of craftsmanship the number might be much higher. Some craft enterprises and workers also get lost under manufacturing codes, and what is decided to constitute craft changes this.

The remainder of *Part 3* is organised as follows. Section 3.1.1 presents a brief description of the selected projects, positioning the cases in the broader national economic and cultural context. Section 3.1.2 deals with the methodology: a full methodological justification is provided for each case, followed by an explanation of the reasons for their selection and a description of the theoretical and practical issues that characterised the fieldwork. Then, Section 3.2 is divided into three parts – one for each case study. Here, the projects under investigation are presented and discussed in depth, giving relevance to the CICERONE research questions. Case study 1 is about PRISMA, an Italian luxury yacht brand located in Liguria and Tuscany. Here, crafts are observed within a broader production network, demonstrating the ways in which it can contribute to luxury production, and to some extent semi-industrial. This project reflects the production network model. Case study 2 is about Konstantverkarna, a membership-based organisation that gathers approximately 90 different artisans using different materials and from different parts of Sweden. The case was selected as it is an organisation of 90 independent artisans who follow the market governance model identified earlier in this report. By investigating the reasons for why and how the artisans became involved in this organisation, we were able to unpack several artisans’ production networks as well as those of the organisations. Case study 3, the third and final case, focuses on a vertically integrated governance model, where one larger firm produces the design, crafts the product, and disseminates in within the same larger company. The selected company is a glass manufacturer that produces crafts in traditional forms of production, by hand-producing blown glass, cast glass, as well as glass painting and etching. It is located in a region dominated, both now and historically, by a glass manufacturing cluster.

3.1.1 Brief descriptions of the cases

Case 1: luxury yacht production network 'PRISMA'

The project under investigation is a 24-metre luxury yacht called 'Imagine', built in Italy in 2021 by the brand PRISMA (a pseudonym) and distributed to a French shipowner. PRISMA was born in the 1970s as a supplier of nautical services in Italy and the French Riviera. Then, it evolved as a dealer and boatbuilder on behalf of other well-known Italian brands; in the 1990s, the company began to build boats with its own brand. PRISMA is a family-run company involving three different generations: the founder, his children, and his grandchildren. The company is located in Italy, straddling two coastal cities in two distinct regions (*see the map in Figure 4 below*). The registered office is located in Liguria, in the province of Imperia. Here, the brand also has its own shipyards dedicated to the refitting and repair of leisure boats. The production of 'Imagine' (and that of the other luxury yachts released by the brand) occurs in Tuscany, in the nautical district of Viareggio (Province of Lucca), where the whole production process is outsourced to a well-established network of suppliers. Since the brand conducts niche artisanal production – approximately 80 yachts have been built in the last 40 years, all of which are entirely (or almost) tailor-made – the creation of every single yacht requires the involvement of skilled and highly qualified artisans and craft companies. Thus, although the brand retains a central role in the network, craftspeople seem to hold a critical position.

The configuration of the production network reveals that other actors are relevant, such as those involved in the phase of creation (i.e., designer, architects, engineers). Secondary, but not irrelevant, are the actors/activities involved in the other phases of the production chain, such as brokers, the media, and the international boat show circuit.

Map 1. The brand's locations (case 1)

The project under investigation is part of one of the most successful industries of the Italian economy. As reported by Confindustria Nautica (2022), at the end of 2021, the global turnover of the Italian leisure boat industry could have reached a record peak of €6 billion, returning to the levels reached in 2007–2008, before the spread of the financial and economic crisis that upset the world economy. Therefore, according to the last available estimates, the impact of COVID-19 on the global turnover of the sector (–2.6%) would have been completely offset, closing a decade of substantially uninterrupted growth (see Graph 14).

Graph 15. Global turnover of the Italian leisure boat industry

Source: visualisation based on Confindustria Nautica elaborations (2022)

Italy is also a leader in the global leisure boat market. In fact, as reported by Confindustria Nautica, Italy ranked second in 2019 in the world ranking of exporting countries – with exports amounting to US\$2.6 billion – behind the Netherlands (\$3.4 billion). These countries are followed by the UK (\$1.8 billion), France (\$1.2 billion), and Germany (\$1 billion). Graph 2 presents the percentage share of world boatbuilding exporting countries.

Graph 16. Global exporting countries of pleasure boats in 2019

Graph 15 | Visualisation based on Confindustria Nautica elaborations (2019)

Shifting back to the national level of analysis, it is not easy to determine to the extent to which craft enterprises have contributed to the global turnover of the Italian leisure boat industry. These companies do not have dedicated NACE codes for the nautical industry and also serve the civil construction industry. Nevertheless, according to CNA (one of the Italian organisations that represents national craft enterprises), it would be possible to assume that, in 2017, the micro and small craft enterprises of the nautical industry operating in construction, repair, and supply activities generated a global turnover of €1.4 billion, which represents 35% of the overall national leisure boat industry global turnover (CNA, 2019).

Based on secondary data, CNA also provides a set of key information about the spatial distribution and productive specialisation of the micro and small craft enterprises in Italy. As the map in *Figure 5* displays, the major share of micro and small craft enterprises in the industry appear to be highly concentrated in a few areas of the country: 32% of the entire industry is located in Tuscany (17.3%) and Liguria (14.7%). Relevant concentrations are also reported in Campania (8.8%), Sicily (8.7%), and in Veneto (7.7%; see *Figure 5*). Given the high concentration of enterprises, Tuscany and Liguria also occupy the first ranks in terms of employment (34.3% of the total nautical workforce resides in these two regions). As for turnover, Tuscany enterprises generate 25% of the overall turnover of the national leisure boat industry.

Map 2. Territorial share of craft enterprises in the leisure boat industry (source: CNA, 2019)

The observed regional productive specialisations are the result of a deep-rooted boatbuilding tradition that dates back to the High and Late Middle Ages (AD 1000–1500) and even earlier. As documented by Gatti (2004), technical boatbuilding know-how had already developed in Genoa and Liguria before the age of the Crusades. As for Tuscany and Viareggio, the maritime tradition dates back to the 15th

century, when the Tyrrhenian Sea became a strategic seaport. Here, supported by a long-standing tradition of seamen and fishers, the boatbuilding tradition took off in the 19th century, shaping little by little the nautical district as we know it today. The specialisation of the district evolved from the production of commercial small ships to 30- or 40-metre schooners, known as “barcobestia”,⁷⁵ to luxury yachts and superyachts. According to Bellandi, Santini, Vecciolini, and De Propriis – who reported IRPET data –the Viareggio yachting industry in 2011 absorbed approximately 25% of the manufacturing employment in the Viareggio area (defined through ISTAT Local Labour Market Areas, see ISTAT 2011 Census data).

IRPET also provides the most recent data on the regional and local distribution of craft enterprises. Building on data provided by the national Business Register, IRPET clarifies that, at the end of 2021, craft enterprises in Tuscany numbered 99,014 out of a total of 350,228 enterprises (approximately 28.3% of the overall number). Focusing on Viareggio, craft enterprises numbered 3,364 (0.96% and 3.4% of the regional population of enterprises and craft enterprises, respectively). When limiting the analysis to the NACE code 30.1 (“Building ships and boats”), the number of craft-based enterprises in Tuscany is 204 out of a total of 546 enterprises (37.4%); focusing on Viareggio, the number of craft enterprises is 77 out of a total of 222 craft and noncraft active enterprises (34.7%).

Case 2: The artistic craftsmanship organisation ‘Konsthantverkarna’

For the second case study, we departed from a governance model where craftspeople are responsible and influence the entirety of the production chain from creation to distribution. We chose to study a membership organisation, the oldest in Sweden, which gathers a wide set of independent artistic craftspeople who use a variety of different materials. The artistic crafts scene features a vast variety of different materials, artistic pursuits, and skill levels, ranging from amateur hobbyists to highly educated and skilled professional craftspeople. What constitutes artistic craftsmanship is fluid and often depends on the definition at hand. Some artistic craftspeople work within the applied arts, creating useable objects with high aesthetic value, whereas others work more towards the fine arts, disseminating their goods towards galleries, blurring the boundaries between artistic crafts and fine arts. Most craftspeople work independently, selling their works through their own firm. They can, however, also be found within larger businesses – such as ceramic mills, haute couture fashion houses, or glass factories, but this is an industry that predominantly consists of small businesses. These businesses – often one-person operations – have their own unique production networks that are built up by the individual craftsperson under various conditions. The selected second case study in the craft industry is focused on independent craftspeople. To obtain insights into how these networks are built up, and to capture the diversity that exists in the myriad of independent craftspeople, the membership-based organisation of Konsthantverkarna was selected as a case study.

⁷⁵ The name derives from the English term “*the best barque*”. Shipwrights from Viareggio and Liguria transliterated the expression, baptizing their boat as ‘*barcabest*’ (which then transformed into ‘*barcobestia*’; see the online Nautical Encyclopaedia: <https://nautipedia.it/index.php/BARCOBESTIA>)

Konsthantverkarna is a membership-based organisation founded in 1951. It was created with the goal of providing a dedicated space for artistic craftspeople to present and sell their work. It was, at the time, located close to the art school Konstfack in the very centre of Stockholm, Sweden. Since then, it has had some of the most well-known Swedish craftspeople as members, and those that apply for membership are examined by a jury, consisting both of members and invited experts in their fields. Today, the organisation has approximately 90 members, representing a variety of materials from concrete to ceramics, textiles, wood, jewellery, and paper to name but a few. These members are spread over a large area of Sweden, with half living in the two largest cities and half in small-to-medium-sized cities and rural areas. They are generally well educated, with most having attended either Valands or Konstfack, the two most prestigious fine arts colleges in Sweden, or having attended courses at other key colleges. The main activities of Konsthantverkarna are the running of a shop and gallery space, where members can sell their goods as well as exhibit their work in a gallery space joined to the store. Members pay approximately €1000 a year in membership fees, as well as a 30–40% commission on work sold. By selecting Konsthantverkarna, the project was able to investigate a common form of organisation (most larger cities in Sweden have some form of membership organisation for artistic crafts) as well as to obtain insight into how a variety of independent craftspeople organise their production networks.

Case 3: 'Swedish glass making'

The third case study was chosen as an example of a network where there is a clear lead firm that is vertically integrated and where production occurs in-house. To exemplify this, we chose to study a traditional glass manufacturing site, where the production consists of craftspeople who use the methods of glass blowing and casting. This is Swedish glass making, which has for periods over its long history been of world renown, for both its artistic quality and its craftsmanship. This glass industry is particularly associated with the area of Småland in southern Sweden, a dense cluster of hand-blown glass manufacturers that has existed since the late 19th century. This self-proclaimed "Glasriket", which translates to the "Kingdom of Crystal", had in its heyday approximately 87 different manufacturing sites, with the oldest originating from 1742. The majority of these glass manufacturers opened in the period between 1884, when the right to establish business was made into law, and the turn of the 20th century. The first crisis faced by this industry occurred shortly after, with a high influx of cheap imported glass, and it then faced several crises and upswings throughout the 20th century. Over a period of 140 years, this industry has survived, with manufacturing techniques that remain in most aspects the same, and it has also preserved the traditional craftsmanship. Today, it exists as one of the major centres of Swedish artistic craftsmanship, producing the majority of Swedish artistic glass products. In this cluster of artistic craftsmanship, one family-owned factory was studied, which employed 19 people, with 44 having been employed before the pandemic. This case study was chosen as it represents the vertically integrated governance model, where the majority of design, creation, and dissemination activities occur in-house.

3.1.2 Case study methodology

Case 1: A luxury yacht production network 'PRISMA'

The leisure boat production network seems to be an optimal research context in which to study the evolving visions of crafts. As clarified in the general overview of the industry, contemporary artisans should not only mean “old masters” who work alone in their workshops. This vision belongs mainly to the past and only describes a part of the reality. In fact, contemporary craftspeople can work in MSMEs as business owners or employees; they can work with traditional materials or with the most advanced technologies, shaping a changing social imagery around the figure of the artisan. These different visions of craftsmanship coexist in the yachting industry and, in particular, in the project under investigation.

The yachting system can be described as a platform that brings together multiple *filières*, specialised in the realisation of the different components and structures of the craft. Within these *filières*, a multiplicity of actors cooperates, most of whom are craftspeople (carpenters, upholsterers, marble producers and cutters, plumbers, producers or assemblers of technological appliances, window fitters, and electricians, among others). Thus, the high artisanal intensity that characterises the final product is one of the reasons that guided the selection of this case. A second reason is the consistency of the investigated project with the production network governance model. As discussed in Part 1, this model is based on the close collaboration of the brand (usually the lead actor) with a web of artisanal suppliers, who sell their ability and products to it. These artisans are assumed to be the main contributors to the value creation of the final product, but not necessarily those who are able to capture the majority of this value. Based on these premises, the study of the selected production network is the occasion for unveiling the power dynamics that characterise the artisanal work in a larger *filière* (to some extent semi-industrial).

To verify these assumptions, the case study was approached with a mixed methodology, combining quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data were derived from the already discussed Eurostat dataset (see Part 2) and integrated with national-based data provided by collective organisations of craft enterprises and other stakeholders. As for the qualitative data collection, semistructured interviews and an ethnography were conducted. A total of 28 interviews were conducted from 16th September 2020 to 25th April 2022. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and physical distance, 15 of them were conducted through web-conferencing applications. Eleven interviews were conducted in Viareggio and one in Turin. The collected interviews lasted between 45 minutes to 2 hours. Three informants were involved in the creation phase of the network, 13 in the production phase, one in the distribution phase, and one in the exchange phase; nine informants were stakeholders representing collective actors (union or craft enterprise representatives) or political organisms. Two brief ethnographies were also conducted in Genoa during the Boat Show (16th–21st September 2021) and Viareggio, in the shipyard, before the launch and the final delivery of the

investigated yacht (22nd–25th November 2021). All the interviews were transcribed and coded using a CICERONE-developed code booklet (see Annexes).

Case 2: ‘Konsthantverkarna’: The artistic craft-type organisation

To capture the production of independent craftspeople, the membership organisation Konsthantverkarna was chosen as a case study. Konsthantverkarna, which has over 90 members, was considered to be an ideal case study as it would allow us to not only unpack a singular craftspeople network but also to access a multitude of small networks, while also uncovering the organisation strategies in a membership organisation. The membership organisation functioned as a type of platform, with a shop and a gallery space, as well as a meeting point for the networks between craftspeople.

The case study was mainly based on qualitative semistructured interviews, which lasted for approximately 1–2 hours. In total, 17 actors in the network were interviewed, covering both members as well as supporting institutions, such as museum representatives, NGOs, and public institution representatives. The interviews were conducted from the 13th October 2020 to 25th March 2022. The majority of the interviews were conducted face-to-face, often situated in the workshops of the craftspeople being interviewed, where crafted objects in the workshop often led to discussions on the specific production network of that product/project. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the geographical spread of the members throughout Sweden, videoconferencing calls and telephone interviews were used for slightly less than half of the interviews. The interviews were transcribed, with the exception of one, and coded using a CICERONE-developed code booklet.

Case 3: ‘Swedish glass making’

The Swedish glass manufacturer, a factory using traditional methods of blowing and casting glass, represents a smaller case study in this report, where the firm takes the main responsibility for the project from creation to distribution. The project unpacked in this case is the production of glassware, which is designed either by external designers or in-house – mainly the designs of the owner. The factory is a family-run company in the process of a generational shift, which offered an extra dimension into how production networks are reconfigured through the generations.

A mixed-methods approach was used, where qualitative, semi structured interviews formed the basis of the data, but material from the local municipalities and reports by the county administrative board (Länsstyrelse) also informed the understanding of the case.

A total of 7 actors were interviewed, most through video conferencing tools, during October 28th 2021 and April 11th 2022. Interviews lasted between 45 and 70 minutes, and all were transcribed

afterwards. The interviews were all coded using a CICERONE-developed code booklet. The main actors within the company were interviewed, as were external designers, the local tourism board, and representatives of a local glass school. One of the interviewees was also an active participant in a nationwide labour union for designers and artists, which provided extra insight into the industry of artistic crafts and design.

3.2 Case 1: Prisma

Case study 1 is about PRISMA, an Italian luxury yacht brand located in Liguria and Tuscany. Here, craft is observed within a broader production network, revealing the ways in which it can contribute to a luxury production, to some extent semi-industrial. This project reflects the production network model.

3.2.1 Phases, actors, and locations

As described in the previous section, the project under investigation was a 24-metre luxury yacht called 'Imagine', built in Italy in 2021 by the brand PRISMA (invented name) and distributed to a French shipowner. The brand is located in Italy, straddling two coastal cities located in two distinct regions: the registered office is in Liguria, in the province of Imperia, whereas the production of 'Imagine' occurred in Tuscany, in the nautical district of Viareggio (province of Lucca), where the whole production process was outsourced to a well-established network of local or regional suppliers. The brand is a family-run business which realises a niche artisanal production (80 yachts built in the last 40 years), which have been entirely (or almost) custom-made.

Even if the brand does not participate directly in the concrete production of the boat, it plays a central role in the network. In fact, it manages relations with customers (shipowners) without intermediaries (i.e., it has no dealers); it coordinates and controls the whole production process (to some extent in co-habitation with the boatbuilder shipyard); and it activates the exchange levers that contribute to the creation of the value of the product (e.g., participation in boat shows and communication activities).

The network is crossed by a tension between the local and global scales: the brand has a global reach, but the phases of creation and production are concentrated in subnational areas. Distribution and the exchange phase are global. Based on these premises, the phases and actors involved in the production network are described as follows.

3.2.1.1 Phases and actors

Creation

The actors and activities involved in the phase of creation are the shipowner, the brand, the yacht designer, the engineering team, the architect (or interior designer), the media system, and the boat shows. This phase includes the drawing and technical design of the external lines and internal spaces of the yacht. Typically, these activities are conducted by yacht designers, architects, and engineers who work for the brand or in close collaboration with it; sometimes, the brand or shipowner decides

to entrust the exterior or interior project to well-known designers or *archistars*, whose contribution adds prestige (and value) to the final product.

The relationship between design and technical planning is a compromise between the aesthetic and functional aspects of the yacht. As one yacht designer highlighted, *“we often design things that are impossible to make”*. For this reason, the engineer has the task of *“making the drawing real, functional and constructible, following the guidelines of creativity as much as possible”* (interview no. 6). The engineering activity is therefore complementary to that of drawing: the aim is to find solutions that satisfy the stylistic, aesthetic, functional, and structural needs. The creative part *“remains essential to hit the target market”* (interview no. 6). This seems particularly interesting. The CEO of the brand explained as follows:

When we project a new yacht, we do not always know the final customer. Therefore, we need to think of a model that has an international appeal, that is polyvalent and that is suitable for different markets, that can work in Europe, America or China. The challenge is to think of a product that meets more needs or that can be modified on the go to be adapted to the needs of different countries. (interview no. 4)

The starting point for the creation of a yacht is *“a very practical market research”* (interview no. 6) that begins from the analysis of the market niche in which the brand wants to position. The brand and/or the yacht designer has in mind the kind of yacht that it/he/she wants to build and *“tries to understand what is currently on the world market, looking at what the major boat builders produce”*. This task is completed by *“the style and taste of the yard [...]”* and *“the creative flair of the designer [in which] there is a very personal taste”* (interview no. 6). Market research typically takes place through magazines, the Internet, boat shows, and fairs. As one informant clarified, *“fairs are absolutely necessary”* (interview no. 3). In particular, B2C fairs allow boat builders to get in touch with potential customers and allow them to *“see and touch the new models realised by the other boat builders every year”* (interview no. 3).

When present, the customer can negotiate the creative project submitted by the brand. As one architect explained, *“the customer is, to some extent, the true designer of the boat: he/she is the person who decides how the boat should be, even if it is to us the task of giving grace and logical sense to his/her desires”* (interview no. 14). As anticipated, the owner may decide to rely on his/her personal designers and architects, for both the external lines and the interiors:

It is a very rare case but, when it happens, I remain the reference point of the boat builder: the yacht is a complex product, there’s a delicate concept of team that can’t be undermined. Then, I remain at the centre of the project, and I keep an open dialogue with the owner’s architect [...]. They know they can’t come to me and say, ‘you must do as I say’. They just tell me some of the owner’s wishes and I try to realise them. (interview no. 14)

Once the design of the external lines is completed, the project is engineered. This task involves a staff of four engineers and concerns the construction and functional aspects of the boat. The rendered project moves on to the prototype development phase – *“a small-scale model that serves as further proof of the functioning of the project”* (interview no. 4). Then, the designer supplies the metrics to the supplier that will realise the fibreglass mould. As for the interior design, the process includes three actors: the shipowner, the brand, and the architect. As the interior designer clearly explained, *“our goal is to please the shipowner as much as possible and make him feel the true creator of his dream, his toy, his passion”* (interview no. 14). The work begins with the drawing of the interior layout of the boat and covers the stylistic aspects of the internal spaces. Then, the design and rendering process (which is sometimes delegated to external collaborators) begins. Whereas the exterior lines are unchangeable, the interiors remain flexible and highly customisable. The architect emphasised that *“never, in my life, have I realised two identical boats”* (interview no. 14).

Production

The phase of production involves the brand, the boatbuilder shipyard (with its carpenters and workers), and several enterprises, craft enterprises, or single craftspeople who work as suppliers or subsuppliers. The process begins with the production of the fibreglass hull, externalised to a supplier on the basis of the technical project provided by the boat builder company. The hull is moved to the shipyard, where the outfitting of the yacht begins. According to one informant, the CEO at a boat builder company, the multiplicity of actors cooperating in this phase makes the shipyard resemble

a mix between a hive and the Milan Cathedral construction site: a nonstop laboratory, a bustle of artisans who work in teams, respect each other, help each other and collaborate side by side, supporting and enduring each other. (interview no. 4)

This image is realistic and vibrant: during the building process – which generally lasts 2 years – a large amount of manpower operates in the shipyard, dealing with all aspects of production. The actors that participate in the process, mostly artisanal enterprises, are carpenters, plumbers, electricians, metal carpenters, mechanics, motorists, insulators, electricians, external deck layers, upholsterers, refrigerator technicians, air conditioning installers, glaziers, painters, marble workers, handlers, and testers.

These actors share the yard with enterprises that produce accessories, which assemble the onboard components produced in their own production plants and sold separately to the brand and/or to the shipowner. To describe the 150–200 people who collaborate in the construction of the boat under the guidance of the shipyard director, one informant used the expression *“nautical tribe”* (interview no. 4). To the eyes of a visitor, it really appears like a tribe working with precision and devotion on a cathedral:

Teams of workers take charge of almost every square centimetre of the boat. Each team wears a different coverall. Working rhythms appear intense, but not convulsed. The shipyard director controls the activities taking place onboard: I can see some blue coveralls polishing the externals of the hull. On a mobile scaffolding, foreign workers are cleaning windows and portholes. Carpenters check that the furnishings are perfect, and a marble worker struggles with the shower tray. The electricians check the circuit-breakers, and the team of electronics installs a TV on a retractable structure. In the middle of the living room – walls in onyx and furnishing in dark, precious woods – a middle-aged woman is cleaning up the parquet. I ask the shipyard manager: ‘Until what time will you go on?’. He replies: ‘Until we finish everything’. I ask: “What time are you finishing, then?” ‘When everything is perfect’. (Fieldwork notes n. 1)

When everything is perfect, the yacht leaves the shipyard and is *paraded* along the streets of Viareggio; finally, it reaches the square of another shipyard, closer to the dock, and awaits the launching ceremony.

Distribution

The phase of distribution coincides with the delivery of the yacht to the customer. Typically, delivery occurs at the dock closest to the shipyard. After the launching ceremony, the customer boards and controls the boat with the help of the captain. The yacht is not yet finished and remains on the quay for as long as necessary to fine-tune the details, accessories, and final furnishings. Usually, brands rely on a global distribution network of exclusive or authorised dealers. These actors “*are key figures that assist brands in sales and after sales services [...]. Usually, if a brand does not have a well-developed structure of dealers, it cannot face the global market*” (interview no. 4). This is not the case for the investigated brand. In fact, the CEO stated the following: “*Even if our yachts are distributed globally, we do not have a network of dealers because our production is limited. Nevertheless, we have developed some special relationships with Italian and international brokers who collaborate with us and help us to sell our boats*” (interview no. 4). Brokers are also key figures for the sale of used and refitted boats.

Exchange

The phase of exchange involves fairs and boat shows, prizes, advertising, and the media system. Trade fairs and boat shows are the most critical pieces of this puzzle. Among the B2C fairs, boat shows represent the meeting point between brands, boaters, and fans of the sector. Here, brands have the chance to exhibit new models and push their innovations. These events are a crucial moment for connecting brands with potential customers. The investigated brand exhibits its yachts at the most important boat shows in the world, such as the Genoa Boat Show in Italy, the Cannes Yachting Festival in France, and the Fort Lauderdale International Boat Show in the USA. The Genoa Boat Show is the largest exhibition event in the Mediterranean and the most representative of Made in Italy. Organised by Confindustria Nautica with the support of the Italian Trade and Investment Agency, the fair met enormous success in the 2021 edition, with 93,000 visitors, 947 accredited journalists, more than 1

million interactions on social media, and 992 exhibitors, including brands, manufacturers, suppliers, and service companies. The Cannes Yachting Festival, founded in 1977, is considered the most elegant European boat show. The Fort Lauderdale International Boat Show is the greatest in-water boat show in the world, owned by the Marine Industries Association of South Florida (MIASF). Besides B2C fairs, other events are planned to connect brands and suppliers, namely B2B fairs. The most important, METS Trade, takes place in Amsterdam: it is considered the world's largest trade exhibition of marine equipment, materials, and systems and has served as *"a platform for innovation, market developments and networking"* since its launch in 1988.⁷⁶

Fairs and boat shows are often accompanied by prizes and awards for brands, designers, and suppliers. Every year, the Genoa Boat Show assigns the *"Design Innovation Award"*, aiming to *"support and encourage the excellence within the yachting sector"*⁷⁷; the Amsterdam METS Trade assigns the *"Boat Builders Award"*, rewarding *"personal achievement, environmental responsibility, collaborative working, innovation, design and marketing"*. The investigated brand and its architect have been awarded several times for the elegance, innovation, and sustainability of the boats realised. Prizes and awards do not have a direct impact on yacht sales, but they do contribute to the brand's reputation. As one informant highlighted, *"these awards don't help sell more yachts, but they get reporters to write a lot about the award-winning brand, so they have a direct or indirect impact on the winner"* (interview no. 4).

Furthermore, the media system contributes to accruing the symbolic value of yachts through traditional advertising promotion channels, social media, technical reviews, and sea trials reports. Additional nodes for value creation are the shipowners and boat captains.

Archiving

The phase of archiving does not seem particularly developed. To some extent, the final product could be considered an archive itself as it incorporates the work done by the artisans who collaborated in its manufacturing. Furthermore, in some areas with a greater specialisation in shipbuilding, where the nautical tradition is more rooted, several museums collect and exhibit the historical evidence of the techniques and know-how of the ancient *artisans of the sea*. This is the case for the Museo dei Maestri d'Ascia e dei Calafati of Viareggio, which represents a valuable testimony of the shipbuilding history of the town. Some vintage boat collections also exist, such as the Lake Como International Museum of Vintage Boats, which preserves more than 400 historic hulls and exhibits seven prestigious models of Riva, an iconic Italian brand of the recreational craft industry. As the investigated brand is not present in any of these museums or collections, this phase is not relevant to it.

The main tasks and phases of the investigated production network are displayed in *Figure 6* (see next page).

⁷⁶ See <https://www.metstrade.com>.

⁷⁷ See <https://salonenautico.com/en/design-innovation-award-2/>

Figure 4. Case 1: Production network tasks and phases

3.2.1.2 Locations

Within the creation phase, the brand relies on a yacht designer and a team of engineers who are based in Liguria. Here, the universities of Genoa and La Spezia organise degrees and specialisation courses in yacht design and nautical engineering. As for the architect studio, which is located in Umbria and Tuscany, a specific relation with territory does not seem to emerge.

The phase of production is geographically concentrated in the nautical district of Viareggio. This concentration depends on the specific ‘industrial atmosphere’ that characterises the locale, which is based on three elements. The first is the availability of shipyards and docks where the manufacturing and delivery of the final product are realised. As the CEO of the brand highlighted, *“we were obliged to outsource the production of our 24-metre boats to Viareggio because we don’t have large enough shipyards in our region [Liguria]”* (interview no. 4). The second element is the availability of a specific productive fabric, which is made of MSMEs that have developed functional interdependencies and are able to serve luxury brands. As one informant specified, *“there are other areas of Italy where it is perhaps easier to have spaces, larger construction sites, but then there are no enterprises! I think that is important to stay in territories where the enterprises are”* (interview no. 9). The third element is the availability of a skilled workforce. As claimed by one informant, *“products are built where there is a [...] specific ability”* (interview no. 3), and Viareggio seems to present a high concentration of these abilities: *“Shipyards exist all over the world, but quality is only found here”* (interview no. 9). As the CEO of the brand clarified, *“it would not be possible to realise our yachts in places others than this: here we have the maximum of quality and specialisation”* (interview no. 4).

With concern to distribution, it is undoubtedly international, even if the delivery of the final product occurs in local docks. The phase of exchange is also global as the fairs and boat shows are located in different cities in Italy, Europe, and the USA. The spatial footprint of the investigated production network is presented in *Figure 7*.

Figure 5. Case 1: spatial footprint of the production network

3.2.2 Relationships between actors

3.2.2.1 Governance

After identifying the key actors of the production network, let us focus on the governance of the network. As clarified in deliverable D1.3, studying governance means examining how power is distributed among the actors who participate in the different phases of the production cycle. Within the GPN framework, power is described as relational, and its forms can vary according to the type of resources exchanged between actors. The objective of this subsection is to identify those resources and how the relevant relationships are governed.

As will be discussed, considering the whole network, power seems to assume a dyadic structure, polarising between the financial power of the shipowner and the organisational power of the brand. Other nodes of the network hold structural forms of power (e.g., the boatbuilder shipyard towards the second tiers of suppliers in case of subcontracting; the brokers towards the brand in case of intermediation, etc.). Based on these considerations, power seems to be dispersed in the network.

Before analysing the main aspects related to governance, *Figure 8* presents a graphical representation of power relations among the actors who participate in the network.

Figure 6. Case 1: Power relations among production network actors

3.1.2.1.1 Finance, control, and reputation: The flows of power between the customer and yacht builder

The relationship between the brand and the final customer implies different forms of power. First, it is clear that the customer holds the financial power: his/her choice to purchase the yacht makes him/her the real funder of the project. As confirmed by some informants, it is rare for a brand to start the production of a boat without a purchase contract already formalised with the customer (interviews no. 4 and 14). Payments are linked to the achievement of the production goals established in the contract. The brand uses these sums to pay for materials, suppliers, and all workers involved in the project. The flow of the payments can be delayed or suspended in case of irregularities or delays in production. Furthermore, any production delays can result in penalties against the brand. Such a possibility makes clear that the financial power of the customer is associated with a power of control over the brand. As discussed below, this control echoes through the relationships between the brand and its suppliers. On its side, the brand holds a reputational capital originating from the values associated with its products: high quality, an artisanal *filière*, a deep commitment to sustainability, and the prestige of a Made in Italy production. However, according to the CEO, these values do not seem sufficient for balancing the power relation with the shipowner. In fact, referring to the price-making dynamics, although it is clear that *“the brand’s attempt is to maximise the ratio between the cost paid to suppliers and the final selling price”* (interview no. 9), *“the selling prices are always decided*

by the customer [...]. Our goal is to acquire our competitors' customers and turn them into our serial customers [...]. We are not interested in one-off sales [...] and therefore, by satisfying the customer on the price, we hope to invest in him” (interview no. 4).

3.1.2.1.2 Control, quality, and stability: The multi-faceted power that binds brands and suppliers

Regarding the production phase, the relationships between the brand and suppliers are crossed by different trajectories of power. In general terms, there is a clear predominance of the brand over the other actors; moreover, the boatbuilder shipyard retains a specific form of power over the brand and the suppliers. To explain the trajectories of this power, it is necessary to describe how formal relations among actors are organised.

As clarified in the general presentation of the case study, the brand is not directly involved in the production phase. Yachts are assembly products whose manufacturing is outsourced to different actors. Setting aside the suppliers of engines, most of these actors are artisans and craft enterprises. The brand activates contracts (procurements) or direct assignment procedures with them. The main contractors are the boatbuilder shipyard – which also provides carpentry services – and the enterprise that produces the fibreglass hull. These actors deal with the most valuable segments of production: the hull and the internal and external structures are the largest components of the yacht; they are also projected to resist and ensure the safety and reliability of the boat. Separate contracts are signed with other suppliers and craft enterprises (e.g., upholsterers, marble workers, installers, and plumbers).

The shipyard retains a specific form of power, which derives from the holding of the physical infrastructures where the yacht will be built. The owning of productive plants close to the sea is a critical asset and makes the boatbuilder shipyards a strategic partner for the investigated brand (interviews no. 4 and 16). Moreover, the shipyard can be framed as the central hub of the whole production process: the assembly of structures, components, and accessories take place here, making the shipyard a multi-employer context where different enterprises and workers coagulate. As anticipated, the relations among the brand and these enterprises are regulated through separated contracts.

Regarding the production phase, the brand acts as a *“process manager”* who coordinates and controls the work and tasks performed by the suppliers (interview no. 13). As confirmed by the CEO, *“we [the brand] are a bit like conductors, but we are also controllers of the quality of work”* (interview no. 4). The power of control is exerted through inspections of the production site: *“Our control is very tight: every week we personally check the progress of the work. We go to the shipyard personally; we do not send intermediaries [...]. We have the technical competence, and we don’t miss anything”* (interview no. 4). This penetrating control seems necessary for *“the terms of the contract with the shipowner to*

be respected. Nothing can be left behind: otherwise, the whole process will slow down” (interview no. 4). This may result in penalties and the suspension of payments from the client (interviews no. 4 and 13). In the event of delays in or problems with the delivery of the work, the brand also has the power to reframe the work and tasks of suppliers; in such cases, as the CEO highlighted, the supplier *“is joined by other workers who are moved to help him keep up with the pace of production”* or, in extreme cases, *“is replaced”* (interview no. 4).

The selected case is almost unique in the Italian nautical industry: due to its specific characteristics – a small-sized family-run company – it relies on a network of artisans that has remained stable over time. The CEO of the brand stated the following:

We have maintained the supply chain for generations. When my father ran the company, he worked with the parents of my current suppliers. Now I work with the children. We created a synergistic relationship: we trust the quality of their work and they know that we will entrust them with other jobs. (interview no. 4)

What emerges here is a typical trust-based relationship. Actors are connected through the mutual exchange of capitals/resources, which has settled over time: the brand mobilises its economic capital (“stability”) and the artisans mobilise their cultural/technical capital (“quality” and “know-how”). As the CEO of the brand clarified,

we [the brand] respect suppliers by guaranteeing them economic stability [...] and they respect us by guaranteeing us the excellent quality of their services. We are not interested in looking around and we are not looking for other suppliers. The quality of our partners is so high that we can only be satisfied. (interview no. 4)

Does the observed balance between quality (know-how) and stability (economic satisfaction) make the relation more symmetrical? According to some artisans, the answer seems positive: *“We have been working with the brand for 30 years. As long as the brand is satisfied with our work and as long as we are happy with the economic part, we go on”* (interview no. 13). The mutual knowledge between brand and suppliers facilitates the making of deals that satisfy the needs of both parties:

The budgets established in the procurement are more or less standard with all brands – a strategic supplier says – and if you are good at organising, you are in it. We always try to please the brand, and the brand tries to please us. Let's face it: we are a resource for the brand! This year, our materials have increased by 30%: the brand has understood this and has adapted to our expenses, at our higher costs. (interview no. 15)

Since we have been collaborating for decades – another artisan says – we don't even propose estimates to the brand. The brand passes the order directly to us because the relationship is well defined, as usual, in terms of prices and methods. (interview no. 13)

The distribution of power seems to be much more asymmetrical in case of subcontracting. As anticipated in Subsection 3.2.1.1, it is possible that contractors (the boatbuilder shipyard, fibreglass hull producer, and craft enterprises) delegate some parts of the production (e.g., assembly operations, painting, or upholstery) to other enterprises or craftspeople, thus activating a second-tier supply. In general terms, these relations are formalised through contracts between contractors and subsuppliers. The brand is aware of these procedures but is formally kept out of them: it continues to exert a power of control and coordination over the production process and leaves contractors free to decide how to organise and concretely regulate their relations with subcontractors. This process has a relevant implication in terms of the power distribution. In fact, to enter the production network, subcontractors are driven to offer their services at lower costs, whereas the main contractor retains the largest share of remuneration. This dynamic led one informant to claim that *“this way, the actor who really makes the final product is not paid in the right way”* (interview no. 13).

3.1.2.1.3 Between finance and knowledge: The brand’s leading role in innovation

Other power dynamics are stimulated by the search for innovation within the network. The nautical industry is constantly looking for innovations, both in terms of products and processes. While process innovations mainly concern software and the equipment used for the design, construction, and assembly of yachts, product innovations are concentrated in the area of materials, propulsion methods, safety, and pollution. Generally, these innovations have an incremental character. The risks associated with innovation – typically borne by the brand – can be significant but determine the brand’s ability to expand its market shares and improve its positioning in the niche/segment of reference, thus prevailing over its competitors.

As for the investigated production network, the impulse to innovate comes from the brand, which is eager to *“come first, before the competitors”* (interview no. 4). Innovations are developed by the brand in cooperation with research centres and universities and financed with the support of local credit institutions. This mix of knowledge and financial power ensures the brand the very monopoly of innovation within the network.

The driver that pushes the brand to innovate is the will to produce sustainable yachts through low environmental impact productions. The brand is strongly committed to sustainability: this value represents its strategic asset and its hallmark compared with global competitors and pushes the company to *“make a big investment in the resources and specialisation of the suppliers, who are fully involved in the yacht construction project”* (interview no. 4). This means that the brand may take charge of the costs related to training and technical assistance, which are necessary for suppliers, who are affected by innovations. This task is achieved through collaboration with regional research centres, which deal with the transfer of technology. As the brand CEO stated, *“the researchers [of these centres] go to our suppliers to give instructions on how to work the new materials because they wouldn’t know how to do it”* (interview no. 4). Even if this technical assistance/training could promote the upskilling of suppliers, these actors seem not to be able to benefit from this transfer of technology:

the methods and technologies shared are often covered by patents, and suppliers cannot embed them in their ordinary production processes: *“The costs of innovation, including those for the materials, the brand pays them all. For this reason, what we learn does not come out of our relationship: we only use it when we work with him”* (interview no. 15). Therefore, the brand seems able to capture and reappropriate the value generated by the innovation, restoring itself from the initial investment in research.

Innovation is also requested from suppliers, who are encouraged by the brand to innovate materials or production processes to maintain pace with the innovations introduced by the brand. An example from the case study may be helpful to clarify exactly how: starting from the desire to create *“a super-light yacht [...], the most ecological as possible”* (interview no. 4), the brand and the engine supplier studied a radical innovation that required a deep change in the production process. This change required the involvement of all production partners in the implementation of the innovation. Faced with that challenge, the brand asked suppliers to *“study how to contribute to the construction of this boat [...]. Each brought their personal contribution, which actually improved the product [...] This improvement still continues to be applied”* (interview no. 4). This example confirms how the brand can capitalise on the effects generated by innovation.

3.2.2.2 Sociocultural embeddedness

Sociocultural embeddedness refers to a wide range of dimensions, including the historical, cultural, and institutional origins of the economic actors involved in the production network, the cultural identity and tradition related to the territory, and the aesthetic canons, among others.

Regarding the present case study, history and traditions seem to play a crucial role in explaining the relation between territory and the production network. As anticipated in the general description of the case study, the productive specialisations observed in Liguria and Tuscany are the result of a deep-rooted boatbuilding tradition, which dates back to the High and Late Middle Ages (AD 1000–1500) or even earlier. As for Liguria, several studies have documented that a technical know-how in boatbuilding had already developed before the Crusades (e.g., Gatti 2004). Referring to Tuscany, the maritime tradition dates back to the 15th century.

With regard to Viareggio, the modern development of the city is strictly intertwined with the rise of the maritime economy and the boatbuilding tradition. Here, successful shipbuilding activity started in the early 1800s. After the Congress of Vienna, in 1815, the Principality of Lucca (in which Viareggio is located) was assigned to the family of Bourbon, who held in great consideration the development of the port and other infrastructures; State Archives document that in 1823 a 50-tonne schooner was manufactured, commissioned to local workers by a foreign shipowner, which testified to the growth, reliability, and reputation of the local industry (see Falcini 1994). By 1832, the local labour maritime market counted approximately 3000 workers, including fishermen, sailors, boatbuilders, and other

nautical craftspeople (e.g., manufacturers of sails, ropes, and blocks). In 1848, the annexation of the Duchy of Lucca to the Grand Duchy of Tuscany changed the destiny of the local industry: from being the major maritime outlet of a small Duchy, Viareggio was reduced to a secondary role in favour of the larger ports of Livorno and Elba. Benefiting from the expansion of the commercial relations of the Grand Duchy and the circulation of greater financial capitals, the local shipyards were pushed to specialise in the building of elegant and relatively small boats made entirely of wood and dedicated to recreational uses. Along with the exploits of the so-called *barche viareggine*, some important local families of boatbuilders and shipwright masters emerged, such as the Pasquinucci, Bargellini, Bergamini, and Picchiotti families. These activities stimulated the birth of a local *filière* comprising caulkers, sailmakers, blacksmiths, and carpenters, among others. As reported by the historical documentation website “Viareggio as it was”, in those years the city had more than 60 looms for the production of sails (Falcini 1994). The local productive fabric also benefitted from the crucial contribution of the Ansaldo family, located in Genoa, who invested in the local competencies and, in 1917, founded the Sailing Ship Construction and Navigation Company. Within this company, which failed a few years later, some of the most important local boatbuilders were trained, such as Benetti and Codecasa. Within a few years, they founded their own brands, which quickly became global players, followed by other brands such as Bertani and Benetti, Landi, Itoyz, and Puccinelli. The representative of the Lucca division of the National Confederation of Artisans and Craft Enterprises (CNA) highlighted the following:

[S]ometimes people wonder how it could happen that a small town like Viareggio has become one of the most important luxury yacht production districts in Europe and perhaps in the world. One of the reasons is certainly the presence of a historical tradition. (interview no. 9)

According to this informant, history is not sufficient. Another reason for the success of the district seems to be the “*the ability of local entrepreneurs to reconvert their businesses after the spread of the crises affecting the sector*” (interview no. 9). In particular, the informant recalled the example of a local boatbuilder which, after the 2008 crisis, decided to upgrade and reposition in the advanced luxury segment:

In 2008, the brand that had commissioned the hulls to this shipyard cancelled all the orders. The shipyard remained with a number of hulls which, even though almost finished, could no longer be transformed in a final product. What happened? The brand decided to upgrade and produce mega-yachts with its own brand. This is not the unique example in this district. (interview no. 9)

What emerges from this account is the particular habitus or disposition that seems to characterise the local entrepreneurs: “*We call it resilience*”, certified the informant (interview no. 9).

Aesthetic intelligence and the capacity to realise/recognise beauty also seem to characterise the local area. The same informant emphasised how “*we, the Italians, and particularly the Tuscans, have*

metabolically assimilated the codes of beauty and harmony” (interview no. 9). According to the interviewee, “Italian brands can produce beautiful yachts because we have the code of beauty inside our DNA! It comes from the Renaissance... If you visit a yacht made in China, you will notice the differences. Staying in our yachts it’s just like... being in the Garden of Eden” (interview no. 9). Another informant, a well-known marble worker, listed with pride his works on the major mega-yachts of the world, and specified that he also collaborated in the restoration activities of the Basilica of Santa Croce in Florence:

Am I a craftsman or an artist? I don’t know... I come from Pietrasanta, a city where the tradition of marble workers is deeply rooted. Michelangelo Buonarroti also came here to quarry the marbles for the facade of San Lorenzo in Florence. I think my skills comes, to some extent, from the past. (interview no. 25)

3.2.3 Network type

In relation to the governance typologies described in the first part of this report (see “The CICERONE approach to production networks”), PRISMA seems to represent a case of a horizontal network. As discussed on the previous pages, power is in fact not concentrated in the hands of a unique actor but rather dispersed through different poles.

The prominent actors of the network are, undoubtedly, the shipowner and the brand: the first, with its financial power, is considered the very initiator of the network, while the second exerts its organisational power over its suppliers. However, the relationships among the brand and its suppliers seem multifaceted and not unidirectional (see *Figure 8* in Subsection 3.2.2.1). For instance, the boatbuilder shipyard retains a situational power towards the brand due to owning a critical asset for the whole production process, namely the construction site. At the same time, since productive relations are long lasting and based on trust, it seems that the brand and the suppliers are dispositive to make mutual concessions in regard to the economic conditions of the collaboration. On the other hand, the actors operating in the second-tier supply seem the weakest nodes of the network.

Relating to the spatial scale of the network, the prevailing scale is local/regional. As discussed in Section 3.2.1 (“Phases, actors, and locations”), the creation phase occurs in Liguria, whereas the production phase is fully concentrated in Toscana in the nautical district of Viareggio. Regarding distribution, it is undoubtedly international, even if the material delivery of the final product occurs in local docks. The phase of exchange is also global: publications, fairs, and boat shows are located in various cities in Italy, Europe, and the USA. Although not relevant to the production network, archiving mainly occurs locally.

The typology matrix represented in *Table 8* displays the spatial scale of each phase and the governance configuration of the production network.

Table 7. Case 1: spatial scale of the production network and its governance configuration

Production network phases	Local/ regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	Governance
Creation	Creators, customers, lead actors				
Production	Specialised suppliers	Specialised suppliers			
Distribution				Distributors, customers, Customers	
Exchange				Strategic partners- private	
Archiving	Strategic partners- public				
Network level					Horizontal

3.2.4 Impact

3.2.5.1 Economic impact

The economic impacts of the selected production network differ according to the spatial footprint of the activities and phases examined. As explained in Section 3.2.1 (“Phases, actors, and locations”), the phases of creation and production are located in different territories. Whereas creation is dispersed, production activities are concentrated in the city of Viareggio, within the most important Italian nautical district.

The brand – a family-run company founded in the Seventies, which has been able to evolve from offering nautical services to building boats with its own brand – is a medium-sized enterprise: its turnover is less than €50 million (2019 data) and its staff count is less than 15 people, who are employed in administration, the purchase office, and the technical office. The turnover and balance sheet total have been in growth for the last two years following the excellent performance of the national recreational craft industry.

In terms of employment and job creation, the phase of creation of the yacht – consisting of the interior and external design, plus the naval engineering of the boat – do not produce a large impact. These activities are entrusted to professionals who operate outside of the company: a naval engineer for the design of the external lines of the boat, an architect for the interior design, and a small team of technicians for the engineering phases. As the CEO of the brand explained, these are “*freelancers who work for us and some other brands*” (interview no. 4). These professionals have their headquarters in locations other than the brand: the naval engineer is based abroad (Switzerland), the architect has his business in two central Italian towns (in Umbria and Tuscany), while the engineering team is settled in a different province of Liguria. The incomes generated by these jobs is thus dispersed throughout different locations.

Moreover, the impacts of production activities are quite different. The building of the boat involves actors and activities selected from the brand through “*the strategy of concentric circles: we start from our territory [Liguria] and then we go to Tuscany, to Viareggio, where we take almost all the manpower. As for components, we consider also suppliers from the northern Italy*” (interview no. 4). Unlike creation, the production phase seems to generate consistent impacts in terms of employment. According to the CEO,

the recreational craft industry employs many people and gives many opportunities for job creation, from manpower to captains, who earn very well, and perhaps more than us [...] The same applies to artisans, such as plumbers and electricians. Anyone who can glimpse a niche, or a specialisation, can create new jobs in this industry”. (interview no. 4)

Thus, the industry seems to promote and reinforce the artisanal fabric of the territory. As a multiplicative mechanism, the artisanal activities seem to strengthen the related economic activities. As the president of the local section of the CNA highlighted, “*around the artisans’ workshop, a number of vital and interrelated economic micro-networks develop. [...] These activities have to do with raw materials and hold a deeply rooted transformative capacity*” (interview no. 9). The owner of a carpentry firm confirmed that “*our business, and also those of other shipyards and artisans who works with us, are able to create employment in this territory*” (interview no. 5). In short, it seems undisputable that the economic activities related to the very production of the yacht produce significant employment impacts, generating jobs and wages that remain in the area. These effects seem to be stable thanks to the high quality of the suppliers and artisans, whose know-how and expertise keep the production anchored to the territory: “*The Italian boat industry creates dependence on the products of supply chain because, after trying them, you will not accept a lower quality range*” (interview no. 4).

It was more difficult to determine the economic impacts in terms of employment created within the other phases of the production network. In the phase of distribution, it was assumed that a share of the workforce is activated to move the hull from the shipyard to the dock. Furthermore, the yacht’s logistical and launching procedures require the participation of technicians and workers from the port

area. As for the exchange phase, the activities of communication, marketing, and brokerage are undeniably related to the brand. These activities originate economic relationships and generate jobs and incomes. In regard to the sales segment, the brand's CEO reported that *"to sell [our yachts] we work with brokers, who introduce us to the client [...] and get a commission for the reporting and support work"* (interview no. 4). Usually, brokers are independent professionals or part of a brokerage company. As for the relationship between brands and media, the publication of articles/reviews about the features of the boat *"can be free [...] or for a fee"* (interview no. 6). This practice is not unusual in the nautical media system, where publications are often stimulated by the media-buying activity of the brand. As one editor clarified, *"among the responsibility of a media company, there is also the sustenance of the people who work within the company, so it is clear that we must accept advertising"* (interview no. 7). Nautical journalists are usually freelancers.

Moreover, the impact of fairs and boat shows should be seriously considered. Even though precise estimates are missing, it is undeniable that these events, by attracting shipowners, entrepreneurs, experts, the media, and simple visitors, have an economic impact. The Genoa International Boat Show is indicative: the event, held between the 16th and 21st of September 2021, was attended by 93,782 paying visitors and 947 accredited journalists (Salone Nautico, 2021). The organisational machine is that of major events, and the hospitality business draws a huge advantage from it. To provide a first-hand example derived from the fieldwork, the average hotel prices during the week of the show increased by more than 500%: the cost of a 2-star hotel room, usually available for 35 euros per night, reached a peak of 225 euros per night.

Lastly, the economic impact of the archive phase seems not to be particularly relevant. Considering the case of the Viareggio Museum of Shipwrights and Caulkers, people who provide the maintenance of the structure work as volunteers are associated with the League of Shipwrights and Caulkers of Viareggio.

3.2.5.2 Social impact

Focusing on social impacts means evaluating the ways in which the dynamics of the production network affect work and its conditions. This analysis includes the examination of the features of the employed workforce, working conditions, the agency of workers and workers' associations, the role of collective actors, and social upgrading processes (if any). Following Selwyn (2012) as well as Hess and Coe (2012), relevant to this analysis is the evaluation of the conditions under which the *structural* power of workers can turn into a *collective* power, which would be capable of negotiating its interests vis-à-vis the state and capital.

The analysis of these conditions starts with a study of the profile and characteristics of the labour employed within the different segments of the production network. The labour involved in the activities of creation, design, engineering, and sale of the boat is mainly intellectual, and it is managed

directly by the brand, through employment contracts, consultancy and – limited to the brokerage segment – agency contracts. Taking apart the figure of the broker, this group of workers appears to be the most protected within the production network. The reasons lie in the high attention that the brand claims to pay to the well-being of its employees. The CEO claimed that over the years, the company has increased its *"social sensitivity towards employees"* (interview no. 4) by adopting a series of benefits and corporate welfare actions aimed at improving their quality of work and life. These actions include the following:

Aids and loans for the purchase of the first home, investments in education and training to support the development and specialisation of skills in line with everyone's interests, the creation of a healthy and peaceful working environment, also through mediation activities in the event of conflicts in the workplace, and free psychological counselling in the event of personal problems. (interview no. 4)

The brand also seems to be particularly attentive to the creation of an inclusive work environment, reduction of the gender gap, and adoption of work–life balance actions aimed at guaranteeing *"flexibility for women who have children"* (interview no. 4), in line with the *"family feeling that marks all the activities of our company"* (interview no. 4). The brand is also considered a benchmark of female leadership in the nautical industry – a leadership that is also expressed through the role of the CEO in relevant regional employers' organisations. The gender equality issue is debated within the industry. Whereas the CEO of the brand stated that *"if you are skilled and competent, [...] you will rarely encounter difficulties, even if you are a woman in a context dominated by men"* (source: publications on the web), the president of Confartigianato claimed that *"in this industry, there are many opportunities for women, but it is thought that they are mostly reserved for men"* (source: publications on the web). The interpretation of this phenomenon changes depending on the point of observation. From the side of entrepreneurship, the data seem encouraging: according to Unioncamere estimates, female artisan enterprises represented 16.3% of the total artisan enterprises in 2019; furthermore, according to Confartigianato, Italian self-employed women number approximately 1.4 million, higher than the estimates for France (1.2 million) as well as Germany and Spain (1 million). On the other side, no data relating to female labour in artisan enterprises are available. Nevertheless, the evidence from the case study depicts a precise scenario: the workers involved in building the yacht are almost exclusively men. In fact, except for the CEO of the brand and one of her collaborators, the only female workers present at the shipyard during the fieldwork were a booth cleaner employed by a service company and the administrative secretary of the carpentry firm that hosts the hull. This trend was indirectly confirmed by the owner of another carpentry firm (external to the production network) who mention when his craft enterprise trained *"a girl who became a shipwright, probably the only woman in Italy to have chosen this career"* (interview no. 5).

Moving to the production phase, social impacts change considerably. As clarified in the section referring to the production network description (Section 3.2.1), the leisure boat industry makes extensive use of outsourcing through contracts and subcontracting practices. As reported by a trade

unionist, *“the production of a yacht [is] outsourced for more than 90%”* (interview no. 21). The selected case study also follows this typology. The brand is a marketer brand (a “manufacturer without factories” that does not participate directly in production activities; see Gereffi & Frederik, 2010), and production is entrusted to a galaxy of enterprises with different legal statuses and structures (e.g., individual firms, craft enterprises, and micro and small enterprises). These actors cooperate side by side on the same production site, realising a typical example of a “multi-employer working context” (Pira, Sacchetti 2020). Here, the supplier companies mediate the relationship between workers and the client company, reducing the agency of workers and workers’ associations (Coe, 2015). As one unionist stated, *“it is very difficult for unions to have access to shipyards. [...] It would take a small army to verify what happens there”* (interview no. 21).

Firms organise their workforce both through stable and atypical contracts. Employees are paid net salaries that range, depending on the company, between € 1 200 and € 1 800, excluding overtime. The use of atypical work may be urged by production rhythms or the specific kind of tasks and mansions. As explained by one craftsman, it may occur that

an enterprise [...] does not have enough staff to put on board. [...] Then, they call me to ask if I can lend the necessary workers. [...] I do not replace that enterprise in its formal relations with the brand: I just lend the necessary labour for the requested period, and that's all. (interview no. 23)

The use of atypical work affects low-skilled workers through damaging or arduous jobs. In this case, the labour division reproduces the nationality scheme:

We have a lot of jobs [...] and we need foreign workers, especially extra EU, to do them... because they are bad jobs, and Italians don't want to do them... even if you whip them! [...] So, many young workers come from Senegal, Sri Lanka or other countries, with regular contracts of course. These are jobs that the Italians, justifiably, and now also the Romanians, refuse to do despite the protective devices, the vacuum cleaners and everything. [...] They are harmful, ugly jobs [...] that are not pleasant to do. (interview no. 15)

Another informant, external to the selected production network, confirmed the tendency of some brands and shipyards to employ foreign labour to reduce production costs: *“If I call Romanians, I will certainly save money. [...] It's bad to say, but... they are not like us: they accept lower treatment and payments. It is not a question of capacity [...] It just works like this”* (interview no. 22). The same narrative characterised the words of another artisan, who stated that *“Sinhalese and Romanians [...] are not afraid to work for lower salaries because... they need. They accept salaries of 1500 euros, which for an Italian who has a family are few. Romanians seem much more incentivised”* (interview no. 23).

The owners of companies that employ atypical labour specified that recruitment occurs according to the law: *“If you are not up to date with the documents, procedures, payments, safety courses, and*

medical check-up, you cannot enter the shipyard” (interview no. 23). The unions, however, specified that it is not so important to understand:

... whether you are paying contributions; what is key is to understand how many hours these people are working and how many hours you are paying them. You can't verify this data through the documents delivered by the contractor. You could do it only via the L.U.L. (Libro Unico Lavoro) but contractors never show these documents. (interview no. 21)

In conclusion, unionists affirmed that the industry suffers from some anomalies regarding the forms of payment and remuneration of workers (interview no. 21). In particular, some contractors used to pay atypical workers with the “global payroll formula” (“paga conglobata”), and through the disproportionate use of cost reimbursements and travel allowances. The use of global payrolls was condemned by unions:

[W]orkers think they are getting a big salary, but in reality, they are being deceived: they are paid for what they are entitled to. [The global payroll, in fact] includes bonuses, holidays, severance pay, leave, and so on ... It is not an extra salary: it is only what you are entitled to be paid and will be deducted at the end of the year. Deducting these items from the payroll, the wages become very low. This is why the workers are deceived [...]. (interview no. 21)

3.2.5.3 Cultural impact

Shifting to culture, the selected production network seemed to have several impacts on the cultural development of territories. First, a general consideration might be adduced about the cultural value of the production model itself. As confirmed by some informants, the boat building industry is turning gradually towards semi-industrial production models, in which the role of craftspeople is being increasingly marginalised, if not even put at risk (interviews no. 4, 20, 14, and 16). In fact, many boat builders, aiming to achieve scale economies and reduce production costs, choose to shrink the share of craftpersonship involved in shipbuilding, favouring standardised or industrial design products. Typical in this brand’s production model is the fully artisanal quality and customisability of recreational boats, which is not compatible with any industrial process. That is why the brand’s production model seems to be a bulwark of tradition – a resilient production model resisting the standardisation vogue. In fact, as one informant highlighted, “*PRISMA’s production process is typically artisanal [and] it should be cloned because, unfortunately, it will soon be gone*” (interview no. 14).

Other cultural impacts can be traced within the activities conducted by the brand in the context of corporate social responsibility. The brand is proud to testify its commitment “*to the community [through] the sponsorship of cultural, sporting and social events, or through collaborations with technical schools, universities and design schools for surveys, studies, internships or tutoring of masters*” (interview no. 4). As for cultural projects, the brand seems to act as a patron, financing the

realisation of events of international calibre (e.g., an exhibition on the masterpieces of European Impressionism, held in Liguria in 2019) and economic support for cultural competitions, festivals, artistic activities, and reviews organised in the territory, also in partnership with noneconomic stakeholders (i.e., in cooperation with centres of contemporary art and media). Its support for sporting activities has resulted, in particular, in the sponsorship of some sport teams from a Ligurian province (source: brand's Facebook page). As for the support for educational and research institutions, the brand underlines its *"natural inclination to support education"* through collaborations with universities, aimed at *"encouraging development and research, promoting innovation in design"* and *"at sensitizing future designers to [...] respect for the environment"* (source: brand's website). Furthermore, the brand supports the activities of *"marine biologists operating in the area"* (interview no. 4) and hosts school groups interested in visiting the shipyard. A further indication of the attention of the brand towards educational challenges is found in its commitment to promoting the STEAM disciplines among young students – especially women – of the territory, through the financing of scholarships and grants. As for social projects, the brand supports some initiatives on the social integration of people with functional diversities (source: publications on the web).

The major cultural implication of the activities of the brand seems to be linked to sustainability. The brand is highly committed to reducing the environmental impact of recreational boats. The search for sustainability through innovation is *"in the company's DNA"* (source: brand's website) and has become the brand's strategic asset, differentiating it from other national and international competitors. This commitment is recognised by the stakeholders through prizes (also in important international contexts) and appreciations, also confirmed by some interviewees:

At a first glance, the yachts produced by PRISMA may seem like simple luxury products... but this is not the real value that defines its positioning on the market. The real value is respect for the environment. Therefore, we are faced with luxury products that are made with sustainability parameters that, in this industry, only this PRISMA seems to have. (interview no. 7)

This *ethos* is transferred to the financing of experiments on the construction materials of boats and research on technological solutions aimed at reducing polluting emissions, often through partnerships with universities and research centres in Liguria, Lombardy, and Emilia-Romagna. To evaluate whether this process allows for cultural upgrading, it might be useful to understand the attitude of the brand towards the diffusion of the research product. On the one hand, the brand's cultural concern towards sustainability seems to go beyond the organisation's boundaries, affecting all suppliers involved in the building of the boat. In fact, as clarified in Section 3.2.2 (*"Relationships between actors"*), some selected suppliers (i.e., the hull producers) are invited to collaborate in the co-design of innovation and are supported by the brand in their upskilling processes. Based on this consideration, it seems that this corporate culture may extend its effects to the whole *filière* (or its strategic nodes). As for the diffusion of innovations and research products outside of the network, it is unclear whether the brand has an *"open innovation"* attitude. On the one hand, it was reported that the brand publicly

shared the results of its research on the acoustic emissions of boats as a “gift for the future of the environment” (source: publication on the web); also reported was the brand’s decision to share the results of other experimentation on materials during a prestigious yacht event in 2022. On the other hand, it was specified that such experimentation is protected by patent (source: publication on the web). Notwithstanding, the brand is proud to remark that its attitude differs from *“the general individualism that prevails among superyacht manufacturers”* (interview no. 4). The CEO specified that often *“our openness perhaps has not been understood by our competitors, and I don't think we will receive similar offers from any of them”* (interview no. 4). Further evidence of the brand’s attention to the issue of environmental sustainability is found in its support for initiatives to safeguard Mediterranean cetaceans, organised by important Italian nonprofit organisations.

Some additional cultural impacts emerge from the phases of exchange and archive. Regarding exchange, it is undeniable that fairs and boat shows – whose economic impacts were discussed earlier – operate as territorial marketing agents: the weeks of the shows are an excellent opportunity for the territories to promote their own traditions and initiatives related to art, hiking, and cooking (source: publications on the web). As for the archive phase, the Museum of the Shipwrights and Caulkers of Viareggio has a primary role in documenting the social function and traditional construction techniques that have characterised the shipbuilding history of Viareggio, but it also has a documentary function of the local antifascist resistance. The Museum, preserved by the abovementioned League of Shipwrights and Caulkers, finances grants and scholarships dedicated to the memory of two mariners killed by fascist squads in the early 1920s.

3.2.5 Policy implications

In recent decades, the recreational boating industry has been significantly impacted by EU legislation and the development of the single market. The key legislation for the industry is the Recreational Craft Directive 2013/53, adopted in November 2013, which updated legislation covering the design and manufacture of motor and sailing crafts. The Directive laid out the requirements for the assessment procedures to be followed by manufacturers when demonstrating the conformity of their products. It also sought to ensure, by complying with the same standard, that fair competition exists for these products in the EU market. Other relevant legislation refers to consumer rights, taxation, product safety, and environmental issues.⁷⁸

⁷⁸ As for **consumer rights**, the Directive 2011/83/EU sought to harmonise several aspects of national legislation on contracts between customers and sellers, increasing consumer protection. Concerning **taxation**, the VAT Directive 2006/112/EC updated the Common System for Value Added Tax, clarify the EU’s VAT legislation currently in force. Referring to **product safety**, Directive 2001/95/EC on General Product Safety required firms to ensure that items on sale are safe and to take corrective actions when that is found not to be the case. Regarding **environmental issues**, various legal instruments have been adopted at the EU level: the Water Directive 2000/60/EC established a Framework for Community Actions in the field of water policy; Regulation n. 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) addressed the production and use of chemical substances and their potential impacts on human health and the environment; the Marine Strategy Framework Directive 2008/56/EC established a framework for Community Action in the field of marine environmental policy; the Waste Framework

Although these policy instruments cover different areas of interest – such as business and trade, technical and safety issues, tourism, environment, the circular economy, and navigation – they address only in part the artisans and craft enterprises that operate in the industry. Nonetheless, by providing a set of common rules about different aspects of the creation, production, sales, and consumption of recreational crafts, the aforementioned policy instruments affect the competitiveness of the industry, both at the EU and Member State level.

3.2.6.1 Side effects of national policies and the battle against ‘luxury’

Stressing the national impacts of these policies, the informant representing the Italian Marine Industry Association (Confindustria Nautica) emphasised the proactive role of the association in urging the Italian government to adapt to the EU framework: *“We proposed a lot of things to the Italian policymakers, especially at a regulatory level [...] The rapid adaptation to EU directives and the common European framework was crucial in order not to lose competitiveness [...]”* (interview no. 3). Here, a first policy issue seems to emerge that refers to the scarce responsiveness of national policies to the EU policy framework.

The Association also complains that Italian policymakers have always paid insufficient attention to the recreational boating industry, outlining the ‘side effects’ of the policies adopted in the past:

We have called for more attention to politics many times... In general, in recent years, all we have asked for has been to correct the mistakes generated by the previous policies. We could say that, rather than asking for help, we have been asking for remedies [...]. (interview no. 3)

In detail, the informant evoked the year 2013, when

the Italian government introduced a possession tax impacting on yacht owners. With which results? All the boats fled from Italy... Italian politicians have not understood that boats can move, and shipowners can register their flags elsewhere... So, to put it simply, the cited possession tax caused the exodus of 40 thousand boats to other States [...]. (interview no. 3)

This situation exemplifies how negative a short-sighted policy could be in terms of cross-sectoral economic impacts. In fact, shifting back to the reported example, the political decision to tax the owners of yachts and superyachts resulted in a migration of boats that affected the general incomes of mooring-related activities, such as repair, technical assistance, nautical services, marinas, yacht clubs, and tourism: *“Yachts have high maintenance costs. If the State does not favour their stay in our*

Directive 2008/98/EC established a legal framework for treating waste in the EU, confirmed the “polluter-pays principle”, and introduced the concept of extended producer responsibility; the Biocidal Products Regulation n. 528/2012 harmonised the EU’s rules concerning the sale and use of biocidal products; the Port Reception Facilities Directive (EU) 2019/883 enhanced the availability and use of port reception facilities for ship-generated waste and cargo residues.

ports, there will be a loss of turnover, lower VAT and a generalised reduction of revenues along all the related economic activities” (interview no. 3). Based on these claims, the informant seemed to suggest that long-sighted, strategic policies would be crucial for the industry: more advantageous taxation regimes and support for the growth of the economy that encompass navigation and yacht maintenance could promote the development of the entire chain of the activities that serve the boating industry, including artisans and craft enterprises.

According to some informants, the contested policies reveal a latent “state of war against luxury” that would pervade the Italian political institutions: “Unfortunately, boating is considered in Italy stuff for the super-rich. Elsewhere, boating is like a middle-class affair – as it should be” (interview no. 3); “Due to its belonging to the luxury industry, this industry is considered disagreeable and is sometimes instrumentalised” (interview no. 4); “Almost all over the world, boating is considered something popular. In Italy, it is considered a priori as matter for the richest. I think it depends on the ancient and deep-rooted hatred that some institutions cultivate against luxury... This hatred penalised the boating industry for many years’ (interview no. 7). This vision was also confirmed by a young Ligurian shipwright, who was interviewed as the owner of a shipyard specialising in the building of one-off wooden boats:

In my opinion, politics is completely absent [...]. Politicians assume that we, boatbuilders, can survive on our own, perhaps because our business is associated with luxury industries. It’s a misleading assumption. Thus, the existing policies privilege other economic activities... I think there would be more balance. (interview no. 5)

3.2.6.2 Fragmented and divergent: The difficult representation of artisans and workers’ interests

The multiplicity of actors and diversity of interests involved in the leisure boating industry make it difficult to present a coherent platform of claims or policy demands related or connected to the craft component. This issue was confirmed by the President of the Lucca section of the CNA:

It is not easy to collate and integrate the requests that rise from the actors of the industry. A latent competition marks the field, in particular the peripheral tiers of the supply chain [...]. Interests are very fragmented, and it is hard to develop common positions to recommend to policymakers. (interview no. 9)

Divergence and fragmentation arose, for instance, from the opposite assessments that a craftsman and a trade unionist provided on workforce conditions in the shipyards. The craftsman claimed that he has nothing to complain about regarding his condition: “The boating industry is a little paradise. There is a lot of work, and you are well paid for it. Everyone is happy: that’s all. Even if something does not work, it’s not worth opening up Pandora’s box. Can you understand me?” (interview no. 13). The

trade unionist, on the other hand, reflected on the “*loansharking dynamics*” (interview no. 21) that mark the supply relationships and weaken labour rights and conditions (see *Subsection 3.5.2.2* and *Subsection 3.2.6.3*). These contrasting visions persisted through the interviews and made a homogeneous representation of the policy implications of the case study difficult. Notwithstanding, some key issues seemed to emerge, which are discussed as follows.

3.2.6.3 Costs and remuneration of labour

The first issue is related to costs and the remuneration of labour. Craft business owners reflect on the excessive gap between the cost of an hour of work and the net salary received by workers. This gap is due to tax and fiscal burdens. As one informant highlighted, “*the basic problem is that the enterprise spends too much, and the employee takes too little. To give you a practical idea, an employee who gets paid 9 euros per hour only gets 6 euros in his paycheck... But to me, his employer, it costs 18*” (interview no. 15). Thus, this informant suggested measures aimed at reducing fiscal burdens and taxes on labour. One of the informants underlined how urgent it is to intervene “*on the tax wedge, which remains the greatest burden for employers and employees. It is unbelievable that you, the employer, pay 2700 euros for each worker, and they receive only 1200*” (interview no. 28). Another informant who runs a small craft enterprise involved in marble cutting confirmed the following:

[W]ages are too low. You cannot accept salaries of 900 or 1000 euros per month. Every month, a worker loses between 300 and 450 euros in fiscal burdens. It's impossible to continue this way. And we, the employers, would like to hire new and young workers, but we don't have any kind of help or relief from the State. (interview no. 23)

As stated by another informant, this issue risks generating dissatisfaction and tension at work. By reflecting on the paradox of a “*worker who costs me 3000 euros a month and receives a net salary of 1200*”, the informant conceded that “*it is natural that workers get pissed! You ask them to be highly productive, but they harvest a marginal part of what they have sown*” (interview no. 15).

The analysis of the economic treatment of labour is also tackled by unions. Whereas self-employed artisans depict the boating industry as a “*little paradise*” where “*craftspeople earn much more than the artisans who work in the civil industry*” (interviews no. 13 and 23), trade unions shed light on the conditions of the underclass who populate the industry. Workers belonging to this group are not properly artisans: they perform their job for craft enterprises, but they are administered by third firms involved in subcontracting relations. Usually, these workers are foreigners and low-skilled and have a scarce sense of union membership; they do not ask for adequate information on pay slips, nor do they receive them from their employer. Abusing this situation, third firms pay them through the aforementioned “*global paycheck*” (see *Subsection 3.5.2.2*). Thus, ‘workers are fooled’ because the final sum they receive is much lower than the one communicated on the pay slip (interview no. 21). This scenario was confirmed by the owner of a carpentry firm:

Once, something unbelievable happened to me. I had an employee who cost me 25 euros per hour. He told me that he wanted to leave due of a better-paid position. Some months later, I needed to employ some external workers for a project I was involved in, and I met again that guy. I discovered that he was costing me lower than before: his enterprise re-sold him to me for 23 euros per hour! Then, I called him aside and asked: “Are you sure you are earning more?” He replied: “Sure! They give me a global paycheck!” Here is the catch [...]’. (interview no. 20)

3.2.6.4 Pitfalls related to subcontracts

Loss of control over labour conditions over the filière

As seems self-evident, the global paycheck issue is strictly linked to the organisational dynamics of the industry, which makes extensive use of outsourcing, generating multiple tiers of suppliers and multiemployer work contexts. As indicated earlier, this situation makes it difficult for trade unions to access and comprehend the deep dynamics that affect labour within the shipyards. As one unionist clarified,

it is impossible to monitor and verify what happens every day in shipyards. These sites are crowded by hundreds of workers who depend on different enterprises. Many of these do not even have the numbers or the capacity to elect union representatives, so it is really difficult to get in. (interview no. 8)

Another unionist confirmed that

as union organisation, it is difficult to have access to the peripheral tiers of supply. This happens, generally, when the brand or the shipyard is close to bankruptcy. In these cases, there is a general stampede, and the workers turn to us so as not to risk losing money. (interview no. 21)

These considerations testify to the difficulty of monitoring methods of recruitment and the remuneration of work, generating a ‘grey area’ in which anti-union or illegal practices could find a place. To overcome these difficulties, trade unions have been studying “*the possibility of electing representatives of the whole supply chain. These figures could also take charge of the conditions of contracting and sub-contracting workers*” (interview no. 8). Furthermore, “*safety protocols with brands and shipyards should be strengthened, aimed at guaranteeing punctual controls on all the workers accessing to shipyards*” (interview no. 21).

According to some informants, greater attention to the economic treatment of the workforce would also allow unfair competition dynamics to emerge. This seems to be the case for enterprises that employ foreign workers, compressing labour costs to extreme levels:

In the industry, there's a lot of enterprises from Balkans and Eastern who have prices 40% lower than ours. Please, believe me: it's impossible to survive with those prices, unless you renounce to safety or labour protection standard. Usually, these enterprises end up in some mass and close, reopening sometime later with other names. This is unacceptable and it is not allowed to Italian enterprises. (interview no. 23)

Loss of quality, competitiveness, and authorship

According to some informants, the dynamics of subcontracting also risk compromising the quality of the products, causing the loss of an asset that is strategic both for the national and local yachting industry. This loss depends on the intense unbundling of production, induced by cost pressures and productivity needs. As a marble cutter highlighted,

when choosing between quality and budget, quality loses. I am not saying that quality is completely lacking in our products; I am just saying that the dynamics no longer allow to reach the levels of 10 years ago. Now, boatbuilding looks like an assembly line [...]. (interview no. 23)

This issue was picked up by other informants. One of them – a retired carpenter who spent his professional life in a top-level shipyard – clearly stated that, “*due to cost pressure, you are no longer able to produce top-quality furniture; you must be content to produce furniture that resembles luxury products*” (interview no. 22). Another informant framed the loss of quality in terms of loss of competitiveness:

In my opinion, Italian quality has gradually declined. [...] I met some people who showed me their boats made in Germany and the Netherlands. They told me: “We used to purchase such beautiful ships in Viareggio, now times have changed”. I am seriously concerned that our industry risks repeating the destiny of the Italian automotive industry. You know, in the past we have all bought Italian cars, but... then we switched to the Germans! As an artisan business owner, I ask myself and the others: are we sure that everything is fine in our industry? (interview no. 20)

An underrated policy issue is the loss of authorship and recognition implied by subcontracting dynamics. As one informant complained, the increasing unbundling of production generates the birth of new economic actors who position between brands, shipyards, and suppliers and pretend to be craft enterprises to sign up contracts with clients:

There are many fake artisans around. They're intermediaries or traders who, after the sign of the contracts, delegate production to other companies like mine. What happens to my job, then? [...] I am sure that the shipyard knows that the job was made by me, but [...] I feel not recognised

adequately, even to an economic level. [...] The subcontracting system should be revised. It would take more precise rules to protect those who actually carry out the work. (interview no. 13)

3.3.1 Loss of know-how and productive tradition: The issue of training and technical education

There is a clear connection between the loss of quality and skills and traditional know-how. As clearly stated by one informant, if you are socialised in a culture where quality does not matter, *“you will end up losing your skills because you will say to yourself: ‘What’s the point of doing something right, if the only thing that matters is to do it fast?’”* (interview no. 22). Thus, *“skills and competences will be lost”* (interview no. 20). This is not a secondary question for an industry which built its reputation in a top-quality and highly skilled labour market. Therefore, a contradiction seems to exist between statements and real processes.

On the one hand, one stakeholder stated the following: *“People ask how a little town like Viareggio could have become an excellence in luxury boats building. The answer is: traditional local know-how plus investment in skills reproduction”* (interview no. 9). On the other hand, one artisan complained that *“craft competencies are gradually expiring”* (interview no. 13). According to a craft business owner, this process should alarm brands and shipyards: *“[P]rotecting artisanal skills should be of primary interest to them because they no longer have any productive capacity. They delegate all to artisans. What happens if we disappear?”* [RIE]. Relating to this issue, an upholsterer complained that *“even if they should, brands and shipyards do not give any support in transferring our know-how to new generations. Contacts are generally short-term, and they do not allow us to assume the risk of investing”* (interview no. 13). Thus, as a carpenter suggested spectacularly, *“in some years, maybe 10 years, if you give a hand tool to a young worker, you will see that he will not be able to use it”* (interview no. 22). Strengthening this concern, another informant stated that *“the Italian boating industry is based on the know-how of these artisans: we should clone them because, soon or later, they will disappear”* (interview no. 14).

Faced with this scenario, the Councillor for the Economy of Tuscany declared the following:

[M]aybe, a nostalgic idea of crafts will decline, but this does not mean that artisans will vanish: our effort should be devoted to ensuring the right mix of craftsmanship and mechanisation to the leisure boating industry. In this direction, the whole education system should proceed. (interview no. 27)

3.3.2 Measuring the relevance of artisans: The need for dedicated NACE codes

Reflecting on the importance of artisans who work in the leisure boating industry, a craft enterprise representative confessed how *“it is difficult to accurately measure the contribution of craft business*

to development and turnover of the local nautical district". For this reason, the informant suggested that "some specific NACE codes should be dedicated to nautical artisans. This lack is weakening us. With dedicated NACE code, we could finally demonstrate with numbers how important is our role" (interview no. 26).

3.4 Final remarks

Based on the investigated project, some general remarks on the role and function of artisans and craft enterprises can be made. The first concerns the difficulty of providing accurate estimates of the socioeconomic impacts of artisans and craft enterprises, both at the EU and national levels. As discussed in the sections of this report relating to policies and statistical mapping, it is not possible to determine the exactly number of firms and employed persons involved in the crafts industry, nor the global turnover of these economic activities. As already specified, this difficulty derives from the lack of a shared, formal definition of 'craft enterprise' among the Member States of the EU. Due to this absence, a comparison among national craft industries seems impossible, resulting in a lack of knowledge that risks affecting the EU policymaking process. As a matter of fact, within the EU policy framework, the specificities of craft enterprises are flattened out into the general regulatory framework that addresses SMEs. According to some informants, due to this condition, the States whose economic structure is based *precisely* on craft enterprises would be damaged in terms of policymaking. As one regional policymaker recalled:

... we cannot expect the EU to do anything for the Italian crafts industry. More realistically, what one might expect is that Europe takes into consideration the features and specificities of all those national economies that are based on a massive presence of craft enterprises [...] it's up to national governments, to be good at representing and pushing this production model in the EU institution. More than a problem of the EU, it seems to me a problem of representation capacity on the part of national authorities. (interview no. 27)

The problem of measuring the impacts of crafts reverberates at the national level. Artisans and craft enterprises are involved in several industries and sectors, and it is not possible to determine exactly how much they contribute to each of them. The case study offers proof of this difficulty. The leisure boating industry involves a large number of craft enterprises, and only a minor proportion of them – those that participate in the building of ships and boats – are clearly identified with NACE codes who prove their contribution to the maritime economy. As for the other enterprises – those engaged in design, production, assistance, maintenance, and repair activities – it is not possible to clearly establish their precise impacts in the boating industry: these enterprises do not benefit from dedicated NACE codes. Therefore, estimates and analyses of craft enterprises can only be approximate. The relevance of this issue in terms of policymaking seems self-evident.

Another remark relates to the protection and reproduction of artisans' know-how. There is no doubt that craft enterprises are a bulwark of the reproduction of the skills and traditional know-how that constitute one of the critical assets of Made in Italy productions, especially in the boating industry. Despite this awareness, the artisans interviewed complained of a sense of abandonment by the institutions, which is not sufficiently committed to providing artisan companies with tools to pass on these skills. The informants complained that artisanal skills are disappearing and raised a precise alarm: by losing artisanal know-how, one of the distinctive elements of Italian competitiveness risks disappearing. This view did not seem to be shared by all of the actors interviewed. According to a regional policymaker, *"the battle to protect these skills may not necessarily be fought"* (interview no. 27). As claimed by the informant, global economic trends indicate the need for a dimensional growth of micro and small craft enterprises and their primary concern should be *"to become medium and then large enterprises"* (interview no. 27). Thus, the issue of the reproduction of traditional know-how should be minimised because *"it is not so true that artisan skills cannot be replicated. Our companies are full of foreign workers who, little by little, are learning traditional skills. These workers demonstrate that these skills can be passed on easily"* (interview no. 27).

The investigated production network seems to be positioned exactly between these contrasting visions. On the one hand, there is a will not to give up the traditional production model, along with the commitment to reproduce it; on the other hand, there is the appeal of the industrial transformation, which would reduce or radically transform the role and function of artisans. For now, focusing on *"the obsession for details and quality, which would not be possible in industrial productions"* (interview no. 4), the brand that initiates the network seems to have decided where to stand. As for the future, given the evolution of the industry and *"the need to produce bigger boats"*, the brand is urged to seek suppliers equipped with a mentality that

... our artisans, probably, do not have. At that moment, it will be necessary to look for other workers, always with high quality, who are better with bigger productions. The artisans who work with us now are very good, but perhaps they will no longer be suitable. We will have to find others as good as them: it is not a mission impossible. (interview no. 17)

In conclusion, it seems that artisans must be ready to give up the idea of their irreplaceability. Moreover, it seems that they should be prepared to accept the challenges requested by the general transformations of the industry (e.g., dimensional growth, upskilling, and digitisation), proving that they could continue to make the difference. This is not taken for granted but it would be crucial in terms of creation and capture of value. The leisure boating industry, described as a *"little paradise for artisans"* (interview no. 13), seems to be nearing the end: artisans should craft new ways to carve out their own space.

3.3 Case 2: Konsthantverkarna

Case study 2 is about Konsthantverkarna, a membership-based organisation that gathers approximately 90 different craftspeople who work with different materials and are from different parts of Sweden. The case was chosen as it is an organisation of 90 independent craftspeople that follows the market governance model identified earlier in this report. By examining the reasons for why and how the craftspeople became involved in this organisation, we could unpack several craftsperson production networks as well as the organisations.

Case study 1 (Section 3.2) showcased the complex production network of artisanal yacht manufacturing in Liguria, Italy – a nautical district with a long and deep history of artisanal boat manufacturing. The second case study investigates another part of the craft industry – namely artistic crafts. The artistic crafts are a wide industry containing craftspeople who work with artistic intent in a variety of different materials, ceramics, wood, silver and metal, textiles, and glass, to mention just a few (European Commission, 2017). Most artistic craftspeople are self-employed or work in SMEs. We identified an organisation of artistic crafts where several self-employed craftspeople hold membership. The organisation is one of Sweden's oldest craft associations, founded in 1951, and has about 90 members. The organisation is centred around the running of a shop and gallery space in central Stockholm, where members can display, exhibit, and sell their work. It is a well-known crafts association in Sweden and in Stockholm, with a reputation for high-quality craftspersonship. By studying the organisation and interviewing its members, we obtained insights into the production network of the organisation as well as into several craftspeople working with a variety of different materials.

The basis of the analysis was to follow a project's creation, through production and distribution, until it reached a final consumer and was archived. In this case, many projects are undertaken simultaneously, often by the same craftsperson, due to the complex nature of the network. To capture this complexity of the artistic crafts world, the main analytical focus was on understanding the different types of projects that occur, following the production stages. The project in this case comprised several smaller projects, which were lifted as examples so as not to lose some of this complexity. Other projects, such as the development of exhibitions, are not the main focus of the analysis, but rather the project is understood as the crafted objects developed by the craftsperson.

This section of the report contains the results of the fieldwork undertaken, by first identifying and outlining the production network as well as the actors, locations, and phases present in the network (Subsection 3.3.1). Following this outline, the relationship between the different actors is examined, focusing on the power relations (Subsection 3.3.2). In the successive subsections, the governance model of the case study is presented (Subsection 3.3.3), as well as its economic, social and cultural impacts (Subsection 3.3.4). Lastly, after the focus on policy implications (Subsection 3.3.6), the key findings are highlighted in a conclusion section (Subsection 3.3.7).

3.3.1 Phases, actors, and locations

3.3.1.1 Actors and Locations

The main actors in the production network of Konsthantverkarna are the members of the organisation. They are mostly established craftspeople, who already had many years of experience before they gained access to the organisation. Access is granted through a jury process where the craftsperson must apply and be evaluated on their previous work, CV, and submitted pieces. Potential members are judged by both invited external judges and selected internal members. Applicants are evaluated on the quality of their work, exhibition history, and higher education. Every year, approximately 20–25 craftspeople apply and two or three are admitted. As the organisation aims to represent many different fields of craftspersonship, it aims to maintain a balance between the fields; for example, if many ceramicists are included one year, admission might be tougher, and the applicant encouraged to apply the following year. Applicants are welcome from the entirety of Sweden, with nearly 50% of members living in the two largest cities of Stockholm and Gothenburg, while the other 50% live in small and medium-sized cities, as well in the countryside, and operate from their respective workshops. Once admitted, a craftsperson will pay a membership fee, which is approximately €1000 depending on the year, as well as a 30–40% commission on all sales made at the shop. The shop, located in the very centre of Stockholm, is operated by an employed curator who has the main tasks of displaying, disseminating, and exhibiting members' work as well as running a social media account and web shop. The shop organises exhibitions both for members and for invited craftspeople. The organisation aims to *"be a leading institution for Swedish artistic craftsmanship and a leading scene for artistic craftsmen"* (interview 1, chair and member), meaning that the barrier to entry is relatively high.

Surrounding this main line of the production network are art associations that attend exhibitions and make purchases in the shop for their associations, museums that buy contemporary artistic craftship for their collections, as well as individual customers. Publicly funded supportive institutions exist, such as the Swedish Arts Grant committee and the Swedish Art's Council, which rewards stipends to active craftspeople as well as for the running of the organisation. Organisations such as Konsthantverkscentrum represent another type of supporting structure, a government-funded organisation that aims to create interest and awareness around artistic crafts, as well as support active professional craftspeople with courses on running a business and web development. Konsthantverkscentrum is also part of an umbrella organisation called the Nordic Network of Crafts Association, which facilitates cooperation between Nordic craft organisations. Most of these supportive and surrounding organisations are located in Stockholm, so even if the artistic craftspeople themselves are geographically dispersed, often working in isolation, having access to Konsthantverkarna means that they have closer access to all of the support structures that come with a central Stockholm location.

Other key actors include educational institutions, with an emphasis on highly prestigious colleges such as Konstfack, Stockholm, and Valands HDK in Gothenburg, which nearly all members have attended, with other schools such as Capellagården and Nyckelviksskolan also being commonly featured on members' CVs. Teaching, sometimes at the same school as they graduated from, is a common way for craftspeople to earn extra income for their projects.

Actors of other creative industries also intersect with the production network of Konsthantverkarna. Interior design magazines, design and furniture stores, restaurants, fashion brands, and other art galleries were mentioned as actors in which the projects – the crafted works – could end up, either directly through Konsthantverkarna or through other channels. Most of sales were inside Sweden's borders, but a majority of the interviewed craftspeople had exhibited or been represented at a gallery abroad, with Japan, the USA, Denmark, the UK, and Australia being among the countries mentioned.

The aforementioned actors provide a rough sketch of the people involved in the production network of Konsthantverkarna, where the operations of running the shop and exhibition space as well as the production of crafted objects are at the centre of the production network. An outline of the activities of these actors throughout the production chain is provided as follows:

3.3.1.2 Phases of the production chain

In this subsection, the structure of the production phase is presented. As the crafted objects seldom have only one distribution phase, and as Konsthantverkarna is only one part of the production network of the members, an overview of the production network is provided. Examples are also presented of objects that have been sold by an artistic project and exhibited at Konsthantverkarna by one of the members, which serves to demonstrate how a work can flow between nodes in the network.

Creation

The creation stage of the crafted objects is conducted by members of the organisation in their own workshops and studios, which are located in various parts of Sweden. The craftspeople are all in relative isolation during this phase, although four of the interviewees reported sharing a workspace with other artists and artistic craftsperson – either through a building owned by an organisation or through friends. The creation phase was often described as indrawn, where they return to previous works and develop working ideas further. The shop and the organisation have no requirements or wishes for the members regarding what they can produce; here, admitted crafters are free to create and design objects following their own expression, as long as the objects are delivered to the store.

New information about current trends as well as new ideas are mostly found through social media, predominantly Instagram. A smaller proportion of the interviewees also mentioned exhibitions as a key place for inspiration for new ideas for their own artistic expression. Contrary to the creation process, which is performed in relative isolation, finding new skills and information is seldom a solitary

experience. Courses and artist residencies are common ways to receive new inspiration. If a craftsperson realises that a skill is required to be developed to realise an artistic aim, they attend courses or artists residencies specifically geared towards that skill. Several interviewees mentioned that travel stipends from the Swedish Art Grants Committee are a key facilitator if participating in courses and residencies abroad. Furthermore, some techniques were described as something that you could only learn at a specific place. For one crafts project that used birch bark in its production, the craftsperson had to travel to the town of Sigtuna, north of Stockholm, as the only professional expert with knowledge of this skill worked there. Seeking skills and new input to further the ideas of past works, the craftspeople seek external influences. Where these interactions occur varies greatly, but seeking out highly specific skills often means travelling to a specific place where that knowledge is embodied. One member explained how *“one can say that you collect information outside, at different places, you get inspired and then you take it home and develop your expression at the homefield”* (Interview 12, member). The craftspeople then bring new ideas and skills back to the workshop and transform these new impressions into their own artistic expressions.

Creation could also occur in contact with a customer or public institution. For example, three of the interviewed craftspeople had produced tableware for high-end restaurants, where the customer was able to have input in the production process and a larger set of objects were created.

Production

The production is also conducted by the craftspeople in their own studios and workshops, which are built around their needs. These objects can either be one of a kind or part of smaller-scale batches. Several craftspeople described a two-tier production, with one being more innovative and artistic – targeted at exhibitions, publicly funded commissions, and art collectors – and one being targeted towards a wider set of consumers. The latter products are more likely to be sold at the shop and in other contexts, while the former products are more likely to be exhibited in the shop or in other galleries. For example, a craftsperson could create highly unique ceramic sculptures driven by artistic pursuits, but also manufacture tableware for a wider audience of consumers. Not all of the artistic craftspeople had this division in their production; some were entirely driven to produce artistic products for exhibitions and some mainly produced towards sales, but both types of production had a space in the store. The craftspeople seldom produce only for Konsthantverkarna; rather, objects are crafted to be sold both at Konsthantverkarna as well as at other nodes or to be used in exhibitions elsewhere. Although production is performed by the craftspeople individually, they also described how they could obtain input on their production through the organisation, which they seldom access in their own workshops. As one craftsperson stated, *“we encourage each other and help each other, give each other advice”* (interview 4, member). To have colleagues who encourage production or who are able to understand the work and give comments is one of the inputs obtained through membership during the production phase.

Finally, to produce the crafted objects, materials and supplies are required, and the acquisition of materials by the craftspeople differs between fields. For the clay and metal used by ceramicists and jewellers, there are one or two large retailers that sell these products in batches for businesses, and most practitioners use these nodes, sometimes buying in batches together with colleagues. Other craftspeople work with recycled materials, or found objects, such as using second-hand books for paper sculptures or scrap metal found in recycling centres. A few others use materials from nature, such as birch bark.

Distribution

When members have completed objects, they deliver them to the shop themselves. Different from most other membership-based organisations for artistic craftship, Konsthantverkarna has a full-time curator who organises the inventory, manages the store, and coordinates exhibitions, which was seen as a clear advantage and made several of the craftspeople prioritise membership of Konsthantverkarna over that of a local organisation. How the objects are presented is decided by the curator and the sales are managed in the shop. Once a year, the organisation also arranges a members' exhibition where members can jointly exhibit their work. This was said to be one of the benefits of being a member – one always has at least one guaranteed exhibition a year.

The shop has an active presence on social media, mainly through the Instagram account of the organisation, which posts several times a week to highlight work and exhibitions in the shop. This means that the crafted objects delivered to the store can be disseminated further, and it also provides attention to the crafters themselves, as posts could direct traffic to the craftsperson's own Instagram account – increasing visibility for those with active accounts. Noteworthy, although social media is as an important tool for distribution in the shop, and the artistic craftspeople highlighted that it could be used as a valuable tool, the majority did not use social media actively, at least not for posting their own crafts. One interviewee stated the following: *"I am not active on social media [...] I know it is common to sell through social media, but I don't do it. I don't like selling my things actively in that way. It is incredibly luxurious to be able to have them in a store with knowledgeable staff"* (interview 11, member). The work required to have a consistent social media presence is not something that the majority of the interviewees engaged in, and a social media presence was perceived more as something they thought they *should* have or planned to have someday.

The preference for a physical store, rather than an online presence, is critical in this context, which one member described as follows:

I look a bit on social media, but really rather little. No, because I am a person that does not only want to look with the eyes. I want to feel the scent and get more of a full picture. I see that in my own exhibitions too. I mean people look as much with their hands and their fingers as they do with their eyes. Maybe that is also why it so important to be present in Stockholm too. To have a place where you can see and feel. (interview 12, member)

Another member who did engage with social media extensively also highlighted the importance of a physical platform, even when they are available online: *“I know that they find me there [Instagram] because they get in to contact over there and ask where can I see your things in real life? Then I have Konsthantverkarna to direct them to”* (interview 10, member). Having a space for customers to directly experience an object before buying it was perceived as a key feature of craft consumption.

Furthermore, the shop and social media account disseminate crafted objects directly to customers, but many members also highlighted that this was often less important than having access to the central Stockholm location, as having objects available there could lead to further contacts with other types of consumers. The reputation of the organisation draws in related creative fields, something that could lead to larger commissions or projects. Interior magazines were mentioned as one such industry that frequents the shop, buying or borrowing objects for photoshoots. An interview with the artistic crafts section of Nationalmuseum described how they frequented the shop (among other shops) to find contemporary craftship to be representative in the collection, an institution that also gave weight to a CV. Furthermore, art associations organize trips and attend lectures at the shop, often buying art for the association.

It is crucial to note, however, that the distribution at Konsthantverkarna is only part of the crafted objects' distribution. The birch bark project, for example, had been on exhibition before it was given an exhibition space at Konsthantverkarna, and was displayed at an exhibition in Örebro (a mid-sized city in Sweden) a couple of years later. Craftspeople who aim for exhibitions and stipends must exhibit at a variety of places to build their name recognition – making it easier to get more exhibitions, stipends, and clients. Having several points of distribution builds the craftsperson's CV, and being present at more than one node is crucial. For specific fields such as jewellery, being present at international exhibitions, such as Schmuck in München, is of high importance as *“the entire field is there”* (interview 5, member). Other craftspeople who produce crafted objects with a focus on functionality had the most success when making objects for restaurants or commercial retail (e.g., interior decoration shops), where these types of connections could lead to larger sales.

The extent of the distribution phase varied vastly between the interviewed members. Most had their predominant market in Sweden, but nearly all had exhibited internationally and a few were also represented at museums and galleries in other countries, mostly in Europe, but also in countries far away, such as the USA and Japan.

Exchange

The exchange phase at the shop entails the transaction of the crafted goods at the store. This involves not only potential buyers and consumers interested in crafted objects but also various art associations (konstföreningar), which gather people interested in craftspersonship and collectively buy art. Potential customers also include museums, public officials, and related creative fields, such as restaurants, interior decorators, and magazines. These are desirable as they could lead to greater

exposure and larger commissions. Apart from the physical shop, the organisation also has a web shop where exchange can occur, but currently the physical shop is the dominant part of the exchange phase.

As with distribution, it is not only the shop that functions as a space for exchange for the individual craftspeople, who employ several types of nodes for exchange – other shops and galleries, museums, public commissions, and exhibitions all represent alternative exchanges.

Archive

The archive phase has a few main nodes. At the shop, Konsthantverkarna has documented the activities of the organisation since it started in 1951. Here, everything *from “exhibitions, registers, membership registers and the like”* (interview 2, curator) are stored, and 8–10 boxes of material are to be donated to the Stockholm city archive for future research. Still today, the activities of the organisation are documented in a yearly folder, where every craftspeople who exhibits has a section where *“contracts and press releases, copies of the exhibition folder, the resume of the craftspeople and maybe texts by the craftspeople on the exhibition [...] and the sales lists”* (interview 2, curator) are documented and stored.

Moreover, some of the craftspeople also keep some type of documentation, such as photographs of the objects they have sold, but none of them have an organised archive. Although the majority of interviewees used social media to a greater or (typically) lesser extent, when the craftspeople themselves seek ideas for upcoming creations, the social media accounts of other craftspeople are the most referenced source, in addition to returning to older projects.

As mentioned under the creation phase, several craftspeople mentioned different forms of artist residency programmes, either through a course, grant, or invitation from a gallery, to learn new skills. If one needs to learn a new skill, travelling to a place where someone has that skill is important, as skills are not easily attainable at any given place. One craftspeople explained that she had visited Italy to learn specific techniques for how to *“dye the colouring of metals that intrigued me, it is a specific technique and I wanted to learn a lot of different techniques [...] you can’t really learn that in Sweden [...] and not in very many places around Europe”* (interview 4, member, metal). The geographically sticky nature of crafts, as well as how skills are built, means that craftspeople must go to specific places to learn them. Just as craftspeople use experiences from older projects in their new work, such learning experiences point to them functioning as a type of archive themselves. Since skills are trained physically, the archives of experiences and techniques are embodied in these craftspeople, where step-to-step documentation is inadequate for archiving their techniques. This also means that active practitioners are required for skills and techniques to exist.

Lastly, several of the members were represented in a museum, with Nationalmuseum and the Röhsska museum being the most common, which are museums focused on artistic crafts. Some of the members were also represented abroad, such as at the Museum of Arts and Design in New York.

Summary

To conclude this outline of the production network, we found that a range of activities were present for a craftsperson at every stage of the production network. Even though the network at first glance appears simple and straightforward, with craft objects being designed and made by the same person who then transports it to the shop to be displayed and sold, each craftsperson has their own complex production network. Konshantverkarna acts as one node that brings their activities together. These networks contain a multitude of platforms for distribution and a project, be it a series of craft objects, an exhibition, or a unique art piece, can travel through many nodes before reaching a final consumer, museum, or exhibition. *Figure 9* presents a sketch of the production network that highlights how complex a network like this can be.

Figure 7. Case 2: Overview of the production network of Konshantverkarna

3.3.2 Relationships between actors

The production network of the craftspeople at Konshantverkarna is, as showcased, complex with a multitude of different actors interacting. This section highlights the relationships between these different actors. As with the first case study, the focus is on the governance of the network, that is, on understanding which actors influence the structure and function of the network. First, the governance within the network is discussed, followed by a section that details the motivations to join this type of organisation, which is partly due to the reputation that the organisation holds.

3.3.2.1 Governance of Konsthantverkarna

The organisation is governed by a board that is elected yearly at a membership meeting, where all who attend have the chance to apply for positions within the board. The board is responsible for decisions of the running of the organisation as well as for making plans for the future. There are also several working groups that deal with various activities. For example, there is the jury, which is composed of both internal and external craftspeople and makes decisions. There is also an exhibition group that works together with the curator to put exhibitions together. The power structure between members is horizontal, where members can join working groups that interest them or not join such groups at all. One member explained how “[w]e don’t have very clear roles, except a few. We have a chair and a secretary. You can apply to be part of working groups for what that you would like to work with – what you find interesting” (interview 3, member). The level of engagement between members varies significantly; some only visit the organisation as they transport their work to the shop, whereas others take highly active roles within the organisation. Although the power is horizontal, the members who have taken an active role and been in the organisation for a longer time were perceived as having more influence, especially when those members were on the jury. The jury process, as described by those who had experienced it, could be a source of conflict as quality and artistic crafts were understood in different ways between members. The members who were selected also represented the way in which the organisation would continue to develop, thus ensuring that quality being high is crucial for everyone, which could create friction in the selection group and jury. Generally, though, the members seemed to have equal power within the organisation and larger decisions were discussed and made during meetings to which all members were invited. Conflicts arise, but formally members can all influence the decisions of the organisation, even if some craftspeople are perceived to be more influential. Overall, the relationships between members were described as friendly and generous, where advice and information is shared between the craftspeople.

3.3.2.2 Governance of the artistic crafts market: Processes of reputation building

The understanding of the artistic crafts market for these self-employed members shares some similarities to the governance structure of Konsthantverkarna. The market is highly competitive and there is an abundance of active craftspeople, ranging from amateur and hobby production to the highly skilled craftspeople studied here. Therefore, the artistic crafts market is characterised by high barriers to entry, with a concentration of power in those institutions that are influential in how craft products are perceived. For example, having a piece represented at Nationalmuseum can be seen as a sign of recognition and quality, making it easier to gain access to other distribution nodes. This is especially critical for craftspeople who wish to have an artistically driven production, as exhibition spaces are limited. One can apply for a gallery space, but:

... galleries in general rather want to initiate contact, rather than be contacted [...] they get bombarded with queries. That is hard for them to handle so they rather want to do that

themselves. It becomes a bit counterproductive as you need to have exhibitions in order to be visible. You must get into the carousel in order for it to spin. (interview 5, member)

The difference in quality within the artist crafts fields also makes certain institutions more influential in the industry as they produce signs of legitimacy for the craftspeople. Public commissions, galleries, and solo exhibitions were some key actors mentioned that would lift the CV of a craftspeople.

Certain institutions, such as Konsthantverkarna, prestigious art schools, or museums, can give weight to a career. These institutions serve as gate keepers and control the recognition and representation of the crafts field. Getting one's name in front of the eyes and ears of the right gallerists can be crucial as recognition from a well-known one can make other actors interested in that craftspeople's work. Konsthantverkarna is one type of gate keeper as it has *"been the number one artistic crafts gallery. It is difficult to pass through that needle's eye. So for me it has been a stamp of quality to be included. In some way you really are an artistic craftspeople then"* (interview 3, member). Having existed for 70 years and represented some members who *"are like celebrities in their field"* (interview 12, member) meant that the organisation was able to cultivate a reputation as being one of the best platforms for contemporary craftspeople. The national representation was also part of this as the organisation *"welcome[s] members throughout Sweden, because we really want to be number one. The artistic craft shop should be the best of Swedish craftsmanship represented"* (interview 3, member). Being national in scope and having high barriers to entry means that this reputation can be held, giving both the craftspeople and the organisation recognition and legitimacy.

This is also reflected in the sales that occur at the shop. One member stated the following:

I know that – I believe that – more than 50% do not sell enough to cover the costs [of the membership], but still chooses to be in the group. Only because it is status to be in the organisation within one's field. (interview 8, member)

Several of the interviewed craftspeople also experienced this, describing sales as breaking even but with less profits. Belonging to this recognised organisation was enough, as it offered recognition for their work in other parts of their networks. The breadth of the activities at the organisation, in addition to its reputation, meant that other creative networks seeking high-quality craftsmanship were likely to visit this shop.

For craftspeople who are "in" the production network and recognised for their work, the power relations were understood as horizontal. Access to Konsthantverkarna and other institutions was not, and organisations like the one studied, museums, and galleries function as gate keepers with a high concentration of power.

3.3.3 Network type

The typology, as described in the theoretical part of this report, is used to showcase the breadth of different governance models and structures of networks that exist within the CCS. It is a tool for comparing the different case studies, both within crafts as well as between the other industries of the CICERONE research project. For Konsthantverkarna, the local is the most dominant scale, as much of the network is orchestrated by the craftspeople themselves, who are present at every step of the production network. It is the distribution and exchange phases that can be both local and global, depending on the craftsperson at hand and the intermediaries they are involved with. The Konsthantverkarna as an organisation invites craftspeople on both a national and an international scale, and the majority of artistic craftspeople in the organisation have held exhibitions abroad. A smaller percentage also distribute their crafted objects internationally through galleries and retailers. Representation in museums also occurs nationally and internationally, but here the scale of the archive was determined to be local, as the knowledge and start of a new production are always local, and craftspeople travel to others to learn new skills, which are archived at specific places.

Furthermore, the governance structure of this network was perceived to be horizontal throughout, except for the stage of distribution where barriers to entry were considered high, and key gatekeepers (e.g., galleries, organisations, and museums) have the power to determine which products to disseminate or not. Their influence is not present throughout the chain – they have no say in the creation of products, but they can give approval and recognition to products distributed towards consumers. The typology matrix represented below displays the spatial scale of each phase and the governance configuration of the production network. The phases of exchange and distribution are designated as national, as the majority of sales are within Sweden. However, the total reach is global as members are represented in museums and retailers around the world.

Table 8. Case 2: the network's spatial footprint and governance configuration

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation	Creators				
Production	Creators				
Distribution	Consumers	Strategic partners - private		Consumers	
Exchange		Strategic partners - private			
Archiving		Strategic partners - public			
Network level					Horizontal

3.3.4 Dynamics: Changes over time

Although the organisation has deep roots and has existed for over 70 years, having the same baseline idea of representing members who are part of the best artistic craftship in Sweden, certain changes have influenced the shop. One such large change, where it was unclear whether the organisation would be able to survive, was a move from one part of central Stockholm to another around the turn of the millennia. This was due to increasing rents and the availability of a privately subsidised shop in another part of central Stockholm. Here, they lost some of their regular customers who did not understand that the organisation was still operating, or they did not visit the new location regularly. Being embedded in the very centre of Stockholm was perceived as critical by the interviewees, and customers, even though the shop moved less than a kilometre away, were perceived as prone to disappearing as the organisation left its original setting.

Moreover, a few of the informants mentioned some hesitance towards the future and the organisation's ability to attract younger members. The average age of members is relatively high, 61 years as of 2021, and if enough early career craftspeople find other ways to build their careers through the Internet, social media, or collaborations, the function of the organisation would be at risk of disappearing. As the reputation of the organisation is dependent on the high-quality craftship of its members, a loss of members would mean that it would risk losing some of the prestige connected to its name. This would be troubling, not only for the organisation but also for the craft industry in general. As platforms dedicated to high-quality artistic crafts as a unified field, distinct from other types of art, are disappearing, and galleries targeted towards artistic crafts are even fewer in number, the loss of platforms such as Konsthantverkarna would mean less dedicated space for this specific form of artistic production.

The decision to close an art gallery in 2020, namely Gustavsbergs Konsthall, was according to a representative of Konsthantverkscentrum (artistic crafts centre) a hard blow to the artistic craft scene in Stockholm and Sweden. This was because a platform dedicated specifically to contemporary artistic craftspersonship as a unified artistic field was lost. Today, Konsthantverkarna is the only platform in Stockholm that gathers contemporary, highly skilled artistic craftspeople using a broad variety of materials from all over Sweden. If younger craftspeople tended to avoid these types of organisations, it could potentially make the specificity of the artistic crafts field less clear. Some members saw this as worrying, as they perceived value in having the artistic crafts as an artistic field separated from other types of art due to its unique engagement with materials and skill.

3.3.5 Impact

3.3.5.1 Economic impact

The economic impact is difficult to measure for most craftspersonship activities as the industry is a combination of sales, commissions, and subsidies by public agencies, stipends, and teaching activities. Regarding the independent craftspeople themselves, there are 90 members who have been successful in their careers, managing to be self-employed in an industry where clear career paths and secure jobs are often scarce. Every craftsperson interviewed managed their artistic crafts work as a self-employed person, but they differed in how they organised their work and income streams; thus, broad claims about the economic impacts of the case study were difficult to establish. For several members, the sales at the store did not make up for the membership fees, meaning that being a member is a net loss – thus, craftspeople’ motivation to be a member and their beliefs about the importance of the gallery do not concern increased sales. The interviewees who had concentrated their work towards sales, on the other hand, said that sales at the store accounted for a crucial part of their income and that having access to this central Stockholm location was a vital part of their distribution. As such, to understand the economic impacts of the organisation, one should understand that this shop is only part of the production network for these independent craftspeople and that for many its value does not translate to economic revenues directly at the node; rather, being recognised as part of this network is seen as valuable.

Several noted, as mentioned in Section 3.3.1 (“Phases, actors, and locations”), that being a part of this organisation is part of one’s recognition and reputation building, often in the hope that it will bring in other forms of recognition. Being the only platform in Stockholm that represents high-quality artistic craftship from several different materials makes this node attractive for other creative industries. Furthermore, it functions as a gateway to other forms of distribution, such as interior magazines finding their way to the shop to buy or borrow objects for their work. Other such institutions could be museums. One interviewee, employed at one of the larger museums with a large collection of contemporary artistic crafts, described how often just one or two people are responsible for adding relevant pieces to the collection, and that such platforms are involved in scouting for new objects. The interviewee added the following:

You can’t avoid it, we see mostly what happens in Stockholm, because it is here that we live and work. We don’t really have a budget to go Gothenburg either. So, our scouting is in this city – it is limited. That doesn’t mean that we don’t have any idea of what is going on outside of Stockholm, but still. (Interview 8, museum representative)

The economic impacts of membership might not always be as visible as sales in the shop, but it can have economic impacts in other parts of the craftsperson’s production network through exposure to other types of institutions.

Most of the craftspeople interviewed had additional sources of income, as labour was often decidedly precarious:

It's a pretty tough world where I always have many streams of income [...] so I make sure to broaden myself as much as possible, both through knowledge but also through the client base so that you have many things to earn money from. (Interview 8, museum representative)

Having a second (or a third or fourth) source of income was perceived as a sensitive topic for most craftspeople, although the majority had other income streams apart from their craft. One craftspeople, who had studied to become an engineer later in life, explained that

for a while I thought it was embarrassing to admit that you were an engineer too. Now I have come around to it. It was a way to get some normalcy with a proper job and a steady income [...] but I always had the firm going. I think it is very common, to both have your craft business, and then have a second income on the side. (Interview 4, member)

Having additional streams of income was not only viewed as negative. Income from artistic crafts is often low, and additional streams of income, often through teaching, mean that artistic craftspeople can be freer in their work, not only concentrating on making objects that would sell well.

One member, who had received work grants from the Swedish Art Grants Committee and was now able to live off the sales of their crafts, however, highlighted that at the beginning of his career,

the work grant was key for me to continue to work this way. If I had not received it I would not have been able to do as good of a job and I would have had to take an side job.. maybe not leave [the crafts] entirely, but I would not have been able to create in that amount [...] That I received those stipends was key for me to be able to continue, that and living cheaply. (interview 15, member)

Work stipends and grants were key aspects for many of the craftspeople, as they mean that for a set period the recipient can work without the stress of not knowing whether sales were going to be enough. Moreover, they dedicate much time to writing applications for such funding, even if “*nine out of 10 times you do not get it*” (interview 11).

The organisation itself is dependent on subsidies from the Swedish Art's Council to exist, which funds, together with the membership fees and commissions, the running of the shop and gallery space as well as the one to two employees who manage them. Economic impacts are difficult to determine as the main motivations of the craftspeople are seldom financial, but rather an artistic exploration of their materials. Most participate in other networks, particularly in organising courses or participating in teaching at colleges or universities; thus, they offer value in other networks due to their expertise within their chosen material. The economic impact of Konstantverkarna is, although difficult to estimate, not limited to the specific shop but also extends to other networks as well.

3.3.5.2 Social impact

The artistic craft industry is characterised by self-employed labour, often in precarious working situations. The shop employs a full-time curator and a part-time sales manager who manage the operations of the store, which is uncommon in artistic craft organisations in Sweden. Most of the interviewed craftspeople mentioned that this was an important factor in them choosing to become, and remain, members. All other organisations of this type in Sweden require members to work a set number of hours in the shop, which took hours away from where they could have been active in their studios, or in side-projects. This means that the relatively high fees of the organisation were considered manageable as membership allowed them more time to focus on their core business. The organisation thus not only provides stable employment for one person but also creates a node of distribution where crafters are allowed to focus more of their time on their main work, instead of working pro bono in another membership shop. Having a staffed node of distribution was perceived to influence the working conditions of the craftspeople.

As the craftspeople in this case study are all self-employed, with different forms of income streams, the organisation also offers a type of social network where they can access colleagues and information exchanges. Apart from the organisation Konsthantverkscentrum, a state-funded organisation that offers advice to their 700 members on matters such as social media, applying for stipends, or gallery advice, relatively little information exists on how to build a career within the industry. These craftspeople, most of whom are further along in their careers, having established a reputation through a history of exhibitions, representations at museums, and public commissions, create a network of information exchange. In an industry where the path to building a financially viable career is littered with challenges, having a network that not only lends reputation but is also available to exchange information is seen as valuable for craftspeople. The social aspect of having colleagues was another benefit, as the craftspeople often work in isolation in their studios and workshops, receiving little feedback on their work. Membership ensures not only information inputs on galleries or available stipends but also feedback on one's work from other highly skilled craftspeople, which are part of the social impacts of the network.

Moreover, the interviewees expressed that there is a sense of cooperation within the artistic crafts field. Even though it is marked by high level of competition, where there is very limited space for the artistic craftsperson, there is a sense of cooperation between the different actors and institutions: *"My opinion is that the actors within the artistic crafts field have a rather kind and helpful relationship to one another, and that includes the galleries that are not membership organisations but also private actors"* (Interview 2, curator). Even though the work itself is rather isolated, through networks such as Konsthantverkarna, craftspeople can access colleagues and forms of communication between members. It also offers a sense of belonging to the artistic crafts market and an identity of belonging to a wider field. As one member jokingly stated, *"I do not participate in religion or in sports – I'm part of Konsthantverkarna"* (Interview 1, member).

Between Konsthantverkarna and other membership organisations, there is also cooperation. For those organisations located in direct proximity to the shop, having exhibitions simultaneously or having exhibitions in common was one strategy that they kept in contact about. Furthermore, when there are arranged city wide activities such as an “night of the arts” or Stockholm Craft Week⁷⁹, communication occurs between organizations, that ranges from what activities they arrange to how best to attract visitors. Seeking government grants is also something that organisations guide each other through, even though there are a limited number of government grants. As one interviewee put it, “[o]f course we all want to sell the most and the best. But at the same time we are in the same boat” (interview 2, curator). The competitive market of the artistic craft industry means that the craftspeople are able to build strategic relationships of support, both by participating in organisations and through cooperation between organisations, which seems to intensify during periods of struggle. *‘There are about 40 unique membership organisations in Sweden that are of different sizes [...] now that we all struggle a bit during Corona these networks [between organisations] have gotten new life’* (interview 2, curator). Through the pandemic, cooperation has intensified as actors struggle to keep organisations afloat.

The social impact of the organisation and others like it is not only in the provision of a space for selling craftspeople’s work. The organisation also contributes to their working conditions positively, as they receive new channels of information and support and provide a network of colleagues who can offer feedback on their work as well as a sense of identity.

3.3.5.3 Cultural impact

Perhaps the most critical impact of the network, both from the independent craftspeople’s perspective as well as the wider perspective of the Swedish artistic craft scene, is the cultural impact of the organisation. Although many of the interviewees struggled with whether to define themselves as artists or artistic craftspeople, having a dedicated space that gathers a multitude of different materials means that the organisation is one of very few platforms representing artistic crafts and the niche of deep artistic and material knowledge contained in the artistic craft industry. Much of the discomfort with the label “artistic craftspeople” was attributed to the fact that there is a small market, with no real distinction between hobbyists and professional artistic craftspeople, and some of the interviewed members were looking to expand into art galleries. Other members expressed a frustration over how the material knowledge sometimes becomes less important than the artistic expression of the object, as more artistic craftspeople identified more closely with the fine arts than the applied arts, which would be a loss for a specific type of creativity with skill and deep material

⁷⁹ The night of the arts (kulturnatten) is a municipality driven, city wide activity that takes place over one night where different actors in the cultural sector put on event for the public. Stockholm craft week is a multi-day event, where different actors involved in crafts put on activities, exhibitions and talks for the public (for more information on these types of activities, the city wide events have dedicated web pages: <https://kulturnattstockholm.se/?lang=en> or <https://stockholmcraftweek.se/start>).

knowledge being premiered. When asked about the motivation for seeking membership in the organisation, one craftsperson responded as follows:

[P]artly, it is because I think that Konsthantverkarna has a good reputation [...] Mostly it is a kind of quality stamps. You show that you have been through different passages and been admitted through a jury. Being a goldsmith, artistic craftsperson, silver smith, it is the type of profession that has no protection. Anyone can call themselves that in Sweden. [...] If you say that you are an artistic craftsperson you could be the best in Sweden or do some crocheting in front of the TV. (interview 4, member metal)

This marker of expertise, of belonging to some of the best artistic craftspersonship in Sweden, was a recurrent theme in the interviews, where it was mentioned as a motivation for being part of the organisation. Members compared it to being part of “*the national team*” (interview 1, member) or a “*flagship for Swedish artistic crafts*” (interview 12, member). Having a gallery space and shop that clearly separated hobbyists from highly skilled professional craftspeople was seen as crucial as it provided a stamp of quality for the craftsperson. This is also important as it is the only organisation that gathers artistic craftspeople using all materials and from all parts of Sweden. The recent closing (in 2018) of the publicly funded nonprofit Gustavsbergs konsthall – a dedicated artistic crafts gallery located in Stockholm – means that the few dedicated platforms are becoming even fewer. As one interviewee explained, this exhibition hall

was an important place actually. It was. It feels like a great loss from our [institution] as well. We were two publicly funded institutions that that could work for the artistic crafts specifically, and not only as part of ‘design’ or ‘form’. [...] It is a great loss that the field no longer has access to that platform. [...] [P]latforms are missing. Spaces where artistic craftsperson can work [...] there are so many that are incredibly talented, but it can be difficult for them to establish themselves. It is a strong field in Sweden, but of course we are a small country and it is perhaps the largest area of culture. But a large part holds a very high, international standard. (interview 17, external artistic crafts organisation)

Furthermore, the members had complex networks of production outside of the organisation, but many kept their membership not only to sell but also to be present and included in this high-level set of craftspeople. By having high barriers to entry and a history of talented and well-known craftspeople, the organisation maintains a dedicated platforms where the artistic craft is front and centre, while simultaneously ensuring that the organisation is considered highly skilled. The closing of the artistic crafts exhibition hall in 2018 meant that this platform is the only one in Stockholm that concentrates on high-level artistic craftspersonship using different materials, on a national scale, in one singular gallery space. For the independent craftsperson, this means that they have year-round access to disseminate their objects in a central Stockholm location as well as a guaranteed yearly membership exhibition, with the possibility of further solo exhibitions. Even though the members reported there being many members who did not receive any revenue from the shop, being present at a central

Stockholm location in a sector with gallery representation and exhibitions was seen as key in establishing recognition and reputation. Seen from the perspective of the artistic craft industry, this also becomes critical. Having a dedicated platform for high levels of artistic craftsmanship is unique, and the shop and gallery space are one of few spaces where national artistic crafts are on display together as a specific form of creative production. Konsthantverkarna is thus not only a strategic choice made by the individual craftsperson but also an important platform that promotes and showcases high-quality artistic crafts, ensuring that there is at least one such platform in the cultural sector of Stockholm.

3.3.6 Policy implications

This artistic crafts organisation was chosen as it represented the market model of governance identified in the literature review of this report, where an artistic craftsperson is responsible for the production network from creation to archiving. It quickly became apparent that these craftspeople's networks are not simple or straightforward but rather complex, where craftspeople produce crafted objects towards several different distribution channels simultaneously. The artistic arts market is limited and competition is high, meaning that many artistic craftspeople end up in precarious labour situations and are not able to live off their work, but instead take secondary forms of employment. Building a reputation is key for building an artistic niche as well as gaining access to platforms for distribution. Public institutions are in many ways key in the network, both through grants and stipends that keep the organisation operating, but also through providing platforms for distribution. Some key policy implications found in the case are presented in the following paragraphs, highlighting issues from the perspective of the actors as well as policy interventions that were helpful to them.

3.3.6.1 Labour precarity, networks, and entrepreneurial skills

Labour precarity was a common theme among the artistic craftspeople, where most divided their time between their artistic craft business and secondary flows of income, mainly through keeping courses, from work grants and stipends or through secondary employment. Secondary flows of income were perceived as a way to be secure income, allowing the craftsperson to pursue more artistically driven forms of production rather than focusing on pieces that were more commercial in nature, and also as something that got in the way of their main form of production. One interviewee mentioned that he *“work[ed] 150%, 75% at a restaurant and 75% as a ceramics teacher”* (interview 11, member), and he then worked additionally in artistic craft production. Noteworthy, these artisans were in many ways successful within their respective fields, having extensive careers and representation – at organisations such as Konsthantverkarna as well as at international museums and galleries – and had lengthy lists of exhibitions. Membership of the organisation was seen as belonging to a highly skilled set of artisans, and even in this cluster of active artisans, income derived from the crafts often requires supplementation.

One observation made in this case, where the number of interviews might not have been sufficient to make an absolute statement, is that the artisans who did not have secondary employment nor were applying for grants were those who had entered networks of other sectors. One textile artist had worked within the fashion industry for years, which provided a higher income, and several ceramicists produced larger sets of tableware for restaurants. This can be seen as an indication of how producing artistic crafts for sectors other than the artistic crafts market could be a way to facilitate income from artistic crafts. Here, advice and networking activities could be suggested from a policy perspective, together with educational efforts in entrepreneurship and finding avenues for artistic crafts outside of the industry.

Building networks and developing entrepreneurial skills, which often are not taught at higher artistic education institutions, such as photography or an online portfolio and social media presence, were themes that the organisation Konsthantverkscentrum already works with. This is to build a craftsmanship market where craftspeople can access better resources for such skills as well as a wider skill set in the distribution of their productions. According to the interviewee from this organisation, these courses were popular and appreciated efforts that the organisation would like to keep developing. The online format that was forced due to the pandemic was also key here as the courses became easier to access to craftspeople outside of Stockholm.

3.3.6.2 Work grants, stipends, and artist residency programmes

Even though networking and entrepreneurial skills might be one way to strengthen the workers in the industry, the grants received from public institutions and private associations were described as a key facilitator in the careers of craftspeople. One member mentioned how, at the beginning of their career,

the Swedish Arts Grants committee working stipend was key for me to continue to work that way. If I had not received it I would not have been able to do as good of a job and I would have had to take a side job.. maybe not leave [the crafts] entirely, but I would not have been able to create in that amount [...] That I received those stipends were key for me to be able to continue, that and living cheaply. (interview 15, member)

Receiving work grants, which often last a year, allowed the craftspeople to develop their skills and expression with dedication. Similarly, knowledge exchange through artist residency programmes was described as a valuable contribution to craftspeople' work. Grants provided for travelling and taking courses abroad led to further engagement with skills of the craft, at times not accessible in Sweden, as well as to wider, international connections and networks. This was also highlighted by Konsthantverkscentrum, where the lack of export possibilities or help regarding the widening of networks abroad could be better facilitated.

Grant applications were also often considered time consuming and at times confusing, and few could answer whether they knew on what basis they were judged on. Most applications go unfunded according to the interviewees, who expressed frustration regarding the application system:

I do not have the energy to care. I do not have the energy to spend a whole evening trying to write together an application and explain what you have done. With applications it always is the way that you have to write something new. Of course you can look at older applications and use pictures and those types of things [...] you have to write, write applications for stipends, applications for public art, commissions and give a lot of ideas. It is all too difficult to do all of those things. I am very fortunate that I have not had to do those things, except for exchanges and travel grants'. [...] 'I have stopped applying because I do not have the energy. I do not care to apply anymore. And the stipends are like 20 000 crowns [roughly 2000 euros] or something. That is a monthly rent for me. It is not worth it, I cannot be bothered. (interview 14, member ceramics)

Although grants are offered, the complicated process and time consumption in regard to the potential supplemental income were seen as frustrating barriers. Grants and public commissions were generally considered to be key, and a strong basis to build a career upon, especially in early career stages, where the craftsperson has not yet developed their expression, skill set, and reputation. The process of applying, however, was often understood as confusing and time consuming.

3.3.6.3 Preserving platforms for the artistic crafts

A final policy implication is that the artistic craft industry is a unique type of creative production, which is often categorised together with other forms of art and design. Its unique attention to material skill and knowledge can make it harder to gain access to the platforms of the fine arts, which are often dedicated to purely artistic works, with less attention paid to the material nature of the object. As of today, the studied organisation Konstantverkarna is the only platform that represents highly skilled contemporary craftsmanship on a national scale. Presenting as a unified, specific type of artistic expression, with its breadth of materials, the organisation functions as a defining platform for what is to be understood as high-quality craftsmanship. Having dedicated platforms specifically geared towards the craft industry is important, both for increasing interest in the production of artistic crafts and for artistic crafts as a field to be appreciated as a unique and distinct form of artistic expression.

3.3.7 Final remarks

The artistic craftspeople studied in this case work in an acutely competitive market, where artisans have chosen to be part of a larger membership-based organisation in central Stockholm, operating a shop and gallery space dedicated to highly skilled artistic crafts. Although the case was selected due

to its governance model, where craftspeople are responsible for the production network from creation to archiving, the production network that we found was actually a myriad of interconnecting networks. The organisation aims to represent some of the best artistic craftsmanship in Sweden and does so on a national scale. By accepting members who were highly skilled through a jury process and keeping the barriers to entry high, the organisation is able to promote this reputation. The reputation of the organisation is also a key driver for members to join, as it becomes a “stamp of approval” as well as allows access to craft institutions in Stockholm. The reputation of the shop also means that it is a place where production networks of other creative sectors, such as interior decoration or restaurateurs, visit if they are looking for artistic crafts.

The governance model of the case exhibited a horizontal power distribution throughout the chain, where craftspeople influence and control the entirety of the production network, except for the distribution phase. Here, a number of gatekeepers select which crafts to exhibit, buy, reward grants to, or commission. To be facilitated into these nodes, craftspeople need to produce highly skilled and artistic works that would help them build an artistic reputation and thus gain access through more gatekeepers.

Lastly, the organisation today is the only platform where nationally sourced, contemporary, and highly skilled crafts, from a large variety of materials, are represented in Sweden, meaning that they are also part of defining what artistic craftsmanship is in Sweden today.

3.4 Case 3: Swedish glass making

Case study 3 focuses on a vertically integrated governance model, where one larger firm produces the design, crafts the product, and disseminates it within the same larger company. The selected company is a glass manufacturer that produces craft in traditional forms of production, by hand producing blown glass and cast glass, as well as glass painting and etching. It is located in a region dominated, both now and historically, by a glass manufacturing cluster.

The third case study for the craft industry was studied as an additional, smaller case. It is a glass manufacturing firm located in southern Sweden. This glass factory produces glass using traditional forms of manufacture, with a factory production that has existed for over 100 years, although with variations in the types of enterprise. In its current form, it has operated as a family firm since 1988.

The case study is located in Glasriket, which translates to “the Kingdom of Crystal”, an industrial agglomeration located in southern Sweden that consists of four municipalities: Emmaboda, Lessebo, Nybro, and Uppvidinge. The area has been Sweden’s largest producer of glass, with an emphasis on traditional methods of production, and only traditional forms of production remain today (e.g., casting and blowing). The Kingdom of Crystal is a self-proclaimed name, coined in the late 20th century, as large-scale production started to off-shore to low-income countries and tourism became an increasingly important part of the area’s economy. The glass industry has dominated both the landscape and the employment industry, and today it is still a vital part of how the region understands itself, especially in marketing. Today, 13 active glass manufacturers remain, with a number of smaller glass studios and independent workers living and participating in the cluster. Sweden’s only glass-making school is located here, and the four municipalities work together to give the different glass companies platforms to exchange information and actively promote the area as a tourist destination. The firms operating in the area are a mix of smaller and larger companies, with the New Wave Group owning the brands Orrefors and KostaBoda, which have been the largest producers of Swedish glass and, although manufacturing has been off-shored, still represent the brands most closely associated with “Swedish glass”. There are also several freelance glassblowers and smaller studios, as well as small and medium-sized firms that still have production in the area. The studied glass company is one such factory, employing approximately 18 people (44 before the COVID-19 pandemic) and producing glassware and artistic glass in house.

The industry has deep roots in the area, having existed for almost 150 years. Apart from the original glass factory Kosta, which started production in 1742, most factories opened in the later part of the 1800s. Its evolution into a glass manufacturing region began in its history as an export economy of steel. Increased global competition, where countries such as England upscaled their production using stone coal-driven furnaces, and falling prices of steel and steel products, meant that the industry left the region (Krantz, 1998). What remained was people who were either highly competent at running a

complex industry or highly skilled at working in heavy, smouldering work environment that producing steel at the time entailed. Surrounding the industry were also farmers who produced large amounts of wood, which they had previously supplied the steel factories with. A few glass industries opened and were highly successful, leading to the establishment that would dominate the area and being the principal glass manufacturer of Sweden.

In the first decades of the 20th century, the first crisis of the industry occurred. Lower import prices of glassware and dwindling export markets due to the First World War meant that the industry needed to find other ways to sell its goods. The two largest manufacturers, Kosta and Boda, drew inspiration from the current trends in Swedish industrial design, which advocated “vackrare vardagsvara” (which roughly translates to “more beautiful everyday things”; Paulsson, 1919). In circulation were ideas that the monotony and ugliness of the mass produced should be alleviated with the intervention of artists who designed industrially produced products. In the 1970s, as with many other manufacturing industries, competition from global markets made the glass industry rapidly decrease in size. Together with an increasing use of plastic packaging, the Småland glass industry was cut in half, from approximately 4500 workers to 2000 (Johannisson 2019). Industries that had not adapted to creating objects of a value higher than their utility and that were artistically driven no longer had the means to continue manufacturing. The available old factories started to attract studio artists from other parts of Sweden as well as local glass blowers. Some of the glass industries, such as the studied glass factory, were backed up by the local population, which bought up shares to prevent the factory merging with a larger glass manufacturer and save them from bankruptcy.

The 1990s saw additional manufacturing close down or smaller factories merging with larger ones, a process that continued until 2008, when the last large-scale mass-manufacturing plant was closed down. Glass production – in numbers – has declined, but the region is still an active glass manufacturing region. The glass manufacturing that now exists in Småland is now mainly artistically driven and markets itself as such. Instead of mass-manufacturing, a number of new actors and investments have started to appear. For example, in 2011 a new gallery and museum – The Glass Factory – was opened, showcasing the most artistic segments of new production and a rich historical record. It is the only established glass museum to this day. Older factories have also been converted into studios and a new set of actors has been established. As of 2017 in this area, according to media reports, approximately 200 people were employed in the manual production of glass and glass blowing (Eriksson, SVD, 2019), and 13 factories are open. This does not account for those employed at other parts of the production chain, but it does provide a rough estimate of the number of craftspeople active in the area.

3.4.1 Phases, actors, and locations

In this first part of the case study’s results, the actors and locations as well as the configuration of the production network are outlined (section 3.4.1). This is the first step of the case study analysis, which

then informs the understanding of the relationship between the actors in the network (section 3.4.2), the governance typology of the network (Subsection 3.4.3) the impacts of the case (section 3.4.5), and possible policy implications uncovered in the field work (section 3.4.6).

3.4.1.1 Actors and locations

The main actor and lead firm within this case study is the firm itself. It consists of 18 full-time employees, but prior to the COVID-19 pandemic there were a total of 44 employees. The company's production is design-driven and there is one main designer, the owner of the factory, whose artistic designs comprise the largest part of the production. The company also invites guest designers to create designs and form for the glass, which accounts for a smaller part of the production. Additionally, the company produces glass work on commission, particularly for churches, as well as some glass products for industry use. Craftspeople make up the majority of the staff, working both with warm glass through glass blowing and glass casting as well as with cold glass – they make etchings and are particularly known for their glass painting. This is done within the domains of the factory, and no part of the production line is off-shored, but rather remains in-house. There is also a sales and distributions team, which is responsible for customer contact and marketing.

The firm disseminates its goods directly from the factory in a factory shop, targeted towards local tourists who visit the region and its traditional glass manufacturing cluster. Here, tourists can observe, try a traditional form of craftsmanship, and purchase products directly at the site. The factory's products can also be purchased online through the company's own website, retailer websites, as well as through physical retailers throughout Sweden. The company has two flagship stores in Stockholm, which disseminate its products and brands at central Stockholm locations, where international tourists account for a large share of customers.

In addition to the widespread national distribution, the company has a large percentage of their products exported, which are represented in 40 countries from all parts of the globe – its distribution stretches from the USA and Canada to New Zealand and Europe, with the majority of exports going towards East Asia, with the Chinese and – at least before 2022 – Russian markets. The COVID-19 pandemic deeply impacted the factory, mainly due to losses on the export side of distribution, as most retailers of its goods were present in tourist-dependent city districts in Europe and Asia.

To establish and remain in contact with distributors and retailers at these numerous locations, the company utilises agents. These agents are often mediated through Export Sweden, a government agency that exists to aid companies with these types of export questions and has been instrumental in establishing contacts.

The production of glass is deeply embedded in the local rural municipalities of this region of Sweden, which markets itself as the “Kingdom of Crystal”, and the creation and production phase of the

company occur here. Approximately 12 glass factories and studios are active in this small region, with the national glass school being located close to the studied factory. There are also glass museums and a tourism network run by the municipalities of the region. The company and glass manufacturing in Sweden are deeply embedded in the region, with both the infrastructure existing here as well as glass craftspeople being trained and working here. Alongside the cluster of glass industries, there is also a tourism industry, which the glass cluster is a central part of, attracting tourists who bring in a large share of income for many of the companies present.

Sales through tourism are a critical part of the company's revenues, especially since the pandemic, and most of their craftspeople are educated in the localities, either at nearby factories or the national school. After a product has been completed, it is either disseminated in the factory store, online, at retailers, or in concept/flagship stores. In Sweden, the largest flagship store is located in Stockholm, but the company also exports a large proportion of their products.

The spatial footprint is global in span during the distribution and exchange phases, but it is deeply embedded and dependent on the local conditions to produce and create artistic glass products. It is at the local scale that craftspeople are both active and educated, and where the infrastructure to support a variety of glass companies exists. In marketing, the aspect of it being Swedish craftsmanship is highlighted, and the traditional and local histories of the factory are prominently displayed.

3.4.1.2 Phases of production

The aforementioned actors provide a general overview of the different actors present in the network. Below, a sketch is presented of the different stages of production, from a glass product being designed to where it reaches the final customer.

Creation

The design phase is conducted through the established designs of the company, produced by the owner of the company, and which have been a central part of the design and brand of the company since the 1980s. These designs have a specific artistic character that has become synonymous with the factory, focusing on vivid colourful painted glass. There is also collaboration with designers who produce designs for the company, which the company then produces and pays royalties for, taking on the risk of production. Designers often visit the factory and together with the craftspeople take forth a design. Typically, the company reaches out to designers they think are interesting. These can be designers known from larger brands (such as a designer closely related to Marimekko) or smaller designers they consider to have an interesting and strong artistic expression. Occasionally they also take on designs produced by graduate students from the national glass school located in the neighbouring municipality, as the institution tends to collaborate in the studio. They also receive a large number of requests from designers who would like to collaborate with them from all over the world, but these requests are generally less engaged with by the company as they perhaps lack an

understanding of glass production and have the wrong artistic expression. Taking on external designers also presents a large risk for the company, as they do not know beforehand how well the products will sell, and they are the main investor in the production of the designs.

When connecting with external designers, the company tends to seek out less “*blonde, generic*” designs but attempts to “*find people that have strong artistic expression, and maybe are not afraid to make obviously beautiful products, that Swedes perhaps think of as vulgar or not so artsy [...] but we have the international customer and then you want it to be less complicated*” (interview 2, head of communication). One of the interviewees also highlighted how the artistic designs are somewhat fragmented where the owners’ “*artistic glass has a powerful artistic expression. But also makes things that are obviously beautiful, so he has different styles. Our main collection has a more European and also Nordic market. [...] And others have more of an international market*” (interview 2). Bringing in new designers must then appeal to either of these artistic expressions, which was also inferred as sometimes being confusing for customers:

Yes, well always have a bit of a dilemma. We have a catalogue as a tool for our retailers with our full assortment. But really we should have three different catalogues, [highlighting the different types of customers, where] customers looking for our ‘power glass’, do not want to see that we also produce animal motifs because that is not what that person expects. (interview 2)

The company has also worked with large companies such as IKEA, taking forward a design of glass casting, but also with architectural firms, where products through casting can be made more efficiently than blown glass. Having these types of design collaborations and commissions is seen as desirable as these designs “*can be used for more than standing on a drawer, that can be part of a building or a public space*” (interview 2). This interviewee continued as follows: “*[W]e make a lot of specialty projects today, but far less than I would wish – the type of projects where we are contacted and our designers can come up with suggestions*”. This type of “Lego” production would make the company less sensitive to macroeconomic trends, as the main glass collection tends to be decorative and exclusive. The form of Lego production would also, in part, support the artistic glass craftsmanship of the factory and the more artistically driven designs.

Production

When a design has been developed by a designer, either in house or by an external designer, the production process starts. This production process is made completely by highly trained craftspeople and is divided into two steps, namely a warm phase where the glass is blown or cast and a cold phase where the glass can be additionally worked by etching and painting. These two forms of production are increasingly uncommon due to the time required, but the company has made them central parts of their production. The production phase is marked by high levels of risk, especially as the company has a large production of clear glass, where some glass batches become cloudy during the days-long

production process or through visible air bubbles being caught in the material. Each step of the process thus requires expert knowledge, but even so it is not guaranteed that every batch will be successfully produced.

Distribution

Distribution occurs in several different forms. The main form is through tourism, predominantly towards local tourism where tourists visit the factory, where they are able to observe the production process as well as try glass blowing. To reach this group, the company utilises several different channels – such as online marketing on social media platforms, advertisements in local newspapers, as well as participation in the local tourist magazine, which is distributed both locally and to potential visitors in cities like Stockholm. At the different tourist sights of the “Kingdom of Crystal”, the company also displays flyers and posters to encourage visitors to visit the factory.

International tourists also make up a large part of the company’s distribution strategy in Sweden, having two flagship stores in Stockholm. The CEO stated the following:

[O]ur largest market is Sweden, but our products are not Swedish. If you look at the sales contacts in Sweden, it’s retailers – the largest has been the flagship stores, that have been aimed toward tourists. Most were not towards Swedes. Of our Swedish sales, about 50% [before COVID] of that was exported by international tourists exporting in their own suitcase.
(interview 1, CEO)

International tourists in European cities also account for a large proportion, where the company’s products are distributed either by retailers or in concept stores run by independent agents. In these European cities, they also tend to be marketed towards international tourists, mainly those from China and Russia. A shop that was opened in Barcelona just months before the pandemic struck had to close down due to the lack of tourism in the city, although the agent has plans to reopen. Their products are retailed in over 40 different countries by independent retailers, who order the products from a catalogue in which the company presents their entire collection.

Exchange

The exchange phase is fairly straightforward and mainly takes place through various retailers, but also through the online shop. The understanding both from the tourism organisation and the firm is that they have a main customer base of women above the age of 55 years, and the dissemination activities in Sweden are geared towards exchange with these clients. For commissioned products, such as for churches, architecture firms, and other enterprises, exchange occurs as the project is completed.

Archive

The archive phase is the least clear of the phases, where the catalogues and social media outputs function as a type of archive, collecting the commercial output of the company year by year.

Furthermore, the artistic glass produced in the factory is also represented in official archives, such as regional museums. Notable, however, is how much of the archive is stored within the craftspeople' hands. For every project the company undertakes, the staff learn more and become increasingly familiar with the material, which is a type of knowledge that cannot be documented nor learned from descriptions. When a new designer makes designs for the company, he or she typically spends some time at the factory to discuss and try out how ideas are translated into material production.

Figure 8 outlines this production network, where the blue line represents the flow of the products and the yellow line represents the institutional embeddedness. The flow of the products is relatively straightforward, going from creation to production and distribution through the factory and a few key agents. The complexity of the network is within the institutional embeddedness that is required for this production network to occur.

Figure 8. Case 3: Outline of the production network

3.4.2 Relationships between actors

Now that the production network has been sketched above, outlining the production network, its actors, and its location, this section dives into the relationship between actors. Understanding the governance of the network, that is, which parts of the network hold influence over other parts, is key to understanding the configuration of the network. Relationships with other actors in the cluster and in the tourism industry are also briefly discussed.

3.4.2.1 Governance and risk management

The main node of governance that influences the entirety of the production network is the company itself. The financing and all of the risks associated with artistic production are shouldered by the firm. The firm decides which designs are worth the risk and the different forms of projects they wish to engage with, and it owns the entirety of the production process. It is a family-owned company and the owner has been active and owned the company since the 1980s. He is also the head designer and his artistic output has become synonymous with the brand. The company receives far more requests for collaborations by designers from all over the world, but they are able to choose the designs they have confidence in producing. Producing a new set of designs is risky, as if the products do not sell well, the cost of production is placed completely on the company. This means that designers are often required to produce sketches and models for a smaller sum and then receive royalties on the sold products (designer 1). Although the financial risk is placed on the company, this can also mean that designers receive very little for the amount of work they invest in the design process (designer 1). How designers are compensated depends on their skill – if they can produce models of their work instead of only sketches, their initial compensation will be higher. The level of compensation between the company and designer is determined through dialogue between the partners, but as the company is the financial risk taker, its words seem to weigh heavy on the final decision (designers 1 & 2).

Apart from the creation stage, distribution and contact making with retailers are also coordinated by the sales and marketing team within the firm, which locates and keeps in contact with the independently run concept stores, as well as with the wholesalers, retailers, and commissions for larger products. The company is a central node that is vertically integrated, and it reaches all other parts of the production network, being involved from the design phase to the distribution and archive phases. The relationships between agents, distributors, and the firm seemed to be based on trust, but it was difficult to determine which actor assumed the largest risk.

3.4.2.2 Competition and collaboration within the glass cluster

Having a dense network of glass manufacturers means that the region is both competitive and collaborative. One of the interviewees, who had lived most of his life in the surrounding area, understood there to have been a shift away from strong competitiveness, where competition had been *“terrible and almost as a type of fiendship, where you could really feel that there was a strong competition, with no collaboration, but rather a divide and concur situation, where larger companies bought up the smaller ones”* (Interview 1, CEO). The CEO continued to describe how this cutthroat competition had started to wane, and now when there are not as many glass manufacturers left as there once were, collaborating would be more beneficial as the type of production has changed: *“We don’t have a history of exchanging information. It has been every man for himself. We need to change that, it’s not good for the future”*. This sentiment seemed to be shared within the glass cluster, and the company had plans to bring their staff on a field trip to a nearby glass factory to be inspired and

build contact between the two firms. The municipality-driven tourism organisation has also worked hard to facilitate communication between the different glass firms – as well as with other actors in the locality – to promote the glass industry and its production to tourists and facilitate the region to further the tourist industry. As not so many of the original glass manufacturers remain, there is a sense of security that they have a well-functioning brand as well as an awareness of how tourism has become imperative to the region and the survival of the industry, and where closer collaboration can help spur this industry on.

3.4.2.3 The relationship with tourism in the area

As the mass production of glassware has gradually left the area through outsourcing, traditional methods and artistic intentions have become all the more important within both the cluster and the firm. Alongside the closing of factories, a tourism industry has taken shape, where tourists seek to experience the traditional manufacturing methods of days gone by as well as experience high-quality artistic craftsmanship. To facilitate this type of growth, other industries have become more established within the area. The firm participates in these activities by conducting guided tours of the factory as well as offering the opportunity to try different forms of glass making, primarily blowing. The firm advertises itself in regional newspapers as well as creates awareness of the factory through posters at touristic sites. The firm also participates in the magazine distributed by the tourism organisation, both locally (within a two-hour drive) and to addresses in Stockholm, which they target as potential clients. These are large in scale and 140 000 magazines are printed, 40 000 of which are distributed to households around Stockholm and the others in the local area. Apart from these engagements, it was difficult to read how deep the collaboration is between the organisation and different actors in the location in terms of attracting and providing experiences for tourists. They do, however, keep an active forum where 12 factories and smaller glass studios participate by meeting to discuss potential activities. The main conflict for the tourism organisation that stands in the way of developing marketing and cooperation is financing from the municipalities. Many of the activities are financed by the factories themselves (such as the magazine), but there is very little financing for common projects; thus, firms mostly only finance projects towards themselves, and the municipalities take little responsibility for the common activities. The will to co-operate is there, but the funding is at times lacking.

3.4.3 Network type

The typology, as described in the theoretical part of this report, is used to identify the different network types in the case studies of the CICERONE research project. It is to be understood as a tool that helps to break down the breadth of different governance models and structures of networks that exist within the CCS, and as a tool that will benefit comparisons between the different case studies, both within crafts and between the other sectors of the CICERONE project. For the artistic glass

factory, the local scale is the dominant scale, as the network is governed by a lead firm – the factory itself. It influences the activities at every stage of the production network. The distribution phase is local, national, as well as global as they sell their glass products locally at the factory, nationally in their flagship stores, and globally through retailers and agent. It was designated as global, as a large portion of their products are exported and are, at least before the pandemic, one of the larger sources of income. Creation is predominantly local, working with the designs of the owner, as well as national and global through external designers. It was designated here as national, as designers are sourced both from in-house, but also from a predominantly national level. Production and archiving were the two stages that were only local as all production was made onsite.

The governance structure of this case was perceived to be marked by a lead firm – the factory – throughout, as it influences every stage of the production network, from deciding which designs to developing ties with agents in other countries to gain access to retailers.

The attributes related the spatial scale and the governance configuration of the investigated case study are summarised in the Table 9.

Table 9. Case 3: spatial scale and governance configuration of the production network

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation	Creators	Creators			
Production	Lead actor				
Distribution	Consumers	Consumers	Consumers	Consumers	
Exchange	Strategic partners- private	Strategic partners- private		Strategic partners- private	
Archiving	Strategic partners-private and public				
Network level					Hierarchical

3.4.5 Impact

The main actor of the production network is the glass firm itself, which acts as a lead firm through all of the phases outlined above. The impacts of the factory on the surrounding area are discussed in this section, highlighting the economic, social, and cultural impacts of the industry.

3.4.5.1 Economic impact

The economic impacts, as for the previous cases, were difficult to measure in hard numbers. Before the COVID-19 pandemic hit, the company was the largest privately owned glass manufacturer with a staff of 44 people, which, as far as enterprises within the craftsmanship industry go, is a large set of workers provided with stable working conditions. The production network is also truly global in scope, even though the creation phase is local and the company is deeply locally embedded; the distribution and exchange phase are global, with a large share of the revenue produced through exports or indirect exports by international tourists, especially before the pandemic.

The reliance on tourism, especially international tourists, is why the company was badly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Today, the number of employees is down to 18 as the loss of tourists in both Sweden and abroad have led to a drop in sales. Losing a craftsperson, with perhaps decades of experience, is detrimental to the company as the skill-intensive form of production, both on the cold and warm side of the glass, is difficult to replace once lost. Decades are required to train a craftsperson fully in the company, even if he or she has a degree. This has made it apparent for the company that they are vulnerable to financial downfalls, and there is a wish to broaden the production in the factory to larger batches of cast glass on commission by larger companies, such as architecture firms. This would ensure a more reliable income in case of an economic recession, where less people invest in decorative and exclusive glass. This type of “Lego” production would then be able to support the artistic output of the factory in times of crisis.

The company is part of a cluster of glass craftsmanship activity in the area, where the four municipalities surrounding the factories have formed a tourist agency and promotion organisation called “The Kingdom of Crystal”. The unique agglomeration of traditional glass manufacturing has made tourism one of the larger sectors in the region, and a symbiotic relationship exists between glass making and the tourism industry. Without tourists, many of the studios and smaller glass factories would not be able to survive, as they account for the main part of their sales; moreover, there would be little of today’s tourism if this unique set of companies did not exist. The municipal organisation collaborates with the factories, inviting them to conversations on the development of the area as a tourist destination. As the glass mass-manufacturing has been completely outsourced to Southeast Asia since 2008, the artistic forms of craftsmanship have gained a stronger position in the region, inspiring an intensification of cultural tourism. Shifting the industrial production from mass manufacturing towards a smaller set of artistically driven glass production means that a new industry in the form of tourism has been able to develop, which supports the artistic glass activities as well as exists through them. This also means greater economic activity in related sectors, such as hotels, restaurants, and outdoor activities.

3.4.5.2 Social impact

Perhaps the clearest social impact uncovered during the case study is tied to this agglomeration of glass industries that have existed in this locale for well over 100 years. The presence of glass has become part of the local identity of the place and is deeply rooted in the region. One interviewee described the off-shoring of the last large-scale manufacturing 14 years ago as “*still painful memories for many*” (interview 1, CEO), as both pride and identity are tied to being part of the “Kingdom of Crystal”. This is also clear, historically, when understanding previous crises that have struck the glass industry in the region. The company has been through many crises in the past, notably in the 1970s when it declared bankruptcy together with three other companies and was subsequently bought up by the largest glass manufacturer. This glass manufacturer wanted to close the case factory, but the surrounding village, consisting of 104 people at the time, clubbed together and invested enough money to keep it operational. How these types of social initiatives would occur today is not clear, but it emphasises the deep cultural and social significance of the glass industry in the area and larger region – which it has had for a long time. The Kingdom of Crystal is not only a manufacturing or tourism area but also something that gives the region a sense of identity.

The only glass school that provides an education for glass craftspeople is located in a nearby municipality. The principal of this school also emphasised that the glass industry was seen as socially important by local politicians, where municipalities add extra funds to keep the school going but receive no state support for keeping this craftsmanship skill alive. The municipalities are quite small, and the principal emphasised the importance of keeping them interested in glass crafts as otherwise the school would simply not be able to exist, and with it the largest pool of workers for the different glass factories and studios. For such a small municipality to invest in such an expensive education (glass manufacturing is an expensive form of craftsmanship) also showcases how deeply embedded the glass industry is within the local region, providing both identity and pride (sources: representatives from the national glass school and the tourism organisation).

3.4.5.3 Cultural impact

The third and final form of impact identified in these reports is how the form of manufacturing and the skills required to make these products are becoming increasingly rare in Sweden, as large-scale manufacturing of glass production has been outsourced over the past few decades. The fact that the company has these highly skilled craftspeople who work in a range of techniques that are often excluded from mass-manufacturing, such as glass painting and etching, means that the company acts as a type of preserver of a skill that, if not kept alive, would be forgotten. The successive change from a purely manufacturing and mass-manufacturing–based cluster that the region originally was towards a more artistic and cultural tourist-driven cluster also means that these traditional forms are increasingly being used to innovate new forms of aesthetic glass production. The main collection of the studied company, with its emphasis on the head designer and its original aesthetic expression,

was already indicative of this change. As there is no longer any large-scale manufacturing of glass products, the production of glass within the region has become increasingly focused on artistic and innovative expressions of glass craftsmanship, while simultaneously being able to market itself to international tourists as “traditional Swedish craftsmanship”. The main cultural impact of this case is this combination of the ability to produce innovative and artistically driven glass products while still maintaining the traditional craft skill.

3.4.6 Policy implications

This smaller case study was chosen as an example of a vertically integrated governance model, where there is a clear lead firm that influences every step of the production process. This was an accurate understanding of the governance model of the case, where the firm influences every production phase from creation to archiving. External actors in the region were vital components in the production network, facilitating consumption through education and tourism. Through the outline of the production network, the relationship between actors, and the impacts, we were able to locate factors indicative of the types of policies that could strengthen these types of industries, which are listed briefly in the following paragraphs:

Agents

The firm dealt with agents who they contacted through the government organisation Sweden Export, which facilitates networks for Swedish companies looking to export their goods. These agents were instrumental in building up retailers and distributors abroad. Supporting international networks through this type of support made these types of international exports possible. Facilitating contacts and networks with the industry internationally is critical for promoting the expansion of the production network of a craft firm.

Tourism

The local municipalities have together formed a tourism organisation that promote the glass cluster to tourists. As tourism has grown to become an important part of the glass cluster, it is made possible through the specific forms of traditional artisanal production as well as made that artisanal production possible through revenue. The tourism industry supplies the glass factories with customers, who have become an increasingly important part of the cluster’s income. Facilitating the tourism industry by having a dedicated tourism organisation that facilitates collaboration as well as marketing has made this process coordinated between the firms. Collaboration between firms in a craft cluster could be improved and is something that traditional craft clusters can encourage, in addition to providing the tourism organisations with financing to perform these types of projects.

Education

The local cluster has had a supply of new talent through the only national school dedicated to craft glass manufacturing. Between the school and the factories, close collaboration existed, where

students were at times invited to develop artistic glass projects, some of which were incorporated into the production of the factory. The glass school is a costly investment for the municipalities, as they are small and receive no government support. This investment meant that the school can continue to supply the cluster with educated craftspeople who are already locally embedded in the region.

Support in times of crisis

The COVID-19 pandemic hit the industry hard, as the drop in international tourists and the lockdown measures taken in countries where distributors and retailers were located meant that a large part of the industry's revenues were lost, and more than half of the staff were dismissed. The craftspeople were especially difficult to let go of as their niche skill set developed over years would be difficult to replace once the pandemic was over. Nevertheless, the firm survived and continues production today, but building up to the size that it was before the pandemic will be difficult, even as tourists re-emerge, as the niche skill sets of the craftspeople now are lost to the firm. Even though the firm has collaborations with the national glass school in the area and could potentially attract new staff from there, the years of experience lost will take time to build up again. Understanding the specificity of highly skilled work within this industry could be one avenue for supporting sectors such as this one in times of crisis, so that the rebuilding phase can be more efficient.

3.4.7 Final remarks

The glass factory's production network is an example of a vertically integrated craft activity, where there is a clear lead firm that influences the structure of the network. Surrounding this network are a number of supportive actors who facilitate the distribution of goods towards clients both nationally and internationally. The glass factory and the cluster within which it is embedded have transformed during the 20th century, from an area of mass production to an area of artistically driven artisanal craftsmanship that has built a tourism economy. Said economy is facilitated by supportive actors, such as Export Sweden and the municipality driven tourism organisation that facilitates tourists experiencing the creation of artisanal craft products and then purchasing them. The focus of the production that remains in the area has become more artistically driven throughout the previous century, and today no mass manufacturing exists in the area. Being able to produce artistically driven crafted objects is made possible through tourists who want to experience and consume authentic, traditional crafted goods.

PART 4. Conclusions

4.1 Conclusions

Craft is a world in constant evolution and the incredible diversity that characterises it is synonymous with complexity and extraordinary richness. The European craft industry encompasses a wide range of activities that combine tradition, heritage, culture, skill, and design. **This industry is an asset for many European countries as it contributes, in its different forms, to strengthening the productive, economic, social, and cultural identity of the EU.** Indeed, it represents an essential component of the system of SMEs that constitute the backbone of the EU economy. The industry exhibits relevant dynamics of transformation – namely the possibility of overcoming local markets, the digitalisation of production processes and of distribution, and the drive for sustainability – and provides proof of vitality and adaptability. **It deals with an industry that, despite the challenges it faces, maintains a key role in the continent’s economy and society.**

The adoption of the GPN perspective for the craft industry has primarily allowed the identification of the architecture of the relationships among the economic actors involved in the realisation of a craft product, and secondarily the detection of the modalities through which value is created, enhanced, and appropriated along the network with social and economic implications. This approach has made it possible to observe craft in its complexity and entirety, focusing on the flows of resources and the relationships that characterise all segments of the input–output structure, including those that are usually neglected in the academic literature. The adoption of such a perspective has therefore brought some conceptual and empirical novelty to the field.

First, it seems clear that **craft activities encompass an extremely wide variety of concrete practices, which are difficult to capture through existing definitions.** Craft refers to its most traditional forms – namely artistic and heritage crafts – but it also extends to different areas of manufacturing of which it is an essential component. In this research, an *artisanal imprint* has emerged – one could call it *artisanship* – even in the context of semi-industrial productions characterised by limited quality batches, such as in the yachting and glass industries, but also in the food and beverage industry. In these cases, **the character of crafts is ensured by the substantial aspects of production and work more than by formal features of the craft business,** namely a deep-rooted connection with locales, the prevalence of manual work, the skills that settle over time, a deep knowledge of production techniques and materials, production flexibility and timeliness, and the ability to fully satisfy customers’ requests and create products which respond to both aesthetic and functional standards, among others. These characteristics sustain the European Economic and Social Committee’s insight when it asserted that “the concept of crafts is an *issue* that needs to be dealt with. We must think about craft companies as having the entrepreneurial value of custom manufacturing. As such, the size of a company should not determine whether it can be (legally) classified as a craft company”.

Second, the industry displays different types of governance models in which the role of artisans is valued differently and is differently rewarded, subordinated to differentiated power dynamics. Third, the industry is affected by substantial changes. Among them, it faces a demand for sustainability and technical innovation that pose great challenges for the achievement of a balance between tradition and innovation.

Despite its variety in terms of possible business models and new sectoral trends, the evidence from this research points to the continued relevance of traditional mechanisms of reputation and trust that characterise the various business practices, and also the ones that are semi-industrial in their character and seem to qualify all of the phases along the production networks. Equally crucial is to highlight that craft activities produce critical economic and especially social tangible and intangible impacts, among which is the nurturing of both the local and European collective identity. Their positive impact is also indirect as, for instance, they activate complementary industries such as tourism. In this respect, this research has confirmed the importance of the craft industry for the local development of European countries, particularly in rural regions.

In addition, the GPN perspective has allowed us to appreciate the geographical reach of the craft networks investigated. While having an international and European footprint, the specific craft activities of two of these networks appear to be concentrated in clusters or districts that permit the seizure of economies of scope, scale, and proximity and of the special industrial atmosphere of Marshallian memory. The GPN perspective has also highlighted the geographical embeddedness of knowledge and skill, where areas that contain these artisanal clusters have over decades, and even centuries, developed infrastructure, educational institutions, and local know-how, anchoring these industries in one place and making them difficult to substitute to other regions.

This research has nonetheless raised several critical points. First, although **artisans and craft enterprises** are generally indicated as key actors for value creation and the realisation of high-quality products (which is particularly the case for luxury products), they do not seem to harvest adequate material and symbolic compensations for their work. As for the material aspects, even in the context of a symmetrical distribution of power throughout the production network, artisans and craft enterprises seem to be the weakest nodes of the chain, which see customers or lead firms maintain a decisive role; their capacity to negotiate an adequate economic reward is heavily compromised.

Artisans also face another dilemma that opposes the aspiration to conduct quality production and the pressure coming from heightened production rhythms and, often, unfair competition. The articulation of the production network involving subcontracting activities raises serious concerns not only in terms of working conditions and rights but also in terms of the sustainability of the small economic companies involved. For self-employed craftspeople, although they do not face competition from subcontractors, the high levels of competitiveness in the crafts market and lack of platforms for distributing this specific form of creative practice often translate to low revenue streams, or self-exploitative tendencies through charging too little for the products created. From a social perspective,

this also implies a difficult negotiation of their identity: To what extent do artisans matter for luxury brands, larger firms, and customers? More generally, the significant transformations investing the industry in terms of technical and social innovation allow one to consider this question with the complementary lens of its reproduction: How can the industry reconcile artisans' traditional know-how and new trends and dynamics required by the market? As anticipated, such questions require a rethinking of **the role of education and professional training**.

Additionally, despite the positive rhetoric involving the industry and its artisanal nature, a reality appears clear that attains the economic dimension: the evidence from the fieldwork suggests how **craftspeople and craft enterprises are engaged in a competitiveness race** in an economic scenario which is no longer limited to local markets nor to local actors' competition and in the search of a new equilibrium between tradition and innovation. For many, **sustainability might be the new cleavage around which the competitive equilibrium on which the next few years will be built**. The craftspeople who were self-employed and influenced the entirety of the production network were also perceived as being in a competitiveness race, even though they had no employer to share their revenues with. Mass-manufacturing and the abundance of active craftspeople make reputation building imperative to the viability of craftspeople' ability to make revenues from their production. Highlighting the specific values of artistically driven crafts became one such strategy for the craftspeople to distinguish the production value of their crafted objects as well as the increased interest in sustainable production.

To remain competitive and sustainable, craftspeople and craft enterprises demand more adequate and tailored policy interventions. This includes the request for **substantial interventions in the fields of employment, grants, and training/skills** (enterprises blame excessive tax burdens on labour and demand more attention to the recruitment of new generations of artisans) as well as the valorisation of the quality contributions they make. In this respect, this research highlights the limited capacity to articulate network-related policies as the fragmentation of interests often prevails by penalising the whole industry.

Finally, due to the breadth of the industry and the variety of different activities it entails – where the manufacturing process and technique (rather than the final product) constitute an intrinsic part of the value of the goods – the industry easily becomes invisible for successful policy interventions. As demonstrated in the statistical overview, capturing an accurate understanding is near impossible as the existent statistical codes are geared towards typical manufacturing industries, even though it is possible to make an estimation of the size of the industry. The European- and national-level codes and the variety of local definitions of the term “crafts” mean that the specificity of craftpersonship is lost and the industry is difficult to distinguish. The lack of visibility of the industry makes it easily overlooked, to the detriment of workers and potential impacts of production networks. As the cases of the yacht industry and the traditional glass production site highlight, differentiating these types of workers from more standardised forms of production is key. Craft clusters, such as those represented in this study, are deeply dependent on the local conditions at hand, and thus, on unique configurations

that are near impossible to replace. When the expertise of craftspeople is lost, as in the glass industry, these skills are difficult to replace and decade's worth of skills are lost, making the industry susceptible to crisis in ways that other manufacturing sectors are not. The invisibility of the craft industry is also further emphasised in the artistic craft industry, which is often caught between fine arts and traditional making, without the access to distribution platforms afforded to those in fine arts. Understanding the unique nature of craftpersonship and raising awareness around these specific forms of making among potential consumers are key for the industry to be understood as a industry in its own right. The European craft industry offers unique impacts in its local nodes, creating employment, tourism, deep material skills, and local identities. Moreover, acknowledging and lifting the craft industry as a specific form of creative making, different from other types of arts or manufacturing, are key for successful policy making.

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- https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/creative-europe/node_en

Appendix A. Methodology

A1. Research methodology

Introduction

The general aim of the CICERONE research, and in particular of WP2, is to understand the role of Cultural and Creative Sector (CCS) in the local development of EU countries starting from the configuration and dynamics of their global production networks (GPNs). This work package is based on a case study approach combining quantitative with qualitative research. The former is aimed at positioning the sector along a number of dimensions, while the latter will uncover the more in-depth aspects of the GPNs of the selected industries. While the project adopts a prevailing qualitative approach, it also envisages secondary data analysis. The case study approach is coherent with the research aim because of its ability to cover both the phenomenon and its context.

This appendix presents the main methodological issues of the WP2, some of which have been pointed to at the beginning of the reports.

Methodology stands for the systematic examinations of procedures and modalities of explanation that are used for the analysis of empirical data⁸⁰.

In social sciences, empirical research may adopt a descriptive or an explorative logic; however, all research is always informed by a theoretical apparatus, even though the connection between theory and empirical research takes different connotations in the different disciplines/fields.⁸¹ Notably, epistemology draws a distinction between explanation and comprehension. Explanation implies the search for a stable nexus of causality between two (or more) variables, independently from the social and historical context. The underlying assumption is that we should be able to identify universal laws explaining the nature of observations (like in the so-called hard sciences). Comprehension refers to the traditional Weberian conception of understanding the meaning of the action for social actors. Such a meaning is influenced by institutional, normative and cultural dimensions that are spatially and historically specific. Reality is not simply described, but it is read, analyzed and interpreted.

In a situation where universal laws are inapplicable, the logic is to search for empirical generalizations. In order to move towards empirical generalization, social sciences make use of models or typologies

⁸⁰ Selvin, H. C. (1958). Durkheim's suicide and problems of empirical research. *American journal of sociology*, 63(6), 607-619.

⁸¹ Rueschemeyer D. (2009) Usable Theory: Analytic Tools for Social and Political Research.

starting from Weberian insights. Weber describes ideal types as ‘mental constructs, formed by the analytical and one-sided ‘accentuation of one or more points of view and by the synthesis of a great many diffuse, discrete, more or less present and occasionally absent concrete individual phenomena, which are arranged according to those one-sidedly emphasized viewpoints into a unified analytical construct’.⁸² Through ideal types, reality is recomposed and synthesized starting from classificatory categories, so to help researchers to identify dynamics and mechanisms that underlie social processes.

Traditionally, empirical research is based on either qualitative or quantitative methods (or both). The distinction between the two has a technical nature: the choice depends on many elements, such as the research questions, data availability or the approach that drives it.

The choice of the method: the case study

Among many qualitative methodologies, case study research investigates in-depth into a real-life phenomenon by considering its situatedness and contextual embeddedness.⁸³ Such a case can be an individual, a group, an organization, an event, a problem, or an anomaly.⁸⁴ Contrary to the quantitative logic, the case is chosen because it is of interest⁸⁵ or for theoretical reasons.⁸⁶ Unlike experiments, the contextual conditions are not delineated and/or controlled but are part of the investigation.

In the case study methodology, the selection of cases is a crucial phase, and generalization of results is mostly based on that. There are two modalities to select case studies:⁸⁷ random and information-oriented selection. Random selection is usually chosen to avoid systematic biases in the sample; in such circumstances, the sample size is decisive for generalization.

In social science research, cases are generally not randomly selected because it is difficult to in depth explore a huge sample. Moreover, random selection not necessarily provides informative cases, while in a research based on information-oriented selection of cases, the generalizability of results can be increased by the strategic selection of cases. As Flyvbjerg claims:

“When the objective is to achieve the greatest possible amount of information on a given problem or phenomenon, a representative case or a random sample may not be the most appropriate strategy. This is because the typical or average case is often not the richest in

⁸² Weber, [1904] in Rossi P. (1974)(ed.) *Lo storicismo contemporaneo*. Loescher, Torino: 124-125.

⁸³ Ridder, H.G. (2017). The theory contribution of case study research designs. *Business Research*, 10(2), 281-305.

⁸⁴ Burawoy, M. (2009). *The extended case method: Four countries, four decades, four great transformations, and one theoretical tradition*. Univ of California Press; Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London; Yin, R. K. (2014). *Case Study Research Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA

⁸⁵ Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London

⁸⁶ Eisenhardt, K. M., & Graebner, M. E. (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), 25-32.

⁸⁷ Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2).

information. Atypical or extreme cases often reveal more information because they activate more actors and more basic mechanisms in the situation studied.”⁸⁸

Information-oriented selection of cases implies that case studies are selected based on the expectations about their insights into processes, agency, strategies (information content). The experiment in hard sciences can also be seen as an extreme example of information-oriented selected case studies.

“Carefully chosen experiments, cases, and experience were also critical to the development of the physics of Newton, Einstein, and Bohr, just as the case study occupied a central place in the works of Darwin, Marx, and Freud. In social science, too, the strategic choice of case may greatly add to the generalizability of a case study”^{.89}

Cases bring new knowledge either because they have a strategic importance in relation to the general problem or because they help to test the validity of the theory. Moreover, case studies allow cross-country comparison: the different contexts shed light on different dynamics related to economic circumstances, national and local regulatory framework, labour market, local culture and know-how, and so on. According to Robinson⁹⁰ the choice of the territory assumed as the basis of the comparison (being it a nation, region or city) should be carefully chosen in relation to the single case study rather than assumed a priori.

Research design and research steps

As said, WP2 is based on a mixed methods approach of investigation. This means using both quantitative and qualitative tools; primary and secondary data allow a complex research design composed by several interconnected research dimensions: a sector description, an analysis for the identification of the case studies and the case studies themselves.

Industry description

Quantitative data was used to have a factual overview of European GPNs in CCS together with literature and desk analysis.

Literature analysis and quantitative (secondary) data were used to explore and describe the features of each sector, its quantitative consistence and its European production network, its role in the European economy, the territorial distribution of its companies and the typical business models.

⁸⁸ *Ibid.* p.229

⁸⁹ *Ibid.* p226

⁹⁰ Robinson, J. (2011). Cities in a world of cities: The comparative gesture. *International journal of urban and regional research*, 35(1), 1-23.

1. Literature review – for each industry
 - a. Configuration of the Production Network (input-output structure) in the selected industry
 - b. Prevailing governance typology in each industry (e.g. power relationships, barriers to entry, value adding mechanisms, labour processes/skills ...) + possible governance typologies considering single interfirm relationships
 - c. Key socio-institutional dimensions affecting network configuration/dynamics (e.g. fiscal incentives, property rights, labour legislation, path dependent cultural aspects) at various levels (European, national, regional)
 - d. (possible) Changes over time (e.g. digitalisation, technologies, ...) + possible firms upgrading processes (value capture strategies)
 - e. (possible) National variations and specificities (e.g. national funds that support the film industry)

Statistical mapping of production network of CCS in Europe

Statistical data at the EU level (by Nuts 1, 2, 3 if possible) on number of firms, employment, VA, ... relative to the *different network phases* (e.g. creation, production, distribution, etc.) composing the Production Networks of the 8 selected CCIs.

Case studies in WP2

One of the strengths of the research lies in the fact that the great variety of case studies share a common unit of analysis. This is the production network of actors, firms, organisations involved in projects, which is very much in line with a whole body of literature on forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. According to Watson (2012, p. 168), the benefits of a such project-based approach are:

“... first it moves beyond [solely] structural analyses to allow for an understanding of the importance of agency in project work; second it allows us to move on from firm-level analyses to develop an understanding of the complex social networks involved in [production networks]; and finally it moves on from research at the meso-level on inter- and intra-firm networks to provide micro-level analyses of project work.”⁹¹

Such an approach enabled the whole research to take into account agency *and* structure as well as their interaction, thereby heeding the view of Powell and Smith Doerr⁹² who conceptualise networks both as relational forms and structural ones.

⁹¹ Watson, A. (2012). Sociological Perspectives on the Economic Geography of Projects: The Case of Project-Based Working in the Creative Industries. *Geography Compass*, 6(10), 617-631, p. 618.

⁹² Smith-Doerr L, Powell W (2005) Networks and Economic Life. In Neil Smelser and Richard Swedberg, eds. *The Handbook of Economic Sociology*, Russell Sage Foundation and Princeton University Press.

As anticipated in *The Cicerone approach to production networks* section of this report, cases were selected on the basis of their informative power and of the theoretical expectations about their insights. Particularly, case studies represent a sufficient range of variation in terms of key business model characteristics, geographical span within the EU limits and cross the borders of European countries, finally and obviously they are accessible to researchers.

Such choices aim at bringing new knowledge on the contribution of the European CCS to local development, sustainability, social cohesion and (local) identity. Furthermore, as already discussed, an information-oriented selection of case studies increases the generalizability of results.

In details, theoretically based case study selection was grounded on the review of the existing literature on CCS and their organizational forms⁹³ assuming a novel viewpoint. Three common aspects underlie this choice.

- a) GPNs in the CCS, as in any other industries, are characterized by differential power relations. Powerful actors (the lead firm) are those who drive networks and make things happen: as explained, their ability derives from their control of key resources, namely physical, economic, technological but also social, political and immaterial ones. The control of resources however does not automatically imply that the actor is powerful until power is exercised. Rather than being matter of actors' position in the network (more or less marginal actors), power should be conceived as the capacity to concretely exercise control within it. Governance identifies the authority and power relationships that affect how resources – material, financial, human, etc. – are distributed and flow along the chain. Following Gereffi it is possible to distinguish between two typologies of networks: the producers- and the buyer- driven chains. Governance as drivenness embraces a broad idea whereby governance refers to the whole chain dynamics: this concept is meant to capture the power that lead firms exert over other participants and to highlight its ability to govern the chain by making decisions about where, how and by whom goods/services are produced. In the identification of concrete governance typologies characterising a specific sector, the concept of governance as drivenness is one important aspect⁹⁴.
- b) Relationships between lead firms and the other actors in the network differ across industries due to the particular features of the products/services produced, to the production process and the organization of that specific industry. The configuration and coordination of global production networks are also shaped by the expansion of demand and markets. Goods and services' demand needs to be created and sustained by final consumers and end users (i.e. think about the increased role of merchandising). It is therefore important to satisfy customer pressures, (i.e. price, quality), the so-called time to market (i.e. time imperative) as well as the

⁹³ Different disciplinary insights have been gathered from literature in business, economics, sociology, economic geography.
⁹⁴ Greco, L. (2016) *Capitalismo e sviluppo nelle reti globali del valore*. Carocci, Roma.

basic access to the market and to new markets (i.e. in emerging economies). Finally, the choices and strategies of production networks are also influenced by financial considerations, which relate both to firms' activities and to their shift to non-manufacturing ones. Such aspects refer more to technical, organizational dimensions and demand that are shaped primarily by the industries' internal logic.

- c) As underlined, the innovativeness of the CICERONE project lies in the application of the GPNs perspective to the CCSs. Whilst a vast array of studies has concerned the manufacturing industry, considerably less attention has been devoted to the cultural and creative sector. The empirical work required by the project intended primarily to make a contribution to the understanding of the CCS considered by the project at European level. Nonetheless, the empirical research aimed also to account for the broad institutional context in which production networks operate. Institutions do not only influence chains' dynamics but should be considered constitutive of these networks in ways that are critical for understanding their social and economic consequences: institutions were therefore not be considered external to the networks even though they are not strictly connected to inter-firms' relationships.

For each industry, case studies numbers range between two to four, according to the identified typologies, complexity of the case studies, availability of interviewees and so on.

Case study analysis

The empirical research based on case studies (namely the production network of projects) was carried on through the exploration of the single network-nodes and their relationships. Qualitative data was used to produce novel knowledge in the field and constitute the base for further research.

The explicative power of the selected case studies lies in the fact that the analysis is able to produce a 'substantive' representativeness of the EU CCS rather than their statistical one; in other words, case studies analysis allows understanding dynamics, mechanisms, relationships, etc. useful for explaining the functioning of such sector.

After selecting case studies, the empirical investigation was carried out using interviews, observations, ethnographies, digital ethnographies. The key dimensions of the analysis are: the network configuration and its geographical footprint; the governance dimension (power relations; value creation); the variety of embeddedness forms; the impact on socio-economic development.

As already indicated, production networks are socially and territorially embedded, beyond their organizational embeddedness. Societal embeddedness places economic actions within a multilevel institutional and cultural framework. Territorial embeddedness appreciates the differing ways in which firms are anchored to different places and to its specific resources and features, for instance the local culture, labour forces, policies, raw materials and so on. Ultimately CCS industrial dynamics

in Europe was analysed both in their ideal-typical sense (by accounting for the specific sector-level characteristics affecting inter-firm linkages) and with concern to the differentially embedded nature of their economic activities. Attention was paid also to the ways in which actors mobilize and deploy resource, forge alliance, shape regulatory structures through discursive constructions and mechanisms that legitimate the GPN configuration, i.e. eco labels, fair trade, ethical labour, environmentally friendly productions, etc. Consideration was also devoted to any relevant policy (or the lack of it) at the different stages in chain, which may affect the way in which the whole chain is configured. Policy analysis has looked at different kind of policies, i.e. cultural but also industrial as well as regulatory and trade policies. Additionally, policy and policy environment were addressed in their multiscale nature.

A unifying matrix focusing on the two key dimensions of governance (power) and spatial footprint allowed synthesizing the case study results by conducting a series of comparisons in different contexts. In addition, the systematization in the matrix is designed as a tool for policymakers in support of better CCS-relevant policies.

Research strategy

Preparing the interview

For each node of the production network, interviews were made to all the informed people that were considered suitable to understand the mechanisms at play in the node. The number of interviews was decided by each team according to the availability of interviewees and the information to be gathered. Three or four pilot interviews were recommended in order to recalibrate / reorganise the interview script; in some cases, interviewees were not available for the interview, but they were asked a number of key questions via mail: this solution was adopted if no alternative was possible. Empirically, the field was accessed through a company, which represents a node/phase in the network; starting from that, the whole network (both relations among phases and phases themselves) has been explored.

At the beginning of each interview, the interviewer presented him/herself and presented the research. The interviewee was given a leaflet containing information on the research as well as on the specific role that the EU can play in this field. After the signature of a consent form on the part of the interviewee, the interviewer started recording the interview. Interviews were done in person or in videoconference when the situation required it.

Each case study gathered qualitative data on a number of topics, which are detailed in the next section containing the interview outline, namely

- The interviewee profile
- The organization profile
- The network configuration

- The governance structure and strategies
- The embeddedness
- Policy
- Contribution to development

Qualitative data gathering

All interviewees allowed recording the interview with digital recorder. Interviews were then transcribed *verbatim*, pointing out emotional status only if particularly relevant.

Each interview was labelled and stored using all the following variables:

- Industry
- # case study
- Phase of the production cycle
- # interview (within the phase)
- Geography (Nuts3)
- # interview (within the industry)
- Date (DD/MM/YY)

Interviews coding

A two-step codification was used:

- 1) Codification of the interview according to the homogeneous excerpts on the basis of thematic areas identified for the research:
 - Network configuration → CODE: NET-CON
 - Spatial organization of the networks → CODE: GEO
 - The governance of the network → CODE: GOVERN
 - Embeddedness → CODE: EMBEDD
 - Institutional conditions → CODE: INSTIT
 - Policy → CODE: POLICY
 - Contribution of the production network to the development of European regions → CODE: EU_DEVELOP
 - Any other relevant issue that we might "discover" → CODE: OTHER
- 2) Codification of all the excerpts in each of the previously identified thematic areas (input-output structure, its spatial organisation, governance, institutional conditions, role in the EU development, other) based on relevant analytical categories.
 - Ex. Mechanisms of value appropriation; modalities of cooperation among organisations; upgrading mechanisms, working conditions, social/cultural embeddedness; any other new element

A2. Interview outline

Profiling the case study

A first step in the interview outline was to profile the interviewee and her or his organization, company, or agency.

Interviewee's profile

Themes to analyse:

- Position within the organization/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the position
- Main responsibilities
- Years spent in the organization/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the industry
- Years spent in the field
- Competences required for the job
- Any other relevant theme

- What is your job position within the organisation/agency/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this position?
- What are your main responsibilities?
- How many years have you been working in this organisation/agency?/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this industry?
- What are the main skills/competences required for your job?

Organisation profile

Themes to analyse:

- Brief history of the organisation
- Core business
- Legal nature of company
- Employees
- Any other relevant theme

- What does your organization/agency/company/etc. do/develop?
- What is the main activity performed by your company/organization/agency/etc.?
- What is your core business?
- Is your organization/agency/company/etc. independent or is it a part of a bigger company? (if yes) how responsibilities with the headquarter are distributed?
- How many employees does your organisation/agency/company have?
- Can you briefly tell me about your or organisation/agency/company? (*gather some information on its history, key moments, etc.*)

Network configuration

The second step of the interview outline aimed at shedding light on the whole cycle of cultural production from creation to final users (actors involved, roles, geography). In what ways is the industry X articulated/organised? How does the division of labour occur in the industry? Who are the main actors? Their roles? The geography?

The sketch of a diagram together with the interviewee can be a very useful tool at this stage: we suggest to use a large sheet of paper and start with the interviewee in the middle; then add the other organisations/agencies/actors/... involved in the different phases (locate the phases at the corners of the paper). Use this diagram as a map throughout the whole interview.

- Among the projects (services/activities/goods/event) that you briefly presented us, let us consider now the chosen one (possibly it should be one that involves an extended/extra-local/European/international network). Please, help us to identify the whole cycle of cultural production and your role in it.
- Who are the actors that are involved, together with you, in the carrying out of your project (i.e., customers, intermediaries, consumers/audiences, etc.)?

Actors involved

Possible actors involved:

- Artists, composers, designers, creatives
- Producers
- Suppliers, impresarios
- Audience, customers
- Intermediaries, dealers, experts, critics
- Media, influencers
- Archivists
- Any other relevant actor

Themes to analyse for each actor:

- Description of the actors
(Who they are? Big or small organizations/groups, independent, subsidiaries...)
- Role played by the actor in the network
- Type of resources mobilized (financial, economic, reputational, technological resources...)
- Any other relevant theme

- Who do you work with?
- Who are the people that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Who are the suppliers that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Can you tell us more about them?
- (i.e. SME / large organizations, public/private, local/global, independent/subsidiaries, etc.)
- What kind of resources do they mobilize in the project?

- (i.e. a service, an idea, technical or professional knowledge, raw materials, a semi-product, a final product, financial assets, etc.)
- Who are your customers? or your audience?
- Do you sell directly to the final consumer?
- Are there any actors in your business that you would define as intermediaries? Why? For instance, because they help your product/you to be visible, or they “translate” your work for the audience, or they appreciate particularly your work.
- Is there anybody that helps you in promoting your products/projects? (e.g. art curators, advisors, critics, etc.)
- Do they have an impact on your business? How?
- What do they do precisely?
- What does their intermediation consist of?
- Could you give me an example of a situation in which intermediaries were useful to your business?
- How did you come in contact with this intermediary?
- How did they find you?
- Has your relationship with intermediaries changed over time? Why?
- Do media and influencers play a role in your business?
- How do they impact on your activities?
- How do they get to know you?
- Let us consider the social media. Are there any influencers on Instagram/Facebook/etc. that have an impact on your strategies/activities?
- Have your own accounts an impact?
- Do you use them to promote your project?
- Have you or has your organisation got an archive of your projects (creations/services/activities/products)?
- Have you or has your organisation been part of a show/exhibition/etc.?
- Does collecting exist as a practice in your business?
- (If yes), Who are the collectors? Does a collecting market exist?
- Who decides on what will be archived and in which form?
- Have your projects ever been part of a collection?
- Are there any museums/institutions particularly important in your sector that collect major/innovative works?

Spatial organisation

Themes to analyse:

- The geography of the network
- The issue of physical distance
- The management of distance (if relevant)
- The management of communication (if relevant)
- Any other relevant theme

- Where are the actors/organisations of the network located? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- (consider all the phases of the PN)
- Have you ever experienced any problem due to the distance? (for instance, dealing with something implying face-to-face communication; the need to check a process personally; ...)

- How do you communicate with the different actors in the network?
- Do you need to travel a lot?
- How is the geographical distance managed?

Governance

What kind of relationships govern and regulate the network organization in the Industry X? What are the economic, socio-institutional, political aspects affecting inter-firms' dynamics?

Relations among network organisations

Themes to analyse:

- Type of relationships between actors (formal/informal)
- Decision-making process concerning the project. (who decides, autonomy / cooperation / subordination, participation)
- Existence of standards / conventions to follow
- Resources: type of resources that the interviewee can mobilise, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ... type of resources that the interviewee needs, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ...

- What's your role in the network?
- What [actor/organisation x's] role in the network? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- How do your customers/suppliers/partners/... choose you?
- How did your customers/suppliers/partners/... get to know you?
- What are your relationships with customers/suppliers/partners/... based on?
- (i.e. trust, competences, flexibility, quality, price, uniqueness, etc.)
- Has your relationship with customers/suppliers/partners/... changed over time? Why?
- Has your relationship with your customer(s)/audience impacted on your business in terms of production/profit growth, number of people working in the company/organization/agency/etc., visibility, etc. Could you quantify it?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide you with standard projects?
- Have you ever asked them to customise their products for you?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that are difficult to find?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that only they are able to provide you?
- Have you ever developed a project together with suppliers/partners?
- How do you select your suppliers/partners?
- How did your suppliers/partners get to know you?
- Have you ever had any problems with suppliers/partners? how did you solve them?
- Has your relationship with suppliers changed over time? Why?
- Do you have direct relationships with the consumers/audience of your project?
- (if yes) How do you manage it?
- Does audience/final consumer participate in your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes? How?
- How important are audience/consumers' preferences/judgments for your projects/business/activity?

- Does their judgment affect your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes?
- How are your relations with your customers/suppliers/partners/...regulated/governed?
- (i.e. formal agreements, informal accords, individual contracts, codes of conducts, etc.)
- Have you got any exclusive agreement with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- Does it include non-disclosure clauses?
- Does it include the use/concession of technologies/knowledge that are protected by (any kind of) agreement that you cannot use/replicate for other processes?
- (If yes) what kind of agreement?
- Who decides how to create/produce/develop/make/provide/etc. the project that you carry out?
- Does your customers/suppliers/partners/...participate in such a process?
- Do you have a say in such a process?
- Has your customers/suppliers/partners/... their own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Do you have your own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Can you/your customers/suppliers/partners/... negotiate terms and conditions of the creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving/etc. process?
- Is there any quality standard to be respected in such a process?
- What are the consequences in case of non-compliance with the contract/standard?
- Do you envisage any kind of reward for your best suppliers? What does it consist of?
- Do you have any knowledge of the destination of the project (service/activity/good) that you produce/ create/develop/make/provide/etc.?
- In your opinion, how easy would it be for you to replace your other customers/suppliers/partners/...with others?
- In your opinion, how easy would it be for your customers/partners/... to replace you with other suppliers/partners?
- What do you/ does your company/organization/agency do better than others in your industry?
- What is your specific asset/advantage with respect to others?
- How important is reputation in your business? What elements are crucial for it?
- How do you build your reputation?
- How do you make yourself/your organization/agency/company known?
- Have there been any crucial moments in your organization' history/your career that have changed your reputation?
- Have there been any people that have been particularly important for your career/your organization' growth?

Price and value

Themes to analyse:

- Mechanisms at play in the price and value formation (decisions, relevant aspects such as brand, status, reputation, production...)
- Actors involved (or excluded) in value/price formation
- Any other relevant theme

- Who decides the price of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- On the basis of what dimensions?

- (i.e. market position, competencies, reliability, reputation, brand, design, technology, etc.)
- Can you/your supplier(s)/customer(s) negotiate the price? On what basis?
- With respect to such a price do you think that your contribution is adequately rewarded?
- Could you tell us how much it costs the realization of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- How often do you receive a non-monetary reward for your work? What do you receive instead?
- Does the price of the service/activity/good that you exchange with your customer(s)/supplier(s) allow you to run your activity/business according to legal and social standards? Why/Why not?
- Do you know the final price at which the project (service/activity/good) is sold?
- In your opinion what are the elements that contribute to determine the final price of the project?
- (it might be the price of the final good, the price of the ticket of a concert/show/exhibition but also the price of the whole exhibition/festival)
- Do you think that the final price of the project is appropriate? Why?
- Do intermediaries impact on decisions about the price of your project? How?
- In your opinion does the final price of the good/service reflect its value?
- In which stage of the production cycle (refer to the diagram) is the value of the project mostly created?
- Who are the actors/organisations in the PN that gain the most from the realisation of the project? Why?

Working conditions, labour and collective actors

Themes to analyse (when applicable):

- Profile of the workforce/associates/collaborators/partners
- Recruitment process and wage definition
- Organisation of work
- Presence and role of trade unions in the organisation/agency/company/etc.
- Presence and role of trade unions and/or business/trade associations in the industry
- Any other relevant theme

- Do you have employees/collaborators/associates, etc.?
- How is your workforce composed?
- (i.e.: percentage of professionals/consultants/technicians/workers, etc. out of the total, but also percentage of women/men, percentage by ethnicity, etc.)
- How is work organized in your organization/agency/company, etc.?
- (i.e.: on projects, regular working time, piece rates, etc.)
- What types of contracts does your organization/agency/company mainly apply to them?
- (i.e.: fixed-term contracts, permanent contracts, agency staff, freelancers, consultants and contractors, etc.)
- Do they work mainly full time/part time?
- Where do they mainly work?
- (i.e. offices, ateliers, workplaces, at home, in co-working spaces, etc.)
- What aspects do you mainly consider when selecting the workforce?
- (i.e. skills, formal training and education, experience, reputation, flexibility, technical knowledge, etc.)

- Do you employ foreign professionals/workers? Why?
- Do you have internships? Do you have any specific agreement with schools/universities in this respect?
- How do you set salaries and working conditions for your workforce?
- (i.e.: collective agreements, plant level agreements, informal agreements, individual negotiation, etc.)
- Does your organization/agency/company set any productivity incentives/bonus for your workforce?
- Do workers have a say in the activity carried out by the organization/agency/company?
- Do your workers must respect any codes of conduct?
- Do your workers must respect any non-disclosure agreements/clauses?
- Are trade unions present in your organization/agency/company/etc.?
- What are their main claims?
- Have they ever helped you? When?
- Do they influence your business? How?
- (i.e. through the bargaining process, strikes, demonstrations, disputes, etc.)
- Have you had any conflicts with unions recently?
- (If yes), Could you tell me what was the issue?
- How did you negotiate your positions?
- What is the role of business associations/trade associations/etc. in your industry? (at different levels: local/regional/national/international)
- Do you participate in some of them?
- (If yes), How is this beneficial?

Skills and knowledge

Themes to analyse:

- Main skills/competencies/resources required in the industry
- Skills/competencies/resources that make the interviewee / organization crucial / important for the network.

- What kind of skills/knowledge/competencies/technologies/etc. are involved in/needed by your production/creative/distribution/etc. process?
- Do you have any specific expertise that makes you irreplaceable to your partners?
- Do you find skill/knowledge/competencies/technologies in the local labour market or do you need to acquire/buy them from abroad/very far from you/in a difficult way?
- Do you provide any training programme to your workforce? Who decides for them?
- Does/do your customer(s) play a role in such a process?
- (i.e.: sending consultants/technicians/skilled workers, organizing training programmes, etc.)

Innovation

Themes to analyse:

- Main innovations for the industry and the specific economic activity
- Impact of innovations on the cycle of production
- Impact of innovations on relationships with partners
- Impact of digitisation
- Any other relevant theme

- How do you keep yourself informed on the latest technologies/innovations/trends/etc. that are relevant for your business?
- (i.e.: fairs, contests, consultants, journals, magazines and sector publishing, etc.)
- What is the most important/recent innovation that has been introduced in your creative/production/ distribution/exchange/archive process?
- (focus on different types of innovation: product, technological, stylistic, in the distribution, ...)
- Who/what urged this innovation?
- How did this innovation impact on your business?
- (Please, explore the different implications of this innovation)
- Did it allow you to develop new organizational capabilities?
- To hire new/qualified workforce?
- To reach other customers or/and enter new/different markets/businesses/activities?
- To acquire new/better capabilities?
- How did innovation impact with your work?
- Have you been asked to acquire new skills?
- How did this innovation modify your relationships with the other actors/organisations of the network?
- Have you ever needed/solicit collaboration with schools/universities/ laboratories/education centres/etc. for developing/learn any innovation?
- (i.e. for finding skilled professionals/workforces and/or for developing new skills/competencies/knowledge)
- Is there any research centre with which you cooperate to research and develop new services/products/ideas? Are they private, public or are they the result of public-private partnership?
- Has digitalisation had an impact on your activity? How?

Embeddedness

Relations between the production network and the region

Themes to analyse:

- Resources that the territory/context offers and relevance for the activity carried out
- Advantages/disadvantages connected to the area
- Role of Institutions
- Policies
- Any other relevant theme

- What kind of resources can this territory offer to your organization/agency/company, etc.?
- (Here's a list of possible items that you may explore: know-how, traditions; logistics; skilled labour; research structures, academies and schools, innovation hubs, incubators; geography and natural resources);
- For instance, with reference to social resources:
- What kind of social resources can the community of this area offer to your company/organization/agency/etc.? (i.e. local work ethos/culture, informal relations, attitudes towards the economy, openness to innovation, diversity, social values, cultural activities, etc.)
- In what ways are they relevant for your activity?

- Do you think that the local community supports your economic activity? (If yes) In what ways?
- Would you say that it is strategic to be here? Why?
- What factors keep you here?
- Has this territory a special reputation in your industry's tradition? How do you benefit from it?
- (i.e. territorial brand that may help your activity?)
- What are the problems of the territory that impact on your organization/agency/company, etc.?
- Do institutions (regional, local authorities, ---) in this territory encourage economic initiatives in your industry? In what ways?
- Do institutions (i.e. region, local authorities, ---) encourage cultural initiatives in this area? In what ways?
- Does the economic and institutional context in which you work help/hinder your activity? How?
- (focus on fiscal requirements, industrial policies, labour regulation, environmental standards, trade policies, etc.)
- Do you think that the existing policies at regional level are adequate to the needs of your organization/agency/company?
- (focus i.e., on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, etc.)
- Do you think that the existing policies at national / international level are adequate to the needs of your organization/agency/company?
- (focus on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, trade policies, intellectual property right agreements, etc.)
- Has your organization/agency/company, etc. tried to influence policy making?
- Has your organization/agency/company, etc. benefited from policy initiatives developed in industries connected to yours?
- Do you participate in some regional-funded project/initiative?
- In your opinion what should be done at a policy level to promote/help your industry/activity?

Contribution to socio-economic development

Themes to analyse:

- Socio-economic impact of the PN on the region
- Birth/decline of new/traditional job/economic activities connected to the PN
- Birth of new professional/technical schools/courses connected to the economic activity
- Collaboration with institutions/universities/schools
- Participation of the interviewee/organisation in local cultural/social initiatives
- Economic/social/environmental sustainability
- Any other relevant theme

- Does your involvement in a network of (global) activities impact on the economy of the region you work in? In what ways? (i.e.: incomes, employment and wages, local taxation, touristic trends, etc.)

- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth/diffusion/expansion/decline of new/traditional jobs/professionals and/or economic activities connected to it?
- Has your participation in the network favoured any collaboration with universities or local schools?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth of new professional/technical schools/courses/etc. connected to your activity?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the development of local cultural and social initiatives?
- (i.e.: festival, fairs, competition and contests, community revitalization programs, urban regeneration, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network favoured the involvement of your organization/agency/company, etc. in the social life of your locality/region? (i.e.: charity initiatives, with prisons, etc.)
- Do you support/promote any local association/organization/initiative/festival/fair/sport club/etc.?
- Are you involved in any local association/club/organisation for the promotion of the local society?
- (i.e. local festival, local fairs, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the well-being of your workforce's conditions in this region? (i.e.: labour standards, diversity promotion, health and safety, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the environmental sustainability of your economic activity? (i.e.: introducing cleaner technologies, environmental sound processes, materials, etc.)
- Do you think that your business has contributed to change/improve your region's image/reputation? In what ways? (i.e.: local specializations, brand rent effect, testimonials, etc.)

Concluding session

- In your opinion, how important is your contribution to the production network you participate in?
- How do you think you are contributing to the development of local society?
- What are the main values that inspire your activity/organization?
- How do you imagine this industry in ten years' time?
- (focus on e.g. cultural hybridization, technological innovation, new markets, etc.)
- How do you imagine you/your activity in this industry in ten years' time?